

HBM4EU

science and policy
for a healthy futureHORIZON2020 Programme
Contract No. 733032 HBM4EU

Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies

Deliverable Report

D 11.3

WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers

Deadline: April 2019

Upload by Coordinator: 22 May 2019

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Abbreviations

AAMI	Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation
AENTB	Adult Environmental Neurobehavioral Test Battery
AGD	Anogenital distance
AGI	Anogenital index
Al	Aluminium
ALP	Alkaline phosphatase
ALT	Alanine transaminase
AMH	Anti-Müllerian hormone
ANSP	Santé publique France
ASQ-3	Ages and Stages Questionnaire, third edition
AST	Aspartate transaminase
AT	Austria
ATS	American Thoracic Society
BNP	Brain natriuretic peptide
BDE	Decarbomodiphenyl ether
BE	Belgium
BF	Body fat
BG	Bulgaria
BHA	Beta hydroxy acid
BMD	Bone mineral density
BMI	Body mass index
BP	Blood pressure
BPA	Bisphenol A
CAT	Computerised axial tomography
Cd	Cadmium
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CH	Switzerland
Co	Carbon monoxide
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
COPHES	Consortium to Perform Human Biomonitoring on a European Scale
Cr	Chromium
CRP	C-reactive protein

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CVD	Cardiovascular disease
CY	Cyprus
CZ	Czech Republic
DDE	Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene
DE	Germany
DEP	Azieda Sataria Locale Roma
DEXA	Dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry
DK	Denmark
DOHaD	Developmental Origins of Health and Disease
EBCT	Electron-beam computed tomography
ECG	Electrocardiogram
ECRHS	European Community Respiratory Health Survey
EDC	Endocrine disrupting chemical
EE	Estonia
EEA	European Economic Area
EHES	European Health Examination Survey
EL	Greece
ERS	European Respiratory Society
ES	Spain
ESH	European Society of Hypertension
ESTEBAN	Étude de santé sur l'environnement, la biosurveillance, l'activité physique et la nutrition
EU	European Union
FEF	Forced Expiratory Flow
FENa	Fractional excretion of sodium
FET	Forced Expiratory Time
FEV	Forced expiratory volume
FI	Finland
FIF	Forced Inspiratory Flow
FIOH	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
FMUL	Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Lisboa
FR	Flame retardants
FR	France
FVC	Forced vital capacity

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GCMS	Gas chromatography mass spectrometry
GerES	German Environmental Survey
GGT	Gamma-glutamyltransferase
GINA	Global Initiative for Asthma
GLI	Global Lung Function Initiative
GnRH	Gonadotropin-releasing hormone
GP	General practitioner
HbA _{1c}	Glycated hemoglobin
HBM4EU	Human Biomonitoring for EU
HBM	Human BioMonitoring
HCB	Hexachlorobenzene
HCH	Hexachlorocyclohexane
HDL	High density lipoprotein
HEC	Health Examination Centre
HES	Health Examination Survey
Hg	Mercury
HINE	Hammersmith Infant Neurological Examination
HHF	Hellenic Health Foundation
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography
HR	Croatia
HRV	Heart rate variability
HU	Hungary
I	Iodine
IBMT	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Angewandten Forschung E.B.
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
ICT	Information and communications technology
IE	Ireland
IFG	Impaired fasting glucose
IgE	Immunoglobulin E
IGT	Impaired glucose tolerance
IHIS	Ústav Zdrovotnických Informací a Statistiky České Republiky
IL	Israel
IMT	Intima-medial thickness
INSA	National Institute of Health Dr. Ricardo Jorge

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IOTF	International Obesity Taskforce
IPCHeM	Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring
IQ	Intelligence quotient
IS	Iceland
ISAAC	International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISS	Istituto Superiore di Sanità – The Italian National Institute of Health
IUATLD	International Union Against Tuberculosis and Lung Disease
IT	Italy
KI	Karolinska Institutet
LC-MS/MS	Liquid chromatography mass spectrometry
LD	L-lactate dehydrogenase
LDL	Low density lipoprotein
LT	Lithuania
LU	Luxembourg
LV	Latvia
MEC	Mobile Examination Centre
MIR	Magnetic resonance imaging
MMPI-R	Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory
Mn	Manganese
MOH-IL	Israel Ministry of Health
MRCQ	Medical Research Council Questionnaire
MS	Member State
MT	Malta
MUW	Medizinische Universität Wien
Na	Sodium
NCTB	Neurobehavioral Core Test Battery
NES	Neurobehavioural Evaluation System
NHANES	National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
NHC	National Hub Coordinator
NHCP	National Hub Contact Point
Ni	Nickel
NIPH	Norwegian National Institute for Public Health
NL	Netherlands

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NO	Norway
NSC-60	Neurotoxic Symptom Checklist-60
OGTT	Oral glucose tolerance test
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
Pb	Lead
PBDE	Polybrominated diphenyl ethers
PCB	Polychlorinated biphenyl
PD	Parkinson's disease
PE	Polyethylene
PEDS	Parents' evaluation of developmental status
PEF	Peak expiratory flow
PET	Positron emission tomography
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PI	Principle Investigator
PIC	Personal Identification Code
PL	Poland
POMS	Profile of Mood States Questionnaire
POP	Persistent organic pollutant
PP	Polypropylene
PR	Public Relations
PSU	Primary Sampling Unit
PT	Portugal
PT	Prothrombin time
QA	Quality Assurance
QUS	Quantitative ultrasound
RegionH	Region Hovedstaden – The Capital Region of Denmark
RO	Romania
SABA	Short acting beta2-agonist
SCORAD	SCORing Atopic Dermatitis
SD	Standard deviation
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
Se	Selenium
SE	Sweden
SES	Socioeconomic status

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SHBG	Sex hormone-binding globulin
SI	Slovenia
SK	Slovakia
SOP	Standardised Operating Procedure
SPECT	Single photon emission computerised tomography
SPT	Skin prick test
SSU	Secondary Sampling Unit
Ta	Tantalum
THL	National Institute for Health and Welfare
TINE	Touwen Infant Neurological Examination
UBA	Umweltbundesamt
UK	United Kingdom
UMU	Umeå University
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
WC	Waist circumference
WHO	World Health Organization

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Introduction

The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) is a joint effort of 28 countries (24 European Member States, three associated countries and Switzerland), the European Environment Agency and the European Commission, co-funded under Horizon 2020.

The main objective of HBM4EU is to use Human Biomonitoring (HBM) to assess human exposure to chemicals in Europe in order to better understand the associated health impacts and to improve chemical risk assessment. HBM4EU will generate knowledge on chemical exposure levels in the population and their health effects.

In parallel to HBM studies, health examination surveys (HES) are conducted in many European countries. HES are surveys where information collected by questionnaire(s) is complemented with information obtained by physical measurements such as blood pressure and anthropometric measurements, and by analysis of biomarkers from biological samples. The European Health Examination Survey (EHES)¹ was established in 2010 to coordinate the development of national HESs in Europe. Between 2000 and 2017, 15 European countries² have conducted a national HES and in many countries smaller, regional or disease specific surveys have been carried out.

Since for both HBM studies and HESs, data is collected through fieldwork, which is one of the largest expenses for such studies and needed infrastructures are very similar, the potential to combine these two types of studies has been considered. This could result in more cost-effective ways to conduct health and environmental monitoring. In some countries, such as Germany, Israel and France, this combination has already been done at national or regional level.

Human Biomonitoring and health studies have a lot of similarities in terms of the infrastructure and procedures required for their implementation. However, in practice, the opportunity for adding a HBM module to an ongoing/planned health study (and vice versa) is rarely used. Reasons for this may be multifarious and may differ from country to country, and between different study settings.

This report will look at different aspects related to combining HBM and health studies, together with possibilities for mortality and morbidity follow-up through linkage to administrative registers. This report will also provide information about identified and possible health effects related to the chemical exposures and how to directly measure those health effects. WP14 has worked in more detail on effect biomarkers for different health effects.³ Therefore, this report has four main parts:

- Part A. Opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies
- Part B. Availability of administrative registers and possibilities for their use in HBM studies
- Part C. Measuring potential health effects of the priority substances
- Part D. SOPs for selected health measurements.

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Part A. Opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies

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2 Background

Task 11.1 aims to evaluate the opportunities and obstacles of combining ongoing and/or planned health studies (health examination surveys (HES), cohort studies, dietary surveys, occupational studies, etc.) and HBM studies. An inventory of the recently conducted, ongoing and planned health studies, which could be linked to an HBM study, was performed in 2017 and updated in 2018. For this, 2 to 5 studies per participating country were identified by the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs), coordinated by the National Hub Coordinator (NHC). The inventory also includes information about existing biological samples collected in these studies and stored in biobanks for future use.

The settings for conducting HES and/or HBM differ from country to country and the experience from countries where a combination of HBM and HES has already been conducted successfully may therefore not be directly transferable to other countries. It is therefore important to include also studies from countries where HBM and/or health studies are generally conducted in different settings (e.g. national funded studies vs. research driven studies funded by grants).

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3 Objective

The present evaluation serves as an update to Deliverable D11.1⁴ published in January 2018. The overall aim of the evaluation was to identify opportunities and obstacles related to linking HBM, health surveys and administrative data sources, and to create an inventory of the health studies among the 28 countries involved in HBM4EU available, which could include an HBM component. In the current evaluation, an update of included health surveys has been performed compared to the previous report.

Specific objectives are:

- a) To create an inventory of the recently completed, ongoing and planned health studies which could be linked to HBM studies;
- b) To gather information about existing biological samples collected in the health studies and stored in biobanks for future use;
- c) To collect information about whether the ethical approvals for the studies cover the use of the available biological samples for HBM;
- d) To assess possible opportunities and obstacles related to combining HBM and health studies.

In the following, an update will be given related to objectives a-c. However, objective d will not be further evaluated as it was already reported in 2018 in Deliverable D11.1 and during the update, no new combined HBM and health studies were identified.

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4 Methods

A detailed description of the methods has previously been given in Deliverable 11.1. In short, an electronic questionnaire was developed targeted to principal investigators on recently conducted, ongoing or planned health studies that potentially could add an HBM component (Figure 1). The questionnaire was sent out in two distribution rounds. In the first round, principal investigators (PI) of HES or HBM studies were identified by the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) to identify the studies of interest in the respective countries. Out of the 28 national hubs, information on PIs was obtained from 16 countries with more than one identified PI from several of the included countries. The questionnaire was distributed to the identified PIs from each of the countries in July 2017 (Figure 1). The data obtained from the 16 countries were summarised in Deliverable 11.1.

Figure 1: Time line of the development and distribution of questionnaire 11.1

To increase the study sample and to expand the number of countries represented in the survey, a second invitation round was conducted. The second invitation round was primarily targeted against NHCPs in countries from which no information was obtained in the first round. In addition, a screening of relevant studies reported in the questionnaire developed in WP7.1 was performed and PIs from identified studies were subsequently invited to participate in the survey. In cases where no PIs from a specific country were identified, an invitation was directly sent to the NHCP in the given country. In addition to the 52 responses from 16 countries obtained from the first round, another 9 responses from 3 countries were included in the second round. Results based on the expanded dataset are given below.

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5 Results

5.1 Analysis of data from the WP11, Task 11.1 questionnaire

5.1.1 Number of studies reported

In total, 61 different studies were reported as being conducted or planned to be initiated after the second round of invitations. In the first invitation round 16 different countries were represented among the studies that were reported out of the 19 PIs initially invited to the study. In the second invitation round a total of 19 countries⁵ were represented out of PIs from all 28 countries involved in HBM4EU. The geographic distribution across Europe after the first and second invitation round is visualised in Figure 2A and 2B, respectively.

Figure 2: Distribution of the countries from which data was reported (in red) after A) the first invitation round and B) the second invitation round

One of the objectives of Task 11.1 is to evaluate the existing biological samples collected in health studies and stored in biobanks for future use. However, PIs from 4 studies reported that biological samples were not collected at the time of the questionnaire response and it was either reported as unknown or not a possibility to collect samples in future. In addition, 2 studies were excluded due to missing data leaving 55 studies for further analyses.

5.1.2 Characterisation of the studies with possibility of sampling

In the following four geographical regions (Northern, Eastern, Southern and Western Europe) defined according to the United Nations geoscheme⁶ were used, with the exception of categorising Cyprus into Southern Europe instead of Asia. In addition, an 'Other' category was constructed to include Israel. Distribution of countries and number of studies according to region is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Frequency of the reported studies according to region and country (n=55)

Region	Number of studies (%)
Northern Europe	20 (36%)
Denmark (n=10), Finland (n=1), Latvia (n=3), Lithuania (n=1), Sweden (n=5)	
Eastern Europe	6 (11%)
Czech Republic, (n=4), Slovakia (n=2)	
Southern Europe	22 (40%)
Cyprus (n=2), Greece (n=3), Italy (n=3), Portugal (n=3), Slovenia (n=3), Spain (n=8)	
Western Europe	6 (11%)
France (n=1), Germany (n=1), Luxembourg (n=2), Netherlands (n=1), Switzerland (n=1)	
Other	1 (2%)
Israel (n=1)	
Total	55 (100%)

As seen from Figure 3, the most frequent type of studies for which data were reported and biological samples available were Health Examination Surveys (HES) (n=16, 29%), targeted health studies (n=15, 27%), and combined HBM and HES studies (n=14, 25%). Only a minor proportion of the studies were characterised by being an occupational study, dietary study, an HBM study without a HES component or other types of studies.

Figure 3: Frequency of study types (n=55)

The most frequent study type across regions were HES (including both targeted and untargeted HES) ranging from more than 80% (n=5) of the studies conducted in Eastern Europe to more than 40% (n=9) in Northern Europe. Only studies from Northern Europe reported the use of all types of study design (Figure 4). The PI from Israel ('Other') reported a single study characterised by being a combined HBM and HES reflected as 100% in the figure.

Figure 4: Study types stratified according to region (n=55)

5.1.3 Period and duration of the studies

Overall, the included studies were initiated or planned to be initiated between 1982 and 2018 with the vast majority being initiated from 2010 and onwards. After exclusion of studies reporting no specific year of study completion, the median length of the studies was planned to be 3 years ranging from 0 up to 39 years. Different study designs are represented in this survey including both cross-sectional studies and longitudinal studies. Thus, the significant difference in time span between studies is to a large degree due to differences in study design because longitudinal studies usually have a longer time span compared to cross-sectional studies. As illustrated in Figure 5A, the time span differed between regions but also within regions. In Northern Europe the median time span was 2.5 years with two studies reported to be ongoing reflected in the figure as lasting longer than year 2030. The median time span of the 6 studies reported from Eastern Europe was 5 years with two studies planned to end in year 2030. In the studies reported from Southern European countries the median time span was 4 years with one study reported to be ongoing whereas median time span among the 6 studies reported from Western Europe was 13 years with one study reported to be ongoing. Finally, Israel ('Other') reported a single study lasting two years.

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When stratifying according to study type there were significant differences in time span especially among the HES and the combined HBM and HES ranging from 0 to 39 among HES and from 1 to 26 years among the combined HBM and HES (Figure 5B).

Figure 5: Time span in the studies according to region (A) and study type (B)

5.1.4 Storage of biological samples

In the following sections, the focus will be on studies that did not conduct combined HES and HBM surveys ($n=41$). The obstacles and opportunities of combining HBM and HES were evaluated for the 14 combined HES and HBM studies. These results have been reported separately and been published in Deliverable report 11.1.

The vast majority ($n=38$, 93%) of these 41 studies reported that biological samples were collected and stored for future use. This storage of biological samples poses the possibility to perform chemical analysis on the studies and therefore, to introduce an HBM component. As seen from Figure 6, the most commonly stored biological samples that potentially could be used for HBM analysis were blood (whole blood) ($n=25$, 61%), plasma ($n=25$, 61%), serum ($n=23$, 56%), urine samples (random spot urine samples ($n=16$, 39%) and first morning urine samples ($n=12$, 29%)), as well as hair samples ($n=9$, 22%).

Figure 6: Frequently stored biological matrices (n=41)

No major differences in the frequency and type of stored biological samples were seen across the European regions.

5.1.5 Chemicals measured

Out of the 41 studies, 26 PIs (63%) reported that chemicals were measured or planned to be measured in the studies, 9 PIs (22%) reported that this was not the plan, whereas 6 PIs (15%) reported it to be unknown. The most frequent chemicals measured were phthalates (n=16, 39%), bisphenols (n=14, 34%) and cadmium (n=14, 34%) (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Overview of frequently measured chemicals (n=41)

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PIs from the 9 studies that did not include any chemical analysis of collected samples were asked about the main reasons for this. Notably, 6 out of the 9 studies reported that lack of funding was the main issue either in relation to taking additional samples or laboratory analyses of chemicals.

Other reasons also pointed out were logistical issues (n=3) and lack of knowledge about chemicals (n=3).

5.1.6 Funding of the studies

PIs from the 41 studies were asked how the study was funded with the possibility of reporting more than one funding source. The most frequent sources of funding were public sources either by the government (n=20, 49%), public grants (n=20, 49%) and/or EU grants or other international research programmes (n=15, 37%). Only a small portion of the studies was funded by private grants (n=6, 15%). Half of the studies had only a single funding source while the other half had several, with the majority of these (n=17, 42%) having two different funding sources and only a minor portion having three or four different funding sources (n=3, 7% and n=1, 2%, respectively).

When stratified according to the region, studies from Northern Europe were characterised by being funded by a number of different sources whereas Eastern Europe and Southern Europe were characterised by fewer types of funding sources (Figure 8A). In cases where PIs listed more than one type of funding source, the researchers were asked to specify the main type of funding. In Northern and Southern Europe, the main types of funding differed between studies (Figure 8B) and the major type of funding were public grants (46% and 44% respectively). In contrast, there was less variation in types of main funding; in Eastern Europe all studies were primarily funded by the government which was also the case in 4 out of 5 studies from Western Europe.

Figure 8: Comparison of funding sources in the European regions. A) all reported funding sources per study, B) main types of funding sources

5.1.7 Further study characteristics

Of the 41 studies, 54% (n=22) were cross-sectional studies and 46% (n=19) were longitudinal studies with a few studies characterised as a combined study design. Among the cross-sectional surveys, 8 studies (40%) were repeated with varying time span in between; the planned sampling frequency varying from annually up to 9 years interval. For the longitudinal studies, some of the

studies were conducted with yearly intervals and some were conducted following the life circle from prenatal life, childhood up to puberty and adulthood.

As for study size, the majority (n=25, 61%) of the studies had more than 1.000 participants and only a minority had below 100 participants (n=3, 7%). Especially HES were characterised by a comprehensive study size with approximately 70% of the studies (n=21) including more than 1000 participants. Finally, in all 5 HBM surveys the studies contained as a minimum 250 participants (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Study types and frequency of their study sizes reported

Furthermore, the majority of the studies (n=23, 56%) could be characterised as a representative sample of the general population, 39% (n=16) as targeted samples and 5% (n=2) as characterised by other types of sampling. More than half of HES and HBM surveys (n=19, 61% and n=3, 60%, respectively) were characterised by being representative samples (Figure 10) whereas all three occupational surveys were characterised by using targeted sampling using workforce populations.

Figure 10: Characterisation of study population

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The vast majority of the studies included participants of both sexes (n=36, 88%), 3 studies (7%) included only women and two studies (5%) included only men.

Overall, the studies were characterised by participants in a wide age span and the age span differed most significantly in HES (Figure 11). The median difference between the studies was 39 years for all study types (absolute age range: 0-99 years of age) ranging from 9 years in HBM surveys (6-65 years of age), 13 years in other types of study (0-24 years of age), 42 years in HES (0-99 years of age) and 47 years in occupational surveys (18-70 years of age). The most predominant age-groups included in HES, HBM Surveys and Occupational Surveys were adult participants from the age of 18 (n=24, 59%). Only 11 studies (27%) included children below the age of 10 out of which 6 studies (15%) included newborns.

Figure 11: Overview of age span in the studies

5.1.8 Measuring health and lifestyle parameters and the inclusion of register data

Clinical examinations and biomarkers

In the majority of the 41 studies, clinical health examinations were performed (n=33, 81%). In general, measurements of anthropometrics and blood pressure were the most frequent assessments, and especially HES included these assessments but also a number of other different clinical examinations (Figure 12). Among the group of 'other tests' performed, the most frequent were lung function tests, DEXA scans and allergy tests (data not shown).

Figure 12: Overview of clinical examinations

Also, a number of biomarkers were measured in samples from the majority (n=16, 76%) of the studies with biological samples stored or planned to be stored. The most frequently analysed clinical biomarkers were metabolic markers and markers of kidney function (Figure 13). Again, in HES more clinical biomarkers were included compared to the other types of studies. A number of different markers were reported in the category of 'Other markers' including markers of allergy, inflammation and oxidative stress.

Figure 13: Overview of biomarkers

Questionnaire and register data

In total, 40 out of 41 studies (98%) with biological samples stored, or planned to be stored, did not include a collection of any kind of questionnaire data. This study was by the PI categorised as being in the group of ‘Other studies’. However, for the rest of the studies that included questionnaire data, a wide range of questions was in general asked (Figure 14). Especially questions related to lifestyle, socio-economic status and self-reported health were frequently asked in the different studies regardless of study type.

Figure 14: Frequency of questionnaire data

Register data was only retrieved in 15 out of the 41 studies. The most frequent registers from which data was retrieved were mortality registers and registers including information on hospital admissions. Among the HES approximately 50% of the studies and 2 out of 3 of the occupational surveys retrieved data from these registers (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Retrieval of register data

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Finally, among PIs from the 26 studies that did not retrieve register data another 12 studies (46%) reported that retrieving data was a possibility.

5.1.9 Ethical approval for chemical measurement

Questions related to ethical approval covering measurement of chemicals were only given to PIs on HES, occupational surveys, dietary surveys (if any), other types of surveys with biological samples collected or planned to be collected for future use. Thus, PIs on combined HBM and HES (n=14) studies but also PIs on HBM surveys (n=5) were excluded in the following leaving 36 studies.

Ethical approval covering the measurement of chemicals in collected samples was available in 21 studies (58%); 18 HES (50%), 1 occupational survey (3%), 2 other types of study (6%). In addition, out of the 15 PIs from studies who responded that ethical approval was currently not available, another 9 PIs responded that ethical approval for measuring chemicals could be obtained in the future. Thus, in total 30 studies had approval or could obtain approval for chemical measurements in the future.

Among the 21 studies that already had ethical approval covering measurement of chemicals, the PIs were asked which chemicals were covered by this approval. Approximately half of the studies (10 out of 21 studies) did not have restrictions on the approval and could potentially measure all chemicals of interest. 6 out of 21 responded that 'metals' and 'heavy metals' were covered by the approval. Finally, phthalates, bisphenol A, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and pesticides were also listed in 2-3 cases each as chemical groups with ethical approval.

Among the 21 studies with ethical approval, the following matrices that can be used for chemical measurements according to the ethical approval are shown in Figure 16. Only the most frequent matrices are shown.

Figure 16: Matrices with ethical approval (n=21)

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5.1.10 IPChem – the Information Platform for Chemical monitoring

Of the 41 studies with biological samples stored, or planned to be stored, only a few studies (n=3, 7%) reported to be legally allowed to upload chemical data from the study to IPChem (according to ethical and personal data protection directives/regulations) on an individual level and another 29% (n=12) on an aggregated level. However, the majority (n=26, 64%) of the studies stated that it was either unknown or currently not a possibility to upload data to IPChem (Table 2).

Table 2: Upload of data from the study to IPChem

	Number of studies (%)
Yes, as data on an individual level	3 (7%)
Yes, but only as aggregate data (e.g. distributions, means, etc.)	12 (29%)
Unknown	20 (49%)
Currently no, but it might be possible if specific regulation is taken in future	6 (15%)
Total	41 (100%)

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6 Conclusions

The present work has allowed the gathering of data on health surveys where an HBM component might be added in a cost-effective manner. An inventory with these studies was produced and has been updated.

The survey showed that there is a great potential for adding an HBM component to the majority of the studies which did not yet include this. More than 90% of the studies reported that biological samples were collected and stored for future use. Furthermore, more than half of the studies had already ethical approval which allowed measurement of chemicals in the collected samples, and the majority of the remaining studies considers that this approval would be possible to obtain. Indeed, even though the studies did not formally include an HBM component 63% of the studies reported that the measurement of some chemicals was performed or is planned to be performed in the future.

The remaining question is to figure out what limits researchers from introducing an HBM component to the different studies conducted. We have previously evaluated obstacles and difficulties in studies combining HBM and HES in D11.1. Common for the countries succeeding in combining HBM and HES was that the programmes were funded and implemented as national programmes under ministerial direction. In line with this, among the present studies that did not include measurements of chemicals, the main reasons for not including chemical measurements were lack of funding either in relation to taking additional samples and laboratory analyses of chemicals. Also among the ongoing studies without an HBM component, significant regional differences in main funding sources were seen which could possibly explain some of the reasons for not conducting combined HBM and HES.

In conclusion, based on ongoing or planned data on studies from 19 EU or EU affiliated countries there is a great potential for adding an HBM component and some of the studies already collect HBM related data to some degree. However, continuous funding and prioritisation may be one of the main obstacles for not conducted combined HBM and HES.

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Part B. Availability of administrative registers and possibilities for their use in HBM studies

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This document has been prepared in collaboration with all involved partners.

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2 Background

Administrative registers, such as registers of in- and out-patient hospitalisations and mortality registers, may provide nationally representative data on morbidity and mortality in a country. In many countries such registers are nationally representative or several regional registers exist, covering the majority of the country. In principle, if register information is recorded using personal identification number or other type of identification, which would be available also in HBM studies, a record linkage could be conducted if allowed by national data protection regulation. This type of record linkage would provide a cost-effective data source for morbidity and mortality follow-up and for obtaining baseline health information.

The aim of this evaluation was to identify administrative registers in different EU Member States and learn about their contents and how they could be linked to the HBM studies.

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3 Methods

3.1 Preparation of the questionnaire

An electronic questionnaire was prepared to obtain information about existing health related administrative registers in the EU Member States. The content of the questionnaire was prepared in collaboration, through several rounds of iteration by all involved partners (NIPH, THL, MUW, WIV-ISP, IHIS, SDU, KI, UMU) in 2017. NIPH prepared an electronic version from the questionnaire using QuestBack by Digium. The web questionnaire was pilot tested with task partners and final adjustments were made based on received feedback.

3.2 Identification of administrative registers

The 1st round of questionnaire was sent to the National Hub Contact Points (NHCP) in 2017. Results from this round were presented in the Deliverable 11.1, Part B.⁷ At that time, only 19 countries (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Sweden and Switzerland) replied, leaving a gap in full coverage of the EU Member States and EEA (European Economic Area) countries. The 2nd round was organised in 2018. By the end of September 2018, three new countries (Netherlands, Slovakia and Spain) provided information about their administrative registers resulting in a total of 22 countries with information.

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4 Results

Results presented here are based on replies to the questionnaire by different register owners/users in 2017 and 2018. Since not all EU Member States (MS) are represented and number of registers also varies considerably between those MS that have replied, there may be some bias on representativeness of the results within and between MS.

4.1 Description of registers

4.1.1 Health related administrative registers

Respondents to the questionnaire reported altogether 129 registers (Appendix 1) from 22 countries. Most of the reported registers were classified as 'Other type of register' (33%). From specified registers, most common were the disease specific registers (26%), while birth registers constituted 14% and causes of death registers constituted 15%. Smaller proportion of the registers covered in-patient hospitalisations (11.5%) and out-patient consultations (7%), prescriptions of medications (7%) and malformations (5%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Number of reported registers by type of register

Among the disease-specific registers, 53% were cancer registries, 9% coronary heart disease registers and 6% diabetes registers. The remaining 32% included registers for multiple sclerosis, AIDS, occupational diseases, childhood diseases, rare diseases, stroke and infectious diseases.

In the other types of reported health registers, the majority of reported registers were morbidity registers (80%). All of these were French registers. Most of the reported French registers were regional or type specific cancer registers. In addition to this, several cardiovascular disease registers were included under morbidity registers from France. Also individual registers of blood donors, abortions, vaccinations, hospital infections and antibiotic use and medical records for recruits and serving personnel were reported under this category.

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4.1.2 Main purposes of the registers

The purpose of the register is often defined by the type of the register:

- **Birth registers** are designed to collect information about pregnancies and births. In Denmark, for example, a special Occupational Birth Register exists which is designed to provide information about parental work during pregnancies and child development. In general, birth registers will provide statistics on pregnancies and births. They also enable cross-sectional and – if follow-up is in place – longitudinal analyses relating pregnancy- and birth-related factors to outcomes in childhood and beyond, in pursuance of the “Developmental Origins of Health and Disease” (DOHaD) hypothesis.
- **Causes of death registers** are designed to collect information about causes of death for statistical purposes. They tend to be used for public health officials who wish to monitor time trends of cause-specific mortality in a given geographic region. In addition, they enable studies of disease aetiology and progression in a variety of settings, from clinical to observational studies.
- **In-patient hospitalisation registers** vary between countries in design and purpose. Generally, these cover hospitalised patients and their diagnoses for monitoring purposes. In Lithuania, the Injury and Accident Monitoring was also classified as in-patient hospitalisation register and its main purpose is to collect data on injuries and accidents for statistical purposes. Some of the in-patient registers, like the Danish Occupational Hospital Register, are focused on issues related to occupational health. In general, they can be useful for identifying incident cases of a given disease, e.g. in Denmark, their world-wide unique Parkinson’s disease (PD) register enabled the implementation of a population-wide PD case-control study.
- **Out-patient consultations** generally collect data on health care usage, prevention and treatment of diseases outside hospitals. Collected data is used for statistics and monitoring.
- **Registers for prescriptions of medications** are designed to monitor the patterns of medication prescriptions and use, to evaluate the costs and in some countries such as Finland where some medication are reimbursed, the reimbursements. In Sweden the register is used to increase patent security. Registers also provide information for statistics and can serve as surrogates for diseases (e.g., individuals who take anti-PD drugs), enabling a variety of observational studies.
- **Registers for malformations** are designed to provide surveillance and statistical information about congenital anomalies. In Czech Republic, the National Register of Reproductive Health is merged with the National Registry of Mothers at Childbirths, the National Registry of New-borns, the National Registry of Congenital Malformations, the National Registry of Abortions and the National Registry of Assisted Reproduction into a unified system providing better monitoring of reproductive health.
- **Disease specific registers**, which are mainly cancer registers, are designed to provide statistics and epidemiological overview of cancer incidence and prevalence in a country. Similarly, for other reported disease specific registers, their purpose is to enable varied evaluations and disease monitoring.
- **Multi-purpose registers** are available in some countries. For example, Belgium reported their www.healthdata.be which is not a register, but a technical platform and service

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provided consolidating all patient registers in Belgium. Other examples are the Danish Occupational Hospital Register and the Finnish Care Register for Health Care which has both in-patient hospitalisations and out-patient consultations.

The basic purpose of national health registers is the documentation of health data. They are used for monitoring, trend analyses and sometimes also for the examination of spatial variation.

Thus 129 registers were reported, some of the reported registers fit the description of several types of register. Most often in-patient and out-patient registers have been combined (7 cases). In one of these cases also cause of death was included. Four birth registers contained additional information, usually on malformations (2 cases) or on other diseases (2 cases). Two registers (from Denmark and from Poland) were reported to contain “all of the above” types, the Danish register being the one specifically on occupational issues (Occupational Birth Register).

4.2 Characteristics of the registers

4.2.1 Contents of the registers

In the questionnaire about administrative registers, some basic information about the type of information included to the registers was asked. Figure 2 summarises the key elements included in the registers excluding 34 registers reported from France for which this information was not provided. In total, 87% of the registers included the information on sex and 89% date or year of birth for the subject. In 79% of registers also date of registration of condition and in 69% of registers, the residence (e.g. rural or urban) was recorded. Since most of the registers were health related, 70% of them used ICD codes to register events.

Figure 2: Key elements included to the registers

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4.2.2 Geographical coverage of registers and possible problems with representativeness

From reported 129 registers, 60% were classified as national registers, and for 30% of the registers the coverage was not reported. Most of the registers without known coverage were from France. Yet, based on the names of the registers (e.g. ‘Somme Cancer Registry’, ‘Registry of general cancers in Gironde’), it can be presumed that some – not all - of them have a limited spatial coverage.

Even though the majority of registers were reported to have a national coverage, this does not imply that all registers are complete or representative. For some registers, specific exclusion criteria are applied: e.g. in the Swedish ‘Prescribed Drug Register’, medications given to patients at the hospitals are not included, in the Danish ‘Occupational Hospital Register’ no information can be found on employees in companies with less than 10 employees, etc. Yet, in overall terms, the registers currently identified in the database have mostly a national coverage and, according to a question specifically asking about representativeness, are representative at population level.

4.3 Technical features of the registers

4.3.1 Types of personal identifiers used in different registers

Most of the EU Member States have some personal identifier (PIC) to identify individuals⁸ as listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Type(s) of identifier(s) used in different countries

Country	Type of identifier
Austria	AT Sector-specific personal identifier
Belgium	BE National register number
Bulgaria	BG Uniform civil number
Croatia	HR Personal identification number (PIC)
Cyprus	CY no information available
Czech Republic	CZ Birth number
Denmark	DK Personal identification number (PIC)
Estonia	EE Personal identification code (PIC)
Finland	FI Personal identity code (PIC)
France	FR National health insurance number (NIR)
Germany	DE No national identification number. Taxpayer identification number and economy identification number but used only for taxation purposes
Greece	EL National identification numbers. ID card number is not unique and changes if the person gets a new identity card.

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Country		Type of identifier
Hungary	HU	No national identification number. ID card identification number, social security number, tax identification number, passport identification number, driving license number exists.
Iceland	IS	National identification number (PIC)
Ireland	IE	Personal public service number
Italy	IT	Italian fiscal code
Latvia	LV	Personal code (PIC)
Lithuania	LT	Personal code (PIC)
Luxembourg	LU	No information available
Malta	MT	No information available
Netherlands	NL	Citizen service number (personal number) (PIC)
Norway	NO	Birth number (PIC)
Poland	PL	Public electronic census system number
Portugal	PT	Not one national number but several different identification numbers: civil identification number, tax identification number, social security number, healthcare user number, voter's number, driver's license number.
Romania	RO	Personal numerical code (PIC)
Slovakia	SK	Two national identification numbers: birth number and citizen's identification card number
Slovenia	SI	Unique master citizen number
Spain	ES	National identity document after age of 14 years
Sweden	SE	Personal identity number (PIC)
Switzerland	CH	Social security number (most persons)
United Kingdom	UK	National insurance number

Obviously, having a personal identification number in a country does not automatically mean that it is systematically used in registers. In the reported registers, national level personal identifiers were used in 54% of the registers. There were other identifiers, which possibly would allow register linkage in 11% of the registers, and in 3% registers did not include any identifier allowing the register linkage. It should be noted that from 27% of the registers (all reported French registers) information about availability of the identifier was missing. (Table 2)

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Table 2: Registers according to the type of identifier

Type of identifier	Number of registers	% of all reported registers
Individual identification code (national level personal identifier = PIC)	70	54%
Individual identification code (not national but regional)	1	1%
Register-specific individual identification (with possibilities to link to other (national) registries for research purposes)	13	10%
Non-person identification (possibility for e.g. probability linkage)	8	6%
Stored with pseudonym	1	1%
No identification at all	2	2%
Unknown	35	27%
TOTAL	129	100%

Out of 22 countries, 18 (AT, BE, HR, CY, CZ, DK, ES, FI, IS, IL, LT, NL, NO, PT, SK, SI, SE, CH) include PIC in some of their registries and 9 in all of their registers. In nine countries also registries with a different type of personal identifier (AT, CY, DK, IL, LT, NO, PT, ES, and CH) were reported. Non-person identification (with a possibility for, e.g., probability linkage) was reported for General Hospital Morbidity Study in Poland. German Centre for Cancer Registry Data stores data with pseudonym. Ireland reported register-specific individual identification for cancer registry and non-person identification for infectious disease reporting. (Table 3)

Table 3: Countries according to the type of unique identifier in reported registers

Type of identifier	Countries	Number of countries	% of all countries
Individual identification code (national level personal identifier)	BE, HR, CZ, FI, IS, NL, SK, SI, SE	9	41%
Varies between registers but at least some registers have national level personal identifier	AT, CY, DK, IL, LT, NO, PT, ES, CH	9	41%
Non-person identification (possibility for e.g. probability linkage)	PL	1	5%
Stored with pseudonym	DE	1	5%
Varies between registers and none has national level personal identifier but possibility link (e.g. probability linkage etc.)	IE	1	5%
Unknown	FR	1	5%

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In general, countries with national level PIC use them systematically in their registers. There are a few register specific exceptions in nine countries (AT, CY, DK, IL, LT, NO, PT, ES, CH) which have national level PIC but is not used in all registers due to the sensitive nature of the specific register.

For example, in Cyprus the HIV/AIDS register, in Norway the Registry of Pregnancy Terminations, and in Spain the Castellon Cancer Registry does not have personal identification. Similarly, three Swiss registries (health survey, multiple sclerosis registry, and cancer registry) use non-person identification.

In Denmark, the Occupations Birth Register, in Israel the National Cancer Registry, in Norway the Prescription Database and the Surveillance System for Infections in Hospitals, in Cyprus the birth registry, in Austria the mortality registry and in Spain the childhood cancer registry only have register specific identifier. Five Portuguese registries also use register-specific identifier.

In Lithuania the Injury and Accident Monitoring and in Switzerland the Myocardial Infarction Registry do not have any identifiers.

Although Ireland uses Personal public service number, its use is limited and has not been reported in disease registries. Similarly, Polish citizens have their PESEL number, but its use was not reported in the Polish hospital morbidity study.

Table 4 shows that in most of the birth registers (87%), causes of death registers (94%), in- and out-patient hospitalisation registers (67%), medical prescription registers (71%) and registers of malformations (75%), national level personal identification code was used.

Table 4: Frequency of different identifiers in different register types

Type of register	National, individual identification code	Regional, individual identification code	Register-specific individual identification	Non-person identification	Stored with pseudonym/ no identifier	Unknown
Birth register	87%		7%			7%
Causes of death register	94%		6%			
Hospitalisations (in-patient and out-patient)	67%	8%	8%	8%	8%	
Prescription of medications	71%		29%			
Register of malformations	75%		25%			
Disease specific registers (excl. cancer)	57%			21%	7%	14%
Cancer register	33%		11%	6%	3%	47%
Other registers	27%		8%	8%		58%

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4.3.2 Size of the registers

The size (number of records) of the registers is dependent on the time that passed since the start of registration and on the proportion of the population covered by the register. Table 5 provides a general overview of the number of records in reported registers by country. In most countries the registers are national, covering all the cases in the country, while in countries where the registers are regional, they are more limited.

Table 5: Size of the registers in different countries

Country	Number of registers	Register category	Number of cases in different registers (range)	Year from which data are available
Austria	3	Causes of Death statistics	about 80 000 per year	1970
		Birth Statistics	about 80,000 a year	1970
		Austrian National Cancer Registry	>1.100.000	1983
Belgium	1	Technical platform and service provider that will consolidate all patient registries in Belgium	Varies between registers, up-to millions per register	
Croatia	1	Croatian National Cancer Registry	About 450,000	2001
Cyprus	4	Causes of Death Registry	64473	2004
		Birth Registry	50.903	From 2007-2013 (public sector only), from 2014-2016 (national)
		HIV/AIDS Registry	1116	1986
		Cancer Register	52929 (including pending cases)	1998
Czech Republic	4	Czech National Cancer Registry	2,300,000	1977
		National Register of Reproduction Health	approximately 2.5 million of births	1994
		National Register of Hospitalised Patients	54,000,000	1994
		Information system Deaths	approximately 4 million	1982
Denmark	8	Danish Occupational Hospital Register		1980
		Occupational Birth Register		1980
		The Danish Cancer Register		1943
		Birth Registry	The registers are nation-wide, covering all cases in the country.	1973
		Prescription registry		1994
		Causes of Death Registry		1970
		Patient Registry		1976
		Statistics Denmark		depends on the data
Finland	6	Finnish Cancer Registry		1953
		Care Register for Health Care		1969
		Archive of death certificates		1936
		Statistics on reimbursements for prescription medicines	All registers are nationwide, covering all cases in the country	Statistics on reimbursements for prescription medicines have been compiled since 1995, The statistics on reimbursement entitlements in respect of medicines 1968
		Medical Birth Register		1987
		Register of Congenital malformations		1963
France	34	A number of regional registers mentioned	No information	No information
Germany	1	Centre for Cancer Registry Data	About 8.5 million cases	2014
Iceland	3	Icelandic Birth Register	Approximately 150.000	1982
		Icelandic Causes of Death Register	Approximately 80.000	1971
		Prescription drugs database	Approximately 3.5 million pr. year	2003
Ireland	2	National Cancer Registry of Ireland (NCRI)	139,526	1994
		Computerised Infectious Disease Reporting	31941 in 2015	2002

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Israel	7	Cancer		
		The Israeli National Cancer Registry		1980
		National diabetes registry	800,000	2012
		National stroke registry	53,000	2014
		Death		
		Birth Registry	About 4,300,000 entries	1993
Lithuania	6	Death Registry	About 1,600,000 entries	1981
		Lithuanian Cancer Register	530000	1978
		Occupational Disease Register	Annually about 400	from 2005
		Register of blood donor	Annually about 65 000	from 2012
		Causes of Death Register	Annually about 40 000	from 2010
		Children health monitoring system	Annually about 350 000	2017
The Netherlands	2	Injury and Accident Monitoring		from 2016
		Dutch population register	Total population	1995
Norway	11	Causes of death register	All NL deaths yearly	No information
		Medical Birth Registry of Norway	All births since 1967	1967
		Registry of Pregnancy Termination	All abortions performed in Norway since 1979	
		Norwegian Cardiovascular Disease Registry	All cases of cardiovascular disease since 2012	
		Norwegian Cause of Death Registry	About 40 000 per year	1951
		Norwegian Prescription Database (NorPD)	All prescription medicines dispensed by 2004	
		Norwegian Immunisation Registry SYSAK	All childhood immunisations from 1995	1995
		Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS)	Cannot find information about this	1975 (but some illnesses not reportable that early)
		Surveillance System for Infections in Hospitals (NOIS)	Cannot find information about this	varying widely
		Norwegian Patient Registry	All hospitalisation and polidclinical treatn	Person-identifiable from 2008
		Cancer Registry of Norway	140 000 notifications per year; 30 000 new	1951
Poland	2	Registry of the Norwegian Armed Forces Medical Service	Not stated; should be all.	2006
		General Hospital Morbidity Study		2006
		PESEL, Universal Electronic System for Registration of the Population		
		The PESEL number is mandatory for all permanent residents of Poland and for temporary residents living in Poland for over 2 months.	8 million	
		National Cancer Registry Hospitalization Registry		
Portugal	6	National Registry of Congenital Anomalies	22728 (1997 to 2015)	1997 - 2016
		Birth Register		2016
		Cause of death	About 100,000 annually.	2014
		In-patient hospitalizations	About 1,000,000 episodes annually.	1990 onwards
		Prescription of medications		2014
		National Cancer Registry		
Slovakia	5	Birth register	All births in Slovak Republic	1998
		National registry of Congenital malformations	All still and live born children with conge	1994
		National stroke register	all patients with stroke	2009
		Report on admission of inpatient care	all terminated of hospitalizations (in-pat	2008
		Deaths and causes of death	all deaths of Slovak citizens	2000
Slovenia	5	Cancer Register of Slovenia	107 000	1950
		Birth register	2,07 million	1985
		Cause of death register	18000 yearly	1984
		Hospitalisations		2016
		Prescription of medications	About 15 million prescriptions	2002
Spain	4	Girona Cancer Registry		1994
		Castellón Cancer Registry	30000	2004
		VALENCIANA CHILDHOOD CANCER REGISTRY	Approx. 180 cases per year	1983 (from 0 to 14 ages) and 2007 (from 0 to 19 ages)
		Registro de Atención Sanitaria Especializada (RAE-CMBD)		
		National registry of specialized care	7	1997

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Sweden	6	Cause of death register	5 633 480	1961
		Register of prescription of medications	About 90 % of the population	2005
		Health Insurance and occupational studies (LISA)	11-12 000 00	1990
		The Swedish Medical Birth Register	All births in Sweden since 1973	1973
		the National Patient Register	All hospital discharges since 1987 and all	1987
		The Swedish Cancer Registry	Approx. 50 000 malignant cancers registe	1958
Switzerland	8	Swiss Health Survey	20000	1992, 1997, 2002, 2007, 2012
		Swiss Multiple Sclerosis Registry	1750	2016
		Cancer Epidemiology and Registration	870000	1970
		Swiss Neborn Screening	About 1.5 Million	1998
		Swiss Diabetes Registry	Approx. 1000 patients	2012
		Acute Myocardial Infarction register		1997
		Swiss Rare Disease Registry		
		Causes of death statistics	2,8 Million	1969

As can be seen from Table 5, the number of cases in the registers that are nation-wide and old is impressive. However, for research and monitoring purposes it is important that registers are accessible and they cover time period relevant for the study. Table 6 provides information by register type.

Table 6: Size of the major registers

Type of register	Number of countries	Number of cases (range)	Countries with total population coverage
Birth registers including registers of malformations	18	50,000 – total population	≥6
Causes of death registers	14-16	Generally very large	Probably the majority
In-patient hospitalisations and out-patient consultations	11	8 million – total population	Around 8
Registers for prescriptions of medications	8	Generally very large	Probably 7
Cancer registers	16	50,000 – total population	Around 10-12

For prospective studies, where incident diseases are ascertained through register linkage during follow-up, the completeness/population coverage of the register is a major issue to avoid bias.

4.3.3 Availability of registers electronically and updating frequency

The availability of registers in electronic format, and year from which they are available, vary considerably between the countries and type of register. A summary is presented in Table 5. Causes of death registers go back to mid-1930's (Finland) and in most of the countries they are

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available electronically at least from 1980's. Also other registers have been available for decades in many countries. Registers tend to be updated regularly.

Among disease specific registers, 18 were specified as cancer registers. Additional to this, of 32 registers reported from France under 'Other types of registers', 22 could be identified as regional cancer registers based on the name of the register, and the other 10 registers were other disease specific registers. For all these French registers, only information on register name and type was provided which limits the use of this information for further analysis. Identified cancer registers were added to the Table 7 as a separate line, including the French registers reported as "Other types of registers", and the other 10 French registers reported as "Other types of registers" were added to the Disease specific registers, excluding cancer registers.

Table 7: Year of electronic availability and last update for different types of registers.

Type of register	N of registers	Year of availability in electronic format min-max	Year of last update (N of registers)	Updating frequency (N of registers)
Birth register	18	1967-2016	2015 (2) 2016(4) 2017(4) 2018 (4) Unknown (3) No electronic data (1)	Irregularly (1) Annually (6) Semi-annually (1) Periodically (1) Continuously (6) Unknown (2)
Causes of Death register	20	1936-2014	2015 (5) 2016 (4) 2017(5) 2018 (2) Unknown (4)	Irregularly (1) Annually (9) Semi-annually (2) Periodically (2) Continuously (4) Unknown (2)
In-patient hospitalisations	15	1969-2016	2010 (1) 2015 (2) 2016 (5) 2017 (2) 2018 (1) Unknown (4)	Irregularly (1) Annually (6) Semi-annually (1) Periodically (1) Continuously (4) Unknown (2)
Out-patient consultations	9	1969-2008	2010 (1) 2015 (2) 2016 (1) 2017 (1) 2018 (1) Unknown (3)	Irregularly (1) Annually (1) Semi-annually (1) Periodically (1) Continuously (4) Unknown (1)

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Type of register	N of registers	Year of availability in electronic format min-max	Year of last update (N of registers)	Updating frequency (N of registers)
Register for prescriptions of medications	9	1968-2014	2015 (2) 2016 (1) 2017 (4) 2018 (0) Unknown (2)	Irregularly (1) Annually (1) Periodically (1) Semi-annually (2) Continuously (4) Unknown (0)
Register of malformation	7	1963-2007	2015 (2) 2016 (3) 2017 (0) 2018 (1) Unknown (1)	Irregularly (1) Annually (5) Semi-annually (0) Periodically (0) Continuously (1) Unknown (0)
Disease specific, excluding cancers	26	1975-2016	2015 (2) 2016 (3) 2017 (6) Unknown (14) No electronic data (1)	Irregularly (1) Annually (2) Semi-annually (1) Periodically (2) Continuously (7) Unknown (12)
Other types (including 10 French registers with limited information)	11	1979-2012	2016 (2) 2017 (6) 2018 (1) Unknown (2)	Irregularly (0) Annually (1) Semi-annually (1) Periodically (1) Continuously (8) Unknown (0)
Cancer registers (including 22 regional French registers with limited information)	40	1943-2014	2012 (1) 2014 (8) 2015 (1) 2016 (2) 2017(2) 2018 (2) Unknown (24)	Irregularly (2) Annually (7) Semi-annually (0) Periodically (2) Continuously (6) Unknown (23)

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4.3.4 Access to register data

The rules of access to the register data varies between countries and often also between registers within country. When register data are accessed for the purpose of register linkage to the HBM or other survey data, usually several levels of authorisation are required. First of all, the ethical approval and data protection approval has to be obtained for the record linkage and in most cases also informed consent of the study participant is required. Obviously, also the register owner has to approve the record linkage. The question in our questionnaire may have been somewhat misleading on this as we asked 'What are the conditions for access to data?' which may have led some respondents to think access to register data in general, not in relation to record linkage to survey data. Therefore, our results have to be considered with some level of reservation. They may better represent the general rules of access for register data for example in case of register based studies.

Only 33% of the registers reported that informed consent of the participant would be required. Most commonly required approvals were the approval by local ethics committee (56%) and register owner (54%). In 16% of the cases, it was reported that access to the register data was not allowed. For example, in Finland and Sweden, when register data are linked to survey data, this must be approved by the national ethics committee, and informed consent from survey participants is required.

In many cases access to the register data is free of charge (44% of reported registers), but some registers also charge fees from data access (56%). Costs vary from standard fees to hourly rates for time used for data retrieval, and their combinations.

In most cases (64%), register data can be delivered within 3 months, and in 8% it may take over one year. Many registers restrict the access to the data only in anonymous or at the aggregated level.

4.4 Problems related to linking of registers to other registers

Even when PIC is available in the register and commonly used in the country, there may be problems in register linkage. Even more complicated register linkage may be if common identifier is missing and linkage has to be done based on other available information. Table 8 provides information about reported, identified problems for record linkage in different countries.

Table 8: Identified problems related to record linkage

Country	Personal identification code used in registers	Identified problems
Austria	Yes	Not all registers include the PIC
Belgium	Yes	None identified
Croatia	Yes	None identified
Cyprus	Yes for death and cancer registers, register specific PIC for birth register, no PIC for some HIV/AIDS registers	If national identification code is missing.

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Country	Personal identification code used in registers	Identified problems
Czech Republic	Yes	Linkage between registers under National Health Information System is allowed. The linkage with other data sources is very restricted.
Denmark	Yes except occupational birth register has a register specific PIC	None if the application is approved by all register authorities in question. For occupational birth register, the use would need to be within those of a birth register (mainly to investigate the influence of parent's occupation on child health)
Finland	Yes	None if the application is approved by all register authorities
France	Yes except for some registers	Linkage has to be approved by ethic committees and authorities
Germany	No. Data stored in pseudonym format	Not defined in the questionnaire
Iceland	Yes	Authorisation by the Icelandic Data Protection Authority required and when used for scientific research also permission by the Icelandic Ethical Committee required.
Ireland	Register specific PIC	Not currently possible.
Israel	Yes	Not defined in the questionnaire.
Lithuania	Yes, except for register on injuries and accident monitoring has none	No technical problems identified but some legal problems for linkage due to personal data protection may exist.
Netherlands		Requires informed consent and some privacy issues.
Norway	Yes	None identified in general. For Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases for some endpoints there is not enough information about patient to do the linkage. For Norwegian Surveillance System for Infections in Hospital data type in not suited.
Poland	No	Not defined in the questionnaire.
Portugal	Register specific PIC	No problems identified in general. However, the change in laws and regulations related to the data protection, final authorisation is still pending.
Slovakia		None identified.
Slovenia	Yes	None identified for those who are entitled to do the linkage by law.
Spain		Some of the linking results anonymous datasets.
Sweden	Yes	None identified.
Switzerland	Yes	Record linkage is heavily regulated by legislation and data linkage with other data sources and final data file must be fully anonymised. For some registers it might be possible to obtain permission from the register owner and Ethics Committee for data linkage, but again, final data file must be fully anonymised.

In countries where the PIC is systematically used throughout the registers, no technical problems were identified for register linkage. Also in most of the countries with register specific PIC, register linkage seemed possible. Several countries stated that national legislation/regulations on personal data protection may have some impact on feasibility of the register linkage. Need for informed consent was highlighted by some countries. Also for some specific registers (with very sensitive data), register linkage was not possible even when PIC was existing.

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5 Conclusions

Although in 2018, we ended up with information on 129 registries, it is clear that data are missing both on how many registers there are within the countries and details about the specific register. Also for some countries data is missing completely. France, for instance, listed the name of 32 registers, but neglected most of the other questions. Despite contact through the national hub contact person, many reminders and attempts to get more information through personal contacts, we did not succeed in getting a complete overview. We considered getting more information through literature/web search, but these sites are most often not available in English or other languages spoken by involved partners.

The current report provides a general, but not complete, overview on availability of health related administrative registers in the countries from which we obtained answers. Countries tend to have several different types of health registers and most of them have national coverage. This provides a good basis for morbidity and mortality monitoring and statistics. The circulated questionnaire was aimed at health-related registers; therefore other registers (e.g., pension registers, information of socio-economic position, etc.) that might provide additional information on health-related questions and required background information on socio-demographic position were not reported. Extending requests in coming years to other administrative registers should be considered.

In three quarters of the responding countries, use of national level personal identifiers was reported for one or more registers. The vast majority of the registries reported some unique identifier, making the linkage to other data theoretically possible. There are several probability-based record linkage methods which can be used when a direct personal identifier is missing. These include for example deterministic record linkage⁹ and probabilistic record linkage¹⁰.

In most of the countries, it is possible to link data between registers. From the replies to our questionnaire, it is still unclear how many countries could link HBM/health survey data to registers to obtain mortality and morbidity follow-up and new EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) may have changed or modified previous practices.

Easy access to register data to determine baseline health profiles, and mortality and morbidity follow-up, could provide satisfying coverage of data and be a cost-effective way to obtain this. Currently, the largest limitations are lack of personal identification in some registers within countries and in some countries in general. Also, when personal identification exists, national data protection regulations may prevent the use of register data to support survey-based studies. The Nordic countries have long traditions for register-linkage between registers, but also to survey data.¹¹

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6 Appendix 1: Reported administrative registers

Country	Official name of the register
Austria	Causes of Death statistics
	Birth Statistics
	Austrian National Cancer Registry
Belgium	healthdata.be (is not a register but technical platform and service provider that will consolidate all patient registries in Belgium)
Croatia	Croatian National Cancer Registry
Cyprus	Causes of Death Registry
	Birth Registry
	HIV/AIDS Registry
	Cancer Register
Czech Republic	Czech National Cancer Registry
	National Register of Reproduction Health
	National Register of Hospitalised Patients
	Information system Deaths
Denmark	Danish Occupational Hospital Register
	Occupational Birth Register
	Dødsårsagsregistret
	Fødselsregistret
	Lægemiddelregistret
	Landspatientregistret
	Statistics Denmark
	The Danish Cancer Register
Finland	Finnish Cancer Registry
	Care Register for Health Care
	Archive of death certificates
	Statistics on reimbursements for prescription medicines
	Medical Birth Register
	Register of Congenital malformations
France	Aquitaine Registry on Interventional Cardiology (ACIRA)
	Digestive cancers registry of Burgundy
	Côte d'Or registry of haematological malignancies (RHEMCO)
	French registry of pleural mesothelioma cases (MESONAT)
	Gironde register of primitive tumours of the central nervous system (Certified Registry 2012-2015)
	Registry on Breast Cancer Patients from The Antoine Lacassagne Centre (SEINON)
	Severe Obesity outcome Network (SOON)
	National cohort on the vascular Ehlers-Danlos syndrome (SEDv)
	Dijon Stroke Registry
	Registry of Congenital Malformations in Alsace (Certified Registry) (REMACA)
	Cancer Registry of French Guiana (certified cancer registry) (RCG)
	Registry of general cancers in Gironde
	Tarn Cancer Registry (Certified Registry 2010-2013) (RCT)
	General Registry on Cancer in the Poitou-Charentes Region (Certified 2013-2015 Registry)
	Somme Cancer Registry (Certified Registry 2013-2016)
	Registre Régional des Hémopathies Malignes de Basse Normandie (Certified register) (RRHMBN)
	ISERE CANCER REGISTER
	Doubs and Territoire de Belfort primitive malignant tumors register
	Cancer Registry of the Manche (certified registry)
	Bas-Rhin Cancer Registry (Certified Registry)

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Country	Official name of the register
	Bas Rhin Ischaemic Heart Disease Register (Certified Register 2013-2016)
	Doubs and Côte d'Or viral hepatitis register
	Registry of general cancers in Lille and its periphery
	Hérault Cancer Registry (Certified Registry 2010-2013)
	Gironde register of hematologic malignancies
	Finistère Registry for Digestive Tumours (Certified Registry 2013-2016)
	Ile de la Réunion Congenital anomalies register
	The Côte d'Or registry for breast cancer and gynecological cancers (Certified Registry)
	The Brest REGistry of STroke (BREST) (certified register 2011-2017)
	Midi-PYRENEÉS CYTOPENIA REGISTRY (CARMEN)
	Limousin Region General Cancer Registry (CERTIFIED REGISTRY 2015-2020)
	Aquitaine Registry on Interventional Cardiology (ACIRA)
	Registry on Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS) in Limousin (FRALim)
Germany	Centre for Cancer Registry Data (Zentrum für Krebsregisterdaten)
Iceland	Icelandic Birth Register
	Icelandic Causes of Death Register
	Prescription drugs database
Ireland	National Cancer Registry of Ireland (NCRI)
	Computerised Infectious Disease Reporting
Israel	Cancer
	The Israeli National Cancer Registry
	National diabetes registry
	National stroke registry
	Birth register
	Death
Lithuania	Lithuanian Cancer Register
	Occupational Disease Register
	Register of blood donor
	Causes of Death Register
	Children health monitoring system
	Injury and Accident Monitoring
Netherlands	Doodsoorzaken register (Causes of death register)
	Dutch population register (Basisregistratie Personen, or BRP)
Norway	Medical Birth Registry of Norway
	Norwegian Registry of Pregnancy Termination
	Norwegian Cardiovascular Disease Registry
	Norwegian Cause of Death Registry
	Norwegian Prescription Database (NorPD)
	Norwegian Immunisation Registry SYSVAK
	Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS)
	Norwegian Surveillance System for Infections in Hospitals (NOIS)
	Norwegian Patient Registry
	Cancer Registry of Norway
	Registry of the Norwegian Armed Forces Medical Services
Poland	General Hospital Morbidity Study
	PESEL (Polish Powszechny Elektroniczny System Ewidencji Ludności, Universal Electronic System for Registration of the Population)
Portugal	National Registry of Congenital Anomalies
	Birth Register
	Cause of death
	In-patient hospitalizations
	National Cancer Registry

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Country	Official name of the register
	Prescription of medications – (PEM – Prescrição Eletrónica de Medicamentos)
Slovakia	National registry of Congenital malformations
	National stroke register
	Birth register
	Report on admission of inpatients care Z (MZ SR) 1-12
	Reporting of deaths and causes of death
Slovenia	Register raka Slovenije
	birth register
	Register umrlih
	Register hospitaliziranih
	Baza zdravil
Spain	Comunitat Valenciana Childhood Cancer Registry
	Girona Cancer Registry
	National registry of specialized care (administrative and clinical database for inpatient, daycases, emergencies and daysurgery)
	Registro de Cáncer de Castellón (Castellón Cancer Registry)
Sweden	Cause of death register
	Register of prescription of medications
	Longitudinal integration database for health Insurance and occupational studies (LISA)
	The Swedish Medical Birth Register
	the National Patient Register
	The Swedish Cancer Registry
Switzerland	Enquête suisse sur la santé
	Swiss Multiple Sclerosis Registry
	National Institute for Cancer Epidemiology and Registration (NICER)
	Swiss Newborn Screening
	Swiss Diabetes Registry - SwissDiab Study (SwissDiab)
	AMIS Plus (Acute Myocardial Infarction in Switzerland)
	Swiss Rare Disease Registry (SRDR)
	Causes of death statistic

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Part C. Measuring potential health effects of the priority substances

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2 Potential health effects of the HBM4EU priority substances

In HBM4EU, two rounds of prioritisation of the substances have been made and substances listed in Table 1 were selected. The prioritisation process aimed to identify a set of substances for which knowledge is needed to support current EU policy making. The prioritisation strategy is described in detail in Deliverable D4.3.¹² The prioritisation criteria included aspects such as concern about human health, available evidence of human and/or environmental exposure at EU level and if there were any open policy questions.

Table 1: HBM4EU priority substances

1 st priority substances	2 nd priority substances
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phthalates and DINCH • Bisphenols • Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) • Flame retardants (FR) • Cadmium (Cd) • Hexavalent Chromium (Cr VI) • PAH • Anilines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acrylamides • Aprotic Solvents • Arsenic • Disyoanites • Lead • Mercury • Mycotoxin • Pesticides • UV filters

For each of the selected priority substances, a scoping document has been prepared. These documents are available through HBM4EU web site at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/the-substances/> and include also a section about hazardous properties of the specific substance. By reviewing these scoping documents, Table 2 was compiled to include information about known and suspected health effects of different priority substances. Table 2 demonstrates that HBM4EU priority substances are linked to several health effects and same health effects are affected by many substances.

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Table 2: Known or suspected health effects of different priority substances

	1 st priority substances							2 nd priority substances									
	Phthalates & DINCH	Bisphenols	PFASs	FR	Cd	Cr VI	PAH	Anilines	Acrylamide	Aprotic Solvents	Arsenic	Disocyanites	Lead	Mercury	Mycotoxins	Pesticides	UV filter
Endocrine disruption	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓					✓		✓	✓	✓
Reproductive health	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Foetal development		✓			✓				✓	✓	✓		✓		✓		
Puberty development	✓	✓	✓														
Cognitive development	✓	✓									✓		✓			✓	✓
Neurological problems		✓	✓						✓		✓		✓	✓		✓	
Immune system		✓	✓				✓		✓				✓		✓	✓	
Haematological system													✓	✓			✓
Obesity, metabolic syndrome		✓	✓		✓						✓						
Diabetes		✓			✓						✓						

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3 How to obtain information for identified health effects?

This section will provide some information about how information/outcomes for identified or suspected health effects of the HBM4EU priority substances could be obtained. Here the focus is on direct health outcomes, while WP14 has worked on more detail about potential effect biomarkers for health effects of interest.¹³

3.1 Endocrine disruption

The endocrine system is the collection of glands (pituitary gland, thyroid gland, parathyroid glands, adrenal glands, pancreas, and ovaries in females and testicles in males) (Figure 1.) which produce hormones that regulate metabolism, growth and development, tissue function, sexual function, reproduction, sleep, and mood, among other things. Some chemicals are known to affect the hormone production of these glands or the activity of the endogenous hormones and are therefore called endocrine disruptors. However, some chemicals can also affect the endocrine organs in other mechanisms and be thereby involved in the development of cancers or benign tumors or a thyroid disease such as struma.

A recent definition of an endocrine disrupting chemical (EDC) by the Endocrine Society is “an exogenous chemical, or mixture of chemicals, that interferes with any aspect of hormone action”, or more specifically, hormone receptor activation that leads to developmental or physiological effects.¹⁴

Endogenous levels of most hormones are strictly regulated in so-called hormone axes with negative feedback loops between the interrelated hormones. Adverse health effects of endocrine disruptors are caused by their ability to disrupt these endogenous hormone balances. Clinical and subclinical effects of endocrine disruption may therefore be assessed by measuring panels of interrelated hormones within the same hormone axis.

Most hormones circulate at extremely low concentrations, typically in the pico- (10^{-12}) or nanomolar (10^{-9}) range, and often in a milieu of closely related and potentially interfering compounds making great demands on method sensitivity and specificity. The most common procedures currently used to measure hormones are immuno- and immunometric assays but gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GCMS) and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) also have a place.

Figure 1: Major endocrine glands

(Picture Wikipedia, picture reused according to Wikipedias licence to copy picture (granted to copy, distribute and/or modify this document under the terms of the GNU Free Documentation License); https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Illu_endocrine_system.jpg. Date last accessed 2019-03-01)

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Liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) is increasingly regarded as the state-of-the-art method for measurement of some hormones, such as sex steroids.¹⁵

3.2 Reproductive health and foetal development

The development of the reproductive system in human occurs early during embryonic and foetal stages and continues from birth to the end of puberty. Markers of reproductive health and foetal development have to be measurable, standardised, valid and unchanged in time to allow durable comparisons. Depending on the marker, it can be measured either at birth, during childhood, at puberty or during adulthood. Anogenital distance, cryptorchidism, hypospadias, semen quality, sperm DNA damage, fertility and fecundity, reproductive hormones and birth weight are used in the assessment of reproductive health and foetal development.

3.2.1 Anogenital distance

Anogenital distance (AGD) is the distance between the anus and the external genitalia and can be measured among new-borns, children or adults. A short male AGD is strongly associated with genital malformations at birth and reproductive disorders in adulthood¹⁶. Regulated by dihydrotestosterone, AGD is a hormone-sensitive marker of development in rodent models, and presumably reflects the gestational androgen exposure.¹⁷ In humans, there is a sex difference in AGD length between normal males and normal females (50–100%).¹⁸ Clinical measurement of AGD may provide a means of ‘looking back in time’ and discerning the level of androgen exposure during the “Masculinisation Programming Window” during early gestation. It can serve as a lifelong biomarker of the action of androgens in utero, or conversely, on the androgen effect’s disruption. It has been used as a non-invasive biomarker of androgen disruption in utero by several groups of investigators.¹⁹

AGD can be measured (in mm) or using anogenital index (AGI, dimensionless).²⁰

3.2.2 Cryptorchidism

Cryptorchidism is defined as the non-descent or the absence of at least one testicle in the scrotum. It is the most common male genital defect at birth.²¹ Testicular descent occurs in two phases, an abdominal descent phase during the first trimester and an inguinal scrotal descent phase during the third trimester. The latter phase is primarily influenced by testicular androgens.²² Testicular descent is normally controlled by endocrinal factors. Chemical substances with endocrine-inducing effects can lead to the risk of cryptorchidism in sons of mothers exposed during pregnancy.²³

The diagnosis of cryptorchidism is mainly done by physical examination (palpable testes), but in some cases may also require laparoscopic surgery (nonpalpable undescended tests)²⁴ which is not feasible in the population studies.

3.2.3 Hypospadias

Hypospadias result from incomplete urethral closure during development of the external genitalia, between the 8th and 12th gestational weeks.²⁵ Some studies have shown a positive relationship between potential exposures to endocrine-disrupting chemicals during pregnancy with hypospadias in male children.^{26,27} The diagnosis of hypospadias (ICD-10: Q54) is usually made after birth during a physical exam.²⁸

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3.2.4 Semen quality

Semen quality is not a single outcome measure but an overall term that includes three main indicators:

- 1) sperm count (millions of sperm per millilitre),
- 2) total motility (%) and
- 3) morphology (percentage of morphologically normal forms).²⁹

Investigators often dichotomize outcomes according to guidelines adopted by the World Health Organization, most recently including sperm concentration 15,000,000/mL or more, motility 40% or higher, and normal morphology 4% or higher.³⁰ The assessment of these parameters requires a spermogram in a specialised laboratory.

In France, the observed decreasing trend in sperm concentration and morphology between 1989 and 2005 in the general metropolitan population, in almost all French regions, reinforced the suspects of the endocrine disruptor effect hypothesis, especially from a wide environmental exposure.³¹

3.2.5 Sperm DNA damage

Damage to the male genetic complement contained within sperm may lead to delayed fertilisation, compromised implantation and infertility.³² In the literature, a number of hypotheses have been proposed to explain how environmental factors, including chemical agents, could affect sperm DNA integrity. However, there is still uncertainty about the best laboratory tests to identify and quantify such DNA damage.³³

3.2.6 Fertility and fecundity

Fertility is commonly defined as the ability of a couple to achieve pregnancies that survive to birth.³⁴ Clinical infertility is defined as the inability to become pregnant after 12 months of unprotected intercourse.³⁵ Fecundity is a woman's biological ability to reproduce based on the monthly probability of conception.³⁶

Looking for an association between chemical exposure and infertility could provide information on the effect of chemical exposure on overall reproductive fitness.

For epidemiological studies, information on fertility and fecundity can be obtained through self-reporting. HBM4EU basic questionnaire has a set of standardised questions, specific for both men and women, about problems related to fertility.

3.2.7 Reproductive hormones

Reproductive hormone levels are potential indicators of endocrine disruption among the general population. Furthermore, their levels are easily quantifiable in blood.

The male reproductive hormones include testosterone, luteinising hormone, sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), INSL3, inhibin b and follicle stimulating hormone. For females, the reproductive hormones include prolactin, oxytocin, estradiol, progesterone, activin, prostaglandin F2 α , prostaglandin PGE2, human chorionic gonadotrophin, placental lactogen, gonadotropin releasing hormone, relaxin and AMH (anti-Müllerian hormone). AMH is the only hormone that can give an idea of ovarian reserves since there is no oocyte quality marker.³⁷

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Exposure to chemicals during pregnancy may also cause adverse effects on the development of reproductive system in utero.

3.2.8 Birth weight

Exposure to environmental stressors during the highly sensitive period of embryonic and foetal development can induce later phenotypic variation due to adaptive developmental plasticity, mediated in part by epigenetic changes, and increase the risk of chronic diseases later in life. Low birth weight is a non-specific adverse birth outcome which may reflect prematurity or foetal growth restriction related to a suboptimal intrauterine environment, such as impaired placental function, and other causal risk factors.

For epidemiological studies, information about birth weight can be obtained either through questionnaire or birth registers. A Norwegian study found that maternal self-reported information about birth weight is very reliable.³⁸ On average, -0.03 (sd=0.20) kg difference was observed between self-reported and register based data.

3.3 Puberty development

The age of pubertal onset has been reported to be occurring at younger ages in both girls and boys than before although the evidence in boys is more limited compared to girls.³⁹ Although the mechanisms triggering puberty onset are poorly understood, gonadal steroids play a key role in the process.

Optimally, evaluation of pubertal onset and progression in children should be performed by trained health care professional by visual inspection and palpation. Despite that the physical examinations are considered the most accurate method of determining the pubertal stage, the examinations can, however, be logistically challenging especially in large sample sizes. As an alternative to physical examinations, self-assessment of puberty either by the child or parent(s) has been suggested. A number of studies have observed reasonable agreement between self-assessment and examination by physician in the simple distinction between pre-puberty and puberty whereas self-assessment is not a reliable measure of determining exact puberty.^{40,41,42} Thus, the choice of method for assessing puberty either by performing physical examinations or using self-assessment should depend on the specific aim of the study. In large epidemiologic studies, self-assessment may be sufficiently accurate for a simple distinction between pre-puberty and puberty.

More details about the procedures to be used for evaluation of puberty development can be found in Part D, Chapter 5 of this report.

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3.4 Cognitive development

Cognitive development refers to the development of thought processes such as information processing, intelligence, reasoning, language development and memory. Chemical exposure early in life may affect the different aspects of cognitive development.^{43,44}

Cognitive and psychomotor developments can be evaluated with several batteries (Table 3).

Table 3: Tests and tools for evaluation of cognitive and psychomotor development

Test/Tool	Target age group	Measured areas of development	Notes
The Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID-III) ⁴⁵	From birth to 42 months	Cognitive, language and motor development	This test has been confirmed as a gold standard measure for infant and toddler development.
The Developmental Indicators for the Assessment of Learning™, Fourth Edition (DIAL™-4) ⁴⁶	2-6 years through 5-11 years	Motor, conceptual and language skills	DIAL™-4 is not a diagnostic test or intelligent test, it is rather a screening tool.
Battelle Development Inventory, 2nd Edition (BDI-2) ⁴⁷	From birth through age 7 years 11 months	Typical development of young children, including screening for school readiness; and assessing or identifying developmental delay or disability	Not intended as an instrument to diagnose specific disabilities
The Differential Ability Scales: 2nd Edition (DAS-II) ⁴⁸	From 2 years 6 months through 17 years 11 months	Verbal, nonverbal, and spatial reasoning	
The McCarthy Scales of Children's Abilities (MCSA) ⁴⁹	4-5 years	A global score for general cognitive development and scores for five subscales (verbal, perceptive-performance, memory, quantitative, and motor development).	
The California Preschool Social Competence Scale (CPSCS) ⁵⁰	4-5 year	To evaluate social competence by measuring the appropriateness of preschool children's interpersonal behaviour and their degree of social responsibility, and includes the concept of independence, understood as interpersonal autonomy.	
The DSM-IV form list of Attention-Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) Criteria (ADHD-DSM-IV) ⁵¹		To evaluate attention-deficit, hyperactivity and impulsivity	
The Childhood Asperger Syndrome Test (CAST) ^{52,53}		To determine autism-spectrum traits.	

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Test/Tool	Target age group	Measured areas of development	Notes
the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire. ⁵⁴		Total behaviour problems	
The Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence (WPPSI-III) ⁵⁵		To evaluate cognitive development	The WPPSI-III provides subtest and composite scores that represent intellectual functioning in verbal and performance cognitive domains, as well as a composite score that represents a child's general intellectual ability.
The Child Behaviour Checklist (CBCL) ⁵⁶	1½ -5 years	Identifying problem behaviour in children	It is used as a diagnostic tool for a variety of behavioural and emotional problems that can be classified as internalising and externalising behaviours, such as attention deficit hyperactive disorder, oppositional defiant disorder, conduct disorder, depression, separation anxiety, phobia, social phobia and a number of other childhood and adolescent issues

3.5 Neurological problems

Neurotoxic agents are known to alter the normal activity of the nervous system. The nervous system is an exceptionally complex system with multiple potential target sites for potentially neurotoxic chemicals. A wide range of methods are available for the assessment of potential neurotoxicity on humans. The choice of assessment methods depends to some extent on what is known regarding the effects of the compound, the purpose of the evaluation and the feasibility of different methods in different types of studies.

Among adults, neurotoxicology evaluations are focused on nervous system structure and function, and among children focus is on development of nervous system.⁵⁷ Among adults, the effects of neurotoxins can be grouped into the effects on motor activities, sensory activities and cognitive functions.⁵⁸ Pre- and post-natal chemical exposures of children are known to result in neurobehavioral problems and even impaired intelligence quotient (IQ).^{59,60,61,62} Chemical neurotoxicity may be manifested as decreases in functional capabilities or delays in normative developmental progression.

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3.5.1 Neurological assessment in adults

Effects of neurotoxicity can be evaluated using clinical methods including neurobehavioral and neuropsychological methods, electrophysiological tests and neuroimaging techniques.

Current approaches in the clinical evaluation of neurotoxic disease and descriptions of neurotoxic syndromes associated with exposure to different agents have been published.^{63,64,65}

Neuropsychological testing is often carried out in the clinical evaluation of neurotoxicity, especially in those cases where there is an indication of cognitive or affective changes.^{64,65} There are several test batteries for clinical neuropsychological testing and some of them are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Examples of tests in a clinical neuropsychological battery⁶⁶

Domain/tests	Description/comments
General intellect	
Wechsler Adult Intelligence Scale-Revised (WAIS-R)	Full-scale IQ, Verbal IQ and Performance IQ constitute measures of general level of cognitive ability compared with population norms; some subtests can serve as "hold" tests
Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test	Measure of verbal intelligence in adults
Wide-range Achievement Test	Measures academic skills in arithmetic, spelling, reading; used to estimate premorbid ability patterns in adults
Attention and executive function	
Digit Span Subtest (WAIS-R)	Immediate recall of digits forwards and backwards; measures simple attention and tracking
Trail Making Test	Connect-a-dot task; measures attention, sequencing, scanning
Continuous Performance Test	Automated test of attention
Paced Auditory Serial Addition	Serial calculation tests; sensitive measure of attention/tracking
Wisconsin Card Sorting Test	Requires inference of decision-making rules; assesses mental flexibility
Verbal ability and language	
Information Subtest (WAIS-R)	Recall of information usually learned in school; robust estimate of native ability in adults
Vocabulary Subtest (WAIS-R)	Fairly robust estimate of verbal intelligence in adults
Similarities Subtest (WAIS-R)	Calls for inference of similarities between nominative words; assesses verbal reasoning
Boston Naming Test	Naming of objects from line drawings; sensitive to aphasia
Visuospatial and visuomotor	
Digit Symbol Subtest (WAIS-R)	Requires matching symbols to digits; assesses perceptual coding and motor speed
Rey-Osterreith Complex Figure	"Copy condition" assesses visuospatial planning and construction
Santa Ana Form Board	Measures motor speed and coordination
Finger Tapping Test	Electronic or mechanical counting of finger tapping speed
Memory	
Wechsler Memory Scale-Revised	Assesses learning and retention of verbal and visual material
California Verbal Learning Test	Provides multiple measures of new verbal learning, recall, recognition memory, use of strategies, inference
Rey-Osterreith Complex Figure	Recall condition assesses memory for complex visual information

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Domain/tests	Description/comments
Mood and personality	
Profile of Mood States (POMS)	Multiple scales of severity ratings of affective symptoms; sensitive to mood disturbance and affective changes
Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory-Revised (MMPI-R)	Personality inventory; provides description of current personality function; some scales sensitive to toxic exposures

The WHO has published a Neurobehavioral Core Test Battery (NCTB) (Table 5.) which can be used on an international scale, in epidemiological studies.⁶⁷ NCTB is relatively inexpensive and easy to use. Also tests listed in Table 6 are commonly used in research studies to assess effects of neurotoxicity on humans.

Table 5: WHO Neurobehavioral Core Test Battery (NCTB)

Domain	Test
Perceptual coding	Digit Symbol (WAIS-R)
Attention and short-term memory	Simple Reaction Time Digit Span (WAIS-R) Benton Visual Recognition
Psychomotor performance	Aiming Motor Santa Ana Form Board
Mood and affect	Profile of Mood States (POMS) Questionnaire

Table 6: Some automated test batteries used in neurotoxicology research⁶⁸

System name	Number of tests	Number of rating scales	Reference
Behavioural Assessment & Research System	4	0	Anger et al. (1994) ⁶⁹
Cognitive Function Scanner	8	0	Laursen (1990) ⁷⁰
Information Processing & Performance Test Battery	8	0	Williamson (1990) ⁷¹
Milan Automated Neurobehavioural System	7	0	Cassito et al. (1989) ⁷²
Microtox System	17	0	Eckerman et al. (1985) ⁷³
Neurobehavioural Evaluation System (NES)	17	1	Baker et al. (1985) ⁷⁴
Swedish Performance Evaluation System (SPES)	18	5	Gamberale et al. (1990) ⁷⁵

Since changes in affect are some of the most dramatic effects of severe neurotoxic exposures⁷⁶, questionnaires and symptom ratings are typically included both in the assessment of individual neurotoxicity cases and in epidemiological studies of exposed populations.

The Minnesota Multiphasic Personality Inventory (MMPI-R), which contains over 500 items requiring a yes/no response, is not feasible to use in population studies due to its length and the nature of some of the questions. The modified version of the Profile of Mood States Questionnaire (POMS)^{77,78}, which is a 65-item rating scale of mood state, have been incorporated into the NCTB and Neurobehavioural Evaluation System (NES) test batteries for use in cross-sectional studies.

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There are also a number of questionnaires and rating scales specifically developed to obtain information in a standardised manner regarding subjective complaints associated with neurotoxic exposure.^{79,80} For example:

- The Q16 questionnaire on symptoms of the early effects of neurotoxic exposures in working populations.⁸¹
- The Neurotoxic Symptom Checklist-60 (NSC-60) on information regarding mood and affect, absentmindedness and memory problems, sensory and motor disturbances, chest problems, equilibrium disturbances, somatic problems, fatigue and sleep disturbances, as well as 7 personality items.⁸²
- The NSC-60 on work exposures.^{83,84}

Because sensory and motor changes have often been associated with exposure to particular chemicals, also behavioural methodologies have been used to provide quantitative measures of different aspects of visual, somatosensory and olfactory function⁸⁵. There are also quantitative measures to examine the effects of chemicals on postural balance and tremor⁸⁶. These methods have been developed for the purpose of monitoring and health surveillance in field studies of exposed workers. Further, behavioural neurophysiological tests constitute part of the Adult Environmental Neurobehavioral Test Battery (AENTB).^{87,88}

In addition to behavioural tests to evaluate visual and somatosensory function, for example the University of Pennsylvania smell identification kit, to examine odour identification and olfactory perception threshold are available.⁸⁹

Quantitative methods, using computer and other technological devices, for examining postural sway are also being used in epidemiological and laboratory investigations of effects of pesticides and solvents.^{90,86} Similarly mechanical and capacitive field methods for assessing the amplitude and frequency of tremor are commonly use.⁹¹

Electrophysiological methods are generally used to diagnose individual patients but could be applied to the study of exposed populations, particularly exposed workers⁹².

Neuroimaging techniques such as computerised axial tomography (CAT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography (PET) and single photon emission computerised tomography (SPECT) provide an invaluable measure of local brain function and dysfunction, which can be integrated with neurobehavioral measures for studying brain-behaviour relationships at the human level.

Neuroimaging methods have proven extremely useful in the diagnosis of certain neurological diseases and are being increasingly used in neurotoxicity studies.^{93,94,95}

3.5.2 Assessment of neurological development among children

Chemical exposure early in life may impair the neurodevelopment of children.^{96,97,98} The end-points frequently used to assess developmental neurotoxicity in exposed children have been reviewed⁹⁹ as well as the methodological issues associated with the design of prospective, longitudinal developmental studies¹⁰⁰.

The neurologic development status among children can be assessed with questionnaires and examinations. Of the questionnaires, the Ages and Stages Questionnaire, third edition (ASQ-3) is the most validated scale, and has been recommended by the UNICEF to verify if children have a normal neurological development.^{101,102,103} It is a monitoring instrument to assess the main

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developmental areas, including communication, gross motor, fine motor, personal-social, and problem solving skills, and to compare the local population to the international development standards. Parents/guardians administer the questionnaire. The Parents' evaluation of developmental status (PEDS) is also administered by parents/guardians.^{104,105} It is primarily used to identify general developmental delay in primary care.

The neurologic examinations are performed by professionals (doctors, psychologists, teachers etc., depending on the examination). They include the Bayley III Cognitive score^{106,107}, Touwen Infant Neurological Examination (TINE)¹⁰⁸, Amiel-Tison neurologic assessment¹⁰⁹, Milani-Comparetti Motor Development Screening Test¹¹⁰ and Hammersmith Infant Neurological Examination (HINE)¹¹¹.

Culture-specific issues have to be considered when using any of the questionnaires or examination batteries. In some countries, country-specific assessment methods have also been developed.

3.6 Immune system

Several chemicals are associated with immunotoxic effects. For example, there is evidence that exposure to bisphenol A and phthalates might increase the risk of asthma symptoms and respiratory tract infections throughout childhood^{112,113,114}.

Comprehensive analysis of immune cell function is biomarker based. A variety of panels for comprehensive immunophenotyping has been published. These panels were designed for clinical applications such as the diagnosis of primary immune deficiencies¹¹⁵ or myelodysplastic syndromes¹¹⁶, or monitoring of patients after transplantation¹¹⁷. Furthermore, a great number of panels were developed to study phenotype and function of specific cell types.¹¹⁸ Claus et al.¹¹⁹ have suggested a comprehensive approach to analyse the most common lymphocyte subpopulations in clinically healthy individuals based on the evaluation of absolute numbers and distribution of lymphocyte subsets, in addition to functional assays to measure key functions of T cells, natural killer (NK) cells and monocytes.

3.7 Obesity, metabolic syndrome and diabetes

WHO defines overweight and obesity as "abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that presents a risk to health". Obesity is a known risk factor for many chronic diseases and there is a clear association between obesity and type 2 diabetes, hypertension and dyslipidaemia. Metabolic syndrome is classified when obesity is associated with one or more CVD risk factors.¹²⁰ The discussion on the current obesity epidemic has included consideration on the possible role of chemical exposures in the development of obesity.^{121,122}

To determine obesity markers such as body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference or body fat % are used. For calculation of BMI, information about height and weight is required.

3.7.1 Height and weight

Information about height and weight can be obtained either through self-reporting or by measurement.

Standardised measurement protocol for height and weight measurement among adults is provided in the EHES Manual.¹²³ Corresponding protocol for children and adolescents is provided in this document under Part D, Section 4.

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For the evaluation of normal/abnormal growth from birth to adulthood, growth charts based on height and weight information are useful. Examples of such growth charts can be found from the WHO Child Growth Standards.^{124,125}

Among adults, studies on the validity of self-reported height and weight, with measured values as the reference data, have shown a tendency of subjects to over-estimate their height and underestimate their weight. It was also observed that the self-report bias was greater among overweight and obese participants than those of normal weight.¹²⁶

3.7.2 Waist circumference

Abdominal obesity is an important independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, dyslipidaemia and hypertension and is related to increased risk of all-cause mortality. Waist circumference and waist-to-height ratio are simple anthropometric indicators and are predictive of the risk of chronic disease.^{127,128} However, studies on the association of chemical exposure and waist circumference have not shown consistent results.^{129,130}

The WHO cut-points for increased disease risk by abdominal obesity are:¹³¹

- Waist circumference greater than 102 cm in men;
- Waist circumference greater than 88 cm in women

An additional measure of body fat distribution may be calculated given that also the hip circumference values are available. The waist-hip ratio (the waist circumference divided by the hip circumference) can also be used to define abdominal obesity, as it provides an index of both subcutaneous and intra-abdominal adipose tissue.

The WHO cut-points for increased disease risk by abdominal obesity by waist-hip ratio are:

- Waist-hip ratio greater than 0.90 in men;
- Waist-hip ratio greater than 0.85 in women.

Among adults, larger than normal range waist circumference is associated with an elevated risk of multiple cardiometabolic risk factors, even after adjusting for BMI. Among children and adolescents, the waist circumference/height ratio is recommended for evaluating the risk by age and sex.¹³²

Standardised measurement protocols for waist and hip circumferences among adults are provided in the EHES Manual.¹³³

3.7.3 Body Mass Index

Body Mass Index (BMI) is a ratio of weight relative to height squared, calculated by the formula

$$\text{BMI} = \frac{(\text{weight in kilograms})}{\text{height in meters}^2}$$

BMI is commonly used as an index to define different weight categories such as underweight, normal weight, overweight and obese. WHO has provided cut-points for different weight categories

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based on BMI for adults¹³⁴ and children¹³⁵. For children also International Obesity Taskforce (IOTF) has provided a definition of overweight and obesity.¹³⁶

Table 7: Body mass index (BMI) classification for adults based originally on WHO classification

Classification	BMI (kg/m ²)	Risk of comorbidities
Underweight	<18.5	Low (but risk of other clinical problems increased)
Normal range	18.5–24.9	Average
Overweight (preobese)	25.0–29.9	Mildly increased
Obese	≥30.0	
Class I	30.0–34.9	Moderate
Class II	35.0–39.9	Severe
Class III	≥40.0	Very severe

When self-reported information on height and weight among adults was used, the BMI was generally under-estimated in comparison to measured height and weight.¹³⁷

Since BMI is not a direct measurement of body fat and does not distinguish between muscle weight and body fat weight, so in some cases, BMI is not recommended for assessing obesity. In cases of more or less muscle than normal (athletes) or some clinical conditions (water retention or amputees), BMI may not reflect the amount of body fat.

3.7.4 Body fat %

Body fat % (BF%) refers to the proportion of fat related to total body weight. BF% can be measured using bioimpedance device, DEXA or skinfold measurement.

Cut-off values to classify obesity should vary with sex and age. However, there is no consensus on fat ranges as there are no appropriate prospective studies on how body fat is linked with morbidity and mortality.¹³⁸ American Council of Exercise proposed 32% BF for adult women and 25% BF for adult men as the healthy top cut-point. The tendency with age is a higher cut-off with increasing age.

BF% may be calculated with skinfolds measurements, an alternative which is less frequently used nowadays. Skinfolds were assessed in USA's National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) since 1960 but dropped out since 2011-2014 survey.¹³⁹ Some common skinfolds are triceps (back of the upper arm); pectoral (mid-chest, just forward of the armpit); subscapular (beneath the edge of the shoulder blade); midaxilla (midline of the side of the torso); abdomen (next to the belly button); suprailiac (just above the iliac crest of the hip bone); and quadriceps (middle of the upper thigh). With skinfold measures, the Jackson-Pollock formula estimates the body fat mass:

- Men BF = $1.10938 - 0.0008267(Y) + 0.0000016(Y^2) - 0.0002574(\text{Age})$
where Y= sum of Chest, Abdominal and Thigh skinfolds in mm
- Women BF = $1.0994291 - 0.0009929(Z) + 0.0000023(Z^2) - 0.0001392(\text{Age})$
where Z = sum of Triceps, Thigh and Suprailiac skinfolds in mm.

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If bioimpedance device is used for assessing BF%, it is important to acknowledge that the results from different bioimpedance monitors are not directly comparable. The interpretation of the results is also device specific.

Validation studies have shown fairly good correlation between body fat or fat free mass measures for skinfolds, leg-to-leg bioelectric impedance and hand-held impedance with DEXA.^{140,141}

3.7.5 Metabolic syndrome

Metabolic syndrome is a multiplex risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD). The components may vary between abdominal obesity, dyslipidaemia, high blood pressure, insulin resistance and others. It is comprised of a combination of risk factors for coronary heart disease, as well as for diabetes, fatty liver, and several cancers.¹⁴²

There is no internationally agreed uniform definition of metabolic syndrome. The criteria differ between institutions (see Table 8).

Table 8: Definition of metabolic syndrome by different institutions¹⁴³

	IDF	NCEP	WHO	AACE
Definition	Diagnosed if glycaemia is abnormal and 2 further criteria are present	Diagnosed if 3 out of 5 criteria are present	Diagnosed if glycaemia is abnormal and 2 further criteria are present	Indicates risk factors
Glycaemia criteria	Fasting glycaemia 5.6–6.8 mmol/l (100–123 mg/dl) or DM2	Glycaemia 6.1–6.9 mmol/l (110–124 mg/dl)	Glucose intolerance, DM2 or insulin-resistance due to HOMA-IR	Fasting glycaemia 6.1–6.9 mmol/l (110–125 mg/dl) or > 7.8 mmol/l (140 mg/dl) 2 hours after oral GTT
Obesity criteria	WC ≥ 94 cm for men, WC ≥ 80 cm for women	WC > 102 for men, WC > 88 cm for women	BMI >30 and HWR > 0.9 for men and >0.85 for women	BMI ≥ 25 and WC > 102 cm for men and WC > 88 cm for women
Dyslipidaemia criteria	Triglycerides ≥ 1.7 mmol/l (150 mg/dl) or HDL < 1.0 mmol/l (40 mg/dl) for men, < 1.3 mmol/l (50 mg/dl) for women	Triglycerides ≥ 1.7 mmol/l (150 mg/dl) or HDL < 1.0 mmol/l (40 mg/dl) for men, < 1.3 mmol/l (50 mg/dl) for women	Triglycerides ≥ 1.7 mmol/l (150 mg/dl) or HDL < 0.9 mmol/l (35 mg/dl) for men, < 1.0 mmol/l (39 mg/dl) for women	Triglycerides ≥ 1.7 mmol/l (150 mg/dl) or HDL < 1.0 mmol/l (40 mg/dl) for men, < 1.3 mmol/l (50 mg/dl) for women
Hypertension criteria	On treatment for systemic arterial hypertension or BP ≥130x85 mmHg	BP ≥ 130x85 mmHg	On treatment for systemic arterial hypertension or BP ≥ 160x90 mmHg	BP ≥ 130x85 mmHg
Other indicators and their criteria			Microalbuminuria ≥ 20 mcg/min	

AACE = American College of Endocrinology / American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists; BMI = Body mass index; BP = arterial blood pressure; DM2 = diabetes mellitus type 2; GTT = oral glucose tolerance test; HOMA = homeostasis model assessment; HWR = hip:waist ratio; IDF = International Diabetes Federation; M = men; NCEP = US National Cholesterol Education Program; SAH = systemic arterial hypertension; Tg = triglycerides; W = women; WC = waist circumference; WHO = World Health Organization.

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3.7.6 Diabetes

Diabetes is an important public health problem. The majority of people with diabetes are affected by type 2 diabetes despite separate global estimates of diabetes prevalence for type 1 and type 2 does not exist. Type 1 diabetes cannot be prevented but effective approaches are available to prevent type 2 diabetes and to prevent the complications and premature death that can result from all types of diabetes.¹⁴⁴

There is also some evidence that for example long-term exposure to bisphenol A might increase the onset of diabetes through changes in human metabolome.¹⁴⁵

WHO defines diabetes with the following criteria:^{144,146}

- fasting plasma glucose ≥ 7.0 mmol/l (126mg/dl) or
- 2h plasma glucose ≥ 11.1 mmol/l (200mg/dl) after a 75-g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) or
- HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$

Between the normal glucose homeostasis and diabetes, there is a pre-diabetic condition with two intermediate stages of abnormal glucose regulation that can be classified as impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) and impaired fasting glucose (IFG). Current estimates indicate that most individuals (perhaps up to 70%) with these pre-diabetic conditions eventually develop diabetes in the future.¹⁴⁷

The WHO recommendations for the diagnostic criteria for IGT and IFG are as follows:¹⁴⁴

IGT

- fasting plasma glucose < 7.0 mmol/l (126mg/dl) and
- 2h plasma glucose ≥ 7.8 mmol/l and < 11.1 mmol/l (140 mg/dl and 200mg/dl) after a 75-g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT)

IFG

- fasting plasma glucose 6.1 to 6.9 mmol/l (110 mg/dl to 125 mg/dl) and (if measured)
- 2h plasma glucose < 7.8 mmol/l (140 mg/dl) after a 75-g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT)

In survey settings, the OGTT is often not feasible. Other data sources are fasting glucose values or HbA1c values, self-reported information on diabetes diagnosis and the use of medication for diabetes. In some countries, data from medical records or administrative registers can also be utilised. A review on validity studies comparing self-reported information on diabetes with measured data or register data showed that the self-reported data was fairly valid and did not notably differ from the data obtained with the more objective methods.¹⁴⁸

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3.8 Cardiovascular diseases

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) comprises a group of disorders of heart and blood vessels, and includes CVDs due to atherosclerosis:

- ischaemic heart disease or coronary heart disease (heart attack),
- cerebrovascular disease (stroke), and
- diseases of the aorta and arteries, including hypertension and peripheral vascular disease;

and other CVDs

- congenital heart disease,
- rheumatic heart disease,
- cardiomyopathies, and
- cardiac arrhythmias.

The underlying mechanisms vary depending on the disease. Coronary artery disease, stroke, and peripheral artery disease involve atherosclerosis. This may be caused by high blood pressure, smoking, diabetes mellitus, lack of exercise, obesity, high blood cholesterol, poor diet, and excessive alcohol consumption, among others. High blood pressure is estimated to account for approximately 13% of CVD deaths, while tobacco accounts for 9%, diabetes for 6%, lack of exercise for 6% and obesity for 5% of cases. Rheumatic heart disease may follow untreated strep throat.^{149,150,151} Environmental chemical such as Bisphenol A (BPA) exposure has also gained increasing evidence as risk factors for CVD.^{152,153}

It is estimated that up to 90% of CVD may be preventable. Prevention of CVD involves improving risk factor status through health behaviours such as healthy eating, exercise, avoidance of tobacco smoke and limiting alcohol intake. Treating risk factors, such as high blood pressure, blood lipids and diabetes is also beneficial.¹⁵⁴

Cardiovascular disease can be diagnosed by blood tests, electrocardiogram (ECG), stress testing, echocardiography, coronary angiography and cardiac catheterisation, chest X-ray, electron-beam computed tomography (EBCT) or cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in clinical settings. Measurement of blood pressure as a risk factor for CVD is also important.

Blood tests include several biomarkers, some of them risk factors for heart disease such as total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, HDL cholesterol and triglycerides, Apolipoprotein A1 and B, C-reactive protein (CRP), and other direct markers of myocardial infarction such as cardiac troponin-T, fibrinogen, high levels of homocysteine, elevated asymmetric dimethylarginine and elevated brain natriuretic peptide (BNP).

In epidemiological studies, information on CVD can be obtained either through self-reported information, by some of the measurements such as electrocardiogram, blood pressure and carotid doppler ultrasonography, which are described below, heart rate variability (HRV), arterial stiffness and ergometry, or through medical records/register data. In addition to self-reported questionnaire data on disease diagnoses, questions on functional ability or symptoms of the participant that are related to cardiovascular health may be included (ability to walk a certain distance, shortness of breath, palpitations, chest pain etc.).

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Self-reported information on hypertension has been prone to underestimate its prevalence when compared to more objective data (medical records or blood pressure measurements in health examination surveys)¹⁴⁸. On the other hand, study participants tend to over-reports CVD diagnoses compared to medical records or administrative data.^{155,156,157,158}

3.8.1 Electrocardiogram (ECG)

Electrocardiogram (ECG) is a simple, non-invasive procedure used to record the electrical activity of the heart. Electrodes are placed on the skin of the chest and connected in a specific order to a machine that measures electrical activity all over the heart. Output usually appears on a long scroll of paper that displays a printed graph of activity on a computer screen. The initial diagnosis of heart attack is usually made through observation of a combination of clinical symptoms and characteristic ECG changes. An ECG can detect areas of muscle deprived of oxygen and/or dead tissue in the heart. If a planned medication is known to be potential to adversely affect heart function, a baseline ECG may be ordered before starting the medication, and follow-up testing may occur at regular intervals to look for any changes.

ECG has also been performed in health examination surveys.^{159,160} More information and a detailed protocol for ECG examination are provided in Part D, Chapter 7, in this document.

3.8.2 Blood pressure

As elevated blood pressure is one of the major risk factors for CVD, blood pressure measurement is an essential part of both clinical examinations and health examination surveys. The protocol for measuring blood pressure in health examination surveys among adults is available from the European Health Examination Survey (EHES project)¹⁶¹. A protocol for blood pressure measurement among children and adolescents is provided in Part D, Chapter 4, in this document.

3.8.3 Carotid Doppler ultrasonography

Carotid Doppler ultrasonography is a popular tool for evaluating atherosclerosis of the carotid artery. Its two-dimensional gray scale can be used for measuring the intima-media thickness, which is a very good marker for atherosclerosis and can aid in plaque characterisation. The plaque morphology is related to the risk of stroke. The ulceration of plaque is also known as one of the strong predictors of future embolic event risk. Patient position: 1) overhead position, in which the examiner sits beyond the patient's head beside the end of the examination table and use two hands for ultrasonography. The sonic window can be made wider and offers a clear view of the carotid artery especially from the posterolateral projection. 2) lateral sitting position, which is used for most other ultrasonography examinations. This position makes it easy to control the machines. However, the right posterior projection is somewhat more difficult. Between these two options, the overhead position for Doppler ultrasonography of the carotid artery is recommended. The optimal patient head position is tilted about 45° away from the artery being examined. The neck of the patient should be relaxed.

Carotid Doppler ultrasonography is used to evaluate the intima-medial thickness (IMT) widely used as one of the parameters of atherosclerosis; plaque morphology, such as the echogenicity of the plaque, the surface, presence of ulceration, as well as the presence of plaque and stenosis, important for predicting future cardiovascular events.¹⁶²

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3.9 Cancer

The data necessary for assessing cancer diagnosis can be obtained either directly by periodic examinations of individuals (using a combination of techniques), by obtaining data from disease registrations, hospital records, and death certificates or through self-reported information with a survey questionnaire.

Examinations used to for clinical diagnosis of cancer include laboratory samples, different imaging procedures and biopsies.

Histopathology/cytopathology

Historically, histopathology and cytopathology have been the main tools utilised in the diagnosis of cancer. While histopathology involves the examination of sampled whole tissue under the microscope, cytopathology is the study of individual cells in disease.

Molecular genetics/cytogenetics

Molecular and cytogenetic techniques are major diagnostic tools in oncology that are used to identify genetic changes that play a role in the development and progression of human malignancies.

Tumour markers/biomarkers

Tumour markers are substances released by cancer cells into the blood. They are used as an adjunct to other investigations in primary diagnosis. A range of potentially predictive markers have been identified.

In survey settings, diagnostic techniques used in the clinical diagnosis of cancer are most often not feasible. In some countries, medical records or other administrative registers are useful data sources for the assessment of the subjects' medical history of cancer. The cancer diagnoses from medical records can be linked to survey data using ICD codes for cancers.¹⁶³

Self-reported information on subjects' cancer history can be gathered by survey questionnaires. For HBM4EU, a set of standardised questions on cancer diagnoses and time and age during the diagnoses have been included to the basic questionnaire.

The accuracy of self-reported cancer diagnoses compared to medical records (cancer registry data) has shown to be related to cancer site. In a large (n=65 582) prospective study among US men and women, the sensitivity of exact matches was highest for breast, prostate, and lung cancers (0.91, 0.90, and 0.90, respectively) and lowest for rectal cancer and melanoma (0.16 and 0.53, respectively).¹⁶⁴ The overall sensitivity was 0.79. The study concluded that the accuracy between self-reported cancer and medical records was quite high, especially related to breast, prostate, lung and colon cancer or the occurrence of any cancer. Furthermore, similar results have been found in recent published Korean study which reported sensitivity of self-reported cancer history to be 0.72, but the accuracy varied by cancer cite.¹⁶⁵

3.10 Liver function

There is evidence for the association of environmental chemical exposure and the markers of liver function or liver damage.^{166,167} Liver function tests are blood tests used to help diagnose and monitor liver disease or damage.^{168,169} The tests measure the levels of certain enzymes and proteins in the blood. Some of these tests measure how well the liver is performing its normal

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functions of producing protein and clearing bilirubin, while other liver function tests measure enzymes that liver cells release in response to damage or disease.

Some common liver function tests include:

- Alanine transaminase (ALT)
- Aspartate transaminase (AST)
- Alkaline phosphatase (ALP)
- Albumin and total protein
- Bilirubin
- Gamma-glutamyltransferase (GGT)
- L-lactate dehydrogenase (LD)
- Prothrombin time (PT)

Depending on country-specific practices, information on liver dysfunction or liver diseases may also be obtained from medical records.¹⁷⁰

3.11 Renal function

The renal diseases acute kidney injury and chronic kidney disease are closely linked and likely promote one another¹⁷¹. Underlying chronic kidney disease is now recognised as a clear risk factor for acute kidney injury. The association of phthalates, bisphenol A, polyfluorinated alkyl acids, dioxins and furans, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and polychlorinated biphenyls with cardiorenal function (more specifically albuminuria, glomerular filtration rate, blood pressure and serum uric acid concentration) has been reviewed¹⁷². The authors concluded that although the effects of environmental chemicals on glomerular filtration rate described in the review are unlikely to cause clinically overt adverse effects, prolonged cumulative lifetime exposure might accelerate the rate of deterioration in kidney function and progression to chronic kidney disease.

Acute kidney injury is defined as an abrupt (within 48 hours) reduction in kidney function based on an elevation in serum creatinine level, a reduction in urine output, the need for renal replacement therapy (dialysis), or a combination of these factors.¹⁷³ The term acute kidney injury should replace terms such as acute renal failure and acute renal insufficiency, which previously have been used to describe the same clinical condition.¹⁷⁴ A patient history and physical examination, with an emphasis on assessing the patient's volume status, are crucial for determining the cause of acute kidney injury. The history should identify use of nephrotoxic medications or systemic illnesses that might cause poor renal perfusion or directly impair renal function. Physical examination should assess intravascular volume status and any skin rashes indicative of systemic illness. The initial laboratory evaluation should include urinalysis, complete blood count, and measurement of serum creatinine level and fractional excretion of sodium (FENa). Imaging studies can help rule out obstruction.

Medical records may also provide useful information on renal function, e.g. on acute kidney injury or chronic kidney disease.^{175,176} Furthermore, collecting self-reported information by questionnaires is feasible in surveys. The HBM4EU standard questionnaire includes a question on kidney disease or dysfunction diagnosed by a medical doctor including the time and age of diagnosis (HBM4EU Basic questionnaire for 1st priority substances).

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3.12 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a lung disease characterised by chronic obstruction of lung airflow that interferes with normal breathing and is not fully reversible. The more familiar terms 'chronic bronchitis' and 'emphysema' are no longer used, but are now included within the COPD diagnosis. COPD is not simply a "smoker's cough" but an under-diagnosed, life-threatening lung disease.¹⁷⁷

The etiology of COPD is chronic lung inflammation, caused in most cases by smoking. COPD is diagnosed when an at-risk patient presents with respiratory symptoms and has irreversible airway obstruction indicated by a forced expiratory volume in one second/forced vital capacity ratio of less than 0.7.¹⁷⁸

A COPD diagnosis is confirmed by spirometry, which measures how deeply a person can breathe and how fast air can move into and out of the lungs. The diagnosis should be considered in any patient who has symptoms of cough, sputum production, or dyspnea (difficult or laboured breathing), and/or a history of exposure to risk factors for the disease. Where spirometry is unavailable, the diagnosis of COPD should be made using all available tools. Clinical symptoms and signs, such as abnormal shortness of breath and increased forced expiratory time, can be used to help with the diagnosis. A low peak flow is consistent with COPD, but may not be specific to COPD because it can be caused by other lung diseases or by poor performance during testing. Chronic cough and sputum production often precede the development of airflow limitation by many years, although the symptoms of cough and sputum do not inevitably lead to developing COPD.

The standardised operating protocol for spirometry is provided in part D, Chapter 6 of this report. Alternatively, information about the COPD may be obtained from medical records or through questionnaire items of diagnosed diseases. For HBM4EU, standardised questions on "chronic bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), emphysema" diagnosed by a medical doctor including the time and age of diagnosis are provided in the Basic questionnaire.

Self-reported survey data has been compared to administrative register data. The prevalence from self-report was notably lower than the prevalence from administrative data in a Canadian survey (5.6% vs. 11.1%)¹⁷⁹, whereas a validation study from Italy showed that self-reported survey data resulted in markedly lower prevalence estimates than data from general practitioners¹⁸⁰.

3.13 Asthma

Asthma is usually defined as a chronic airway inflammation, which causes variable airway limitation and can appear at any age. The common asthma symptoms include recurring episodes of respiratory symptoms such as wheezing, breathlessness, chest tightness and coughing varying in intensity and the period of time. Factors such as exercise, smoking, respiratory infections, weather and exposure to allergens or various particles might trigger the fluctuation of symptoms and airway limitation.^{181,182,183} There is evidence that exposure to bisphenol A and phthalates might increase the risk of asthma symptoms and respiratory tract infections throughout childhood.^{184,185,186}

On population level, there are certain factors, such as tobacco smoking, air pollution, occupational exposures, foeto-maternal health and socio-economic factors, which predispose to asthma. These factors should be considered in the prevention of asthma in a population. However, it is often not possible to determine the trigger causing asthma on individual level.¹⁸⁷

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Asthma is not a homogenous disease. There are various demographic, clinical and pathophysiological types of asthma, which are commonly called phenotypes. There are various determinations of asthma phenotypes but the most commonly used one includes allergic, non-allergic and late-onset asthma and asthma with fixed airway limitation and obesity. However, more research is needed on the clinical effect of these phenotypes.

Diagnosis of asthma should be defined according to international criteria (the GINA guideline)¹⁸³ which include various respiratory symptoms and confirmed expiratory airflow limitation, usually measured by spirometry. Additionally, there are various differential diagnoses of asthma, which partly vary by age and country. These diagnoses include for instance vocal cord dysfunction, bronchiectasis, cardiac failure, hyperventilation and COPD, and these should be considered when diagnosing asthma. It should be borne in mind that a subject may also have two or more diagnoses at the same time.

3.13.1 Childhood asthma

Asthma is the most common chronic disease in childhood. Due to the various different phenotypes of childhood asthma, it has been difficult to agree on a clear definition of the condition and instead an operational description is used: 'Asthma is a chronic inflammatory disorder of the airways in which many cells and cellular elements play a role. The chronic inflammation is associated with airway hyperresponsiveness that leads to recurrent episodes of wheezing, breathlessness, chest tightness, and coughing, particularly at night or in the early morning. These episodes are usually associated with widespread, but variable, airflow obstruction within the lung that is often reversible either spontaneously or with treatment.'¹⁸³ However, in children <5 years of age, clinical symptoms of asthma are variable and nonspecific, and a symptoms-only approach that defines various wheezing phenotypes has been recommended.^{188,189,190,191}

Asthma results from an interaction between different environmental and genetic factors. The environmental influences begin during pregnancy: allergic sensitisation has been described before birth, and several studies have demonstrated reduced lung function in newborn infants of smoking mothers compared to those of non-smoking mothers. Smoking increases the risk of both asthma and poorer lung function throughout childhood. Lifestyle changes have been linked to the increased prevalence of asthma, and especially allergic asthma.

Respiratory virus infections are the major cause of acute bronchiolitis in infancy and of acute asthma attacks among older asthmatic children. From 2 years of age and especially during school years, inhalant allergy becomes increasingly important for childhood asthma. Approximately 60% of all school-aged asthmatic children are allergic. The most important allergens vary according to climate, but in all European countries animal dander is among the most frequent allergens in asthma. In a warm and humid climate, house dust mites and moulds are also of major importance, and, depending upon climate, the seasonal allergens (birch, grass and mugwort pollen) play a role. Allergen exposure may cause acute asthma exacerbations, and even in the absence of an exacerbation, may increase airway inflammation and bronchial hyperresponsiveness.¹⁹²

Occupational agents play a minor role during childhood. Kindergartens and schools are the working environment of children, and the need for a healthy indoor environment in such institutions should be emphasised.

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Genetic

Asthma, and one of its major causes, allergy, have strong hereditary traits. A large number of markers with possible relationships to asthma and airway inflammation have already been identified, but these vary between populations. There has also been increased focus upon epigenetics: the finding that environmental influences may cause DNA methylation and histone formation, and thus change and inactivate the influence of specific genes, has given insight into how the environment may interact with genes, and has shown that this interaction may even be transferred from mother to child.^{193,194}

3.13.2 Assessment of asthma

There is no widely applicable diagnostic test for asthma, and assessment of its frequency and determinants is based on responses to questionnaires, simple tests such as spirometry, and the outcome of medical care such as hospital attendances and drug prescriptions.¹⁸³

The ISAAC (the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood¹⁹⁵) questionnaire is widely used among children and has been validated in several countries.^{196,197} Questionnaires for different age groups have been developed in ISAAC. For adults, the questionnaires include the Medical Research Council Questionnaire (MRCQ, UK)¹⁹⁸, the European Community Respiratory Health Survey (ECRHS) questionnaire^{199,200}, the International Union Against Tuberculosis and Lung Disease (IUATLD) questionnaire^{201,202}, the American Thoracic Society (ATS) ATS-DLD-78 questionnaire²⁰³ and the questionnaire on respiratory health and disease of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES)²⁰⁴.

Spirometry measures ventilation objectively. More information and a detailed protocol for performing spirometry are included in this report in Part D, Chapter 6.

3.14 Skin irritations and inflammations

Several methods are used for assessing skin for different types of irritations and inflammations. Many chemicals may cause skin irritation and inflammation such as contact dermatitis.²⁰⁵

Examination for dermatitis. The examination involves inspection of the skin: 1) around the eyes, 2) around the sides and front of the neck, 3) in front of the elbows, 4) behind the knees, and 5) in front of the ankles. The presence or absence of signs of visible dermatitis is recorded for each of the five areas. A training package of high-quality clinical photographs and instructions for fieldworkers has been developed. This package also included a test set of pictures for central evaluation of fieldworker quality.²⁰⁶

Skin-prick testing for atopy. Briefly, a drop of each allergen extract and the positive (10 mg-mL⁻¹ histamine) and negative (diluent) control are placed on to the skin of the volar side of the left forearm and pierced vertically using 1-mm lancets. After 15 minutes, the outer contour of the weal reaction is outlined using a fine felt-tip pen, and the result expressed as the mean of the lengths of the longest diameter and the perpendicular line through its centre.

Atopic Dermatitis. The Hywel William's Criteria can be used as screening instrument for atopic dermatitis.²⁰⁶

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SCORAD (SCORing Atopic Dermatitis) is a scoring index and a clinical tool to determine the severity of atopic dermatitis and has been published by the European Task Force on Atopic Dermatitis.^{207,208}

SCORAD consists of the following parts:

- A. the extent of the disorder (according to the rule of nines; 20% of the score),
- B. the intensity composed of six items (erythema, oedema/papules, oozing/crust formation, excoriation lichenification and dryness; 60% of the score; each item has four grades: 0 absence, 1 mild, 2 moderate, 3 severe; maximum score 18) and
- C. subjective symptoms (itch, sleeplessness; 20% of the score).

The SCORAD homepage offers the calculation of the score: <http://adserver.sante.univ-nantes.fr/Compute.html>.

The SCORAD has been criticised because it is quite complicated to use and combines objective and subjective data.²⁰⁹ Eczema grading according to SCORAD and objective SCORAD are shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Eczema grading according to the SCORAD and Objective SCORAD²⁰⁹

Eczema grading	SCORAD	Objective SCORAD
Mild	<25	<15
Moderate	25–50	15–40
Severe	>50	>40

3.15 Osteoporosis

For diagnoses of osteoporosis, bone density is measured. Bone density (bone mineral density, BMD) estimates will be obtained with the use of **x-ray bone densitometers (DEXA)**, scanners that use x-rays of two different energy levels to image and measure bone mineral content and bone density.²¹⁰ The bone area to be scanned, the proximal femur, is placed under the scanner arm and positioned with a narrow beam of laser radiation. The x-ray source and detector are scanned across the bone and information from the detector is stored and calculated by the computer unit. The soft tissues contained within the area of the scan are subtracted from the scan and only the bones are imaged and measured. Because soft tissue does not have a substantial effect on the bone mineral density calculations, the results are accurate for most sizes of sample persons. However, a measure of body thickness will be taken at the greater trochanter of sample persons to permit more accurate calculation of bone density. A scan of the proximal femur (hip) will be obtained on adults over the age of 20 years. The sample person will be positioned carefully and asked to hold the limb as motionless as possible while the scan is performed. Scans of the hip require about 10 minutes.

DEXA is the current standard method to determine BMD. However, DEXA devices are quite expensive and usually hospital-based facilities are needed. Thus, for research purposes, also less expensive and simpler methods are needed to assess BMD. **Quantitative ultrasound (QUS)** is a bone health assessment technique which is lower in cost and easier to carry out compared to DEXA.²¹¹ Fracture prediction by calcaneal QUS has shown to be equal compared to DEXA in several studies.²¹² Furthermore, in a recent study among 221 older women, the correlation between the methods was shown to be quite high; Pearson's correlations coefficient between calcaneal QUS and DXA (total hip BMD) was 0.63.²¹³

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4 Conclusions

The current work describes a wide range of health conditions which are associated with environmental chemicals, primarily with the 1st and 2nd priority chemicals identified for the HBM4EU. The methods that can be used to gather information on these health conditions or their indicators vary considerably and include self-reported data (self-administered questionnaires or interviews), measurement data, laboratory analysis and medical records or health register data such as patient records and hospitalisations. The validity of data varies between the methods and conditions. The validity of each method should always be considered along with the feasibility and the costs when choosing study methods to be used in an HBM or health study.

Standardised questionnaires and operating procedures (SOPs) are needed to yield data that will be comparable across the countries and overtime within countries. For some measurements, such as height and weight, there is only one possible outcome and methods of data collection or measurement are straight-forward and common SOP's can be prepared. However, for some health conditions, a series of different methods are available depending level of information to be measured. For example for neurological development one can be interested about verbal development or attention level. These will require different measurement protocols and some of the measurements are country and culture specific. Therefore, providing only one protocol is more challenging. It is not always possible to give conclusive recommendations of the preferable method.

SOPs for many relevant health measurements among adults are available in the EHES Manual.²¹⁴ The next chapter complements the SOP's from the EHES Manual with SOP's for assessing some of the health outcomes identified as relevant in relation to the priority substances in HBM4EU.

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Part D. SOPs for selected health measurements

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2 Background

For comparison between different studies within country and between countries, it is essential that collected data is comparable and harmonised. For objective health measurements, harmonisation should be done already during the fieldwork when measurements are conducted as several details of the measurement procedure as well as used devices may affect the outcome and these cannot be fixed during the post-harmonisation.

For many objective health measurements related to the measurements presented in the previous part of this document, several standardised protocols from different research studies, national surveys and international organisations are available. During the preparation of the following standardised operating procedures (SOPs) for a group of relevant health measurements for the HBM4EU priority substances, we reviewed existing protocols for their commonalities and differences, and based on these reviews proposed a SOP to be used in European HBM studies.

The current SOPs are prepared for measurements for which we had expertise available among task partners and for which European Health Examination Survey (EHES)²¹⁵ had not available SOPs. Work on additional SOPs will continue in coming years and an updated version will be included in Deliverable 11.4 due on M52 (April 2021).

The EHES Manual has SOPs for anthropometric measurements of height, weight, and waist and hip circumference for adults, blood pressure measurement for adults, handgrip and timed chair raise tests for adults, guidelines for blood sample collection when cholesterol and glucose are measured and guidelines for urine (spot and 24 hour) sample collection when dietary biomarkers such as sodium are measured.

This document has SOPs for anthropometric measurements of height and weight for children and adolescents, blood pressure measurement for children and adolescents, measurement of puberty development, spirometry for adults and children and electrocardiogram ECG for adults.

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3 Anthropometric measurements for children and adolescents

3.1 General considerations

Height and weight are two important parameters for calculating the body mass index (BMI). BMI is defined as a person's weight in kilograms (kg) divided by the square of the person's height or length in metres (m²)²¹⁶. This indicator can be used for many purposes in medical, public health and research issues.

BMI was initially developed as a risk indicator of disease in adults. The BMI criteria are used to categorise weight into three main classes (underweight, normal or desirable weight, overweight including obesity). Some common conditions related to overweight and obesity include premature death, cardiovascular diseases, high blood pressure, osteoarthritis, some cancers and diabetes. Recent studies also suggest that early-life exposure to chemicals can interfere with the body's natural weight control mechanisms and thereby increase the risk of obesity²¹⁷.

BMI is also recommended for use among children and adolescents. It is used to monitor weight trends and to identify health risks associated with overweight and obesity. BMI can also be used to track trends in underweight, which can be associated with several factors such as poor nutrition and poor eating habits, chronic diseases, and health problems.

During childhood and adolescence the ratio between weight and height varies with sex and age, so the cut-off values that determine the nutritional status of those aged 0–19 years are gender and age specific. Due to the specificities of childhood growth, the definition of overweight and obesity in children depends on the distribution of BMI by gender in a reference population, not on fixed cut-off values of BMI like among adults. CDC and the American Medical Association recommend using the BMI-for-age growth charts to screen overweight and obesity in children aged 2-20 years^{218,219}. For instance, depending on the CDC growth charts, children of the same age and sex are divided into four main categories: underweight (<5th percentile), normal or healthy weight (5th–84.99th percentile), overweight (85th–94.99th percentile) and obese (≥95th percentile). Three other BMI-based classification systems of childhood obesity, the International Obesity Task Force (IOTF), the World Health Organization (WHO) and the French references, have been compared²²⁰. The WHO references yielded higher prevalence of both overweight and obesity than the other two classification systems.

Four targeted age groups of children are involved within the HBM4EU project (WP7/D7.3): 0-2 years old, 3-5 years old, 6-11 years old and 12-19 years old. Therefore, the following SOPs for anthropometric measurements include all children from 0 to 19 years old.

However, in order to fit both to HBM4EU age categories and standard recommendations for anthropometric measurements in children, four main age categories for children were considered for SOP's for height and weight measurements:

- **Infants**, which include children under 2-year-olds;
- **Toddlers**, which include children aged 2 years.
- **Children**, which include children aged 3–11 years; and
- **Adolescents**, which include the age category of 12–19 years.

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In all age categories, SOPs will be basically similar regarding the main steps of the measurement procedures. However, in practice the measurer will have to adapt the equipment and instructions to the age of participant. Toddlers and young children should be closely guided to perform the gestures needed for a proper measurement, and the parent should also take an active part in the procedure. The measurement protocols in adolescents are similar to those applied among adults.

3.2 Height measurement

3.2.1 Rationale

The height measurement is an anthropometric measure which allows knowing the height of an individual at a given moment. Height data are used to produce children's growth charts. Growth charts are useful for tracking trends in children's growth and development over time. Since disturbances in health and nutrition almost always affect growth²²¹, the monitoring of growth contributes to characterising the health and nutritional status of a population of children and to implementing appropriate public health policies. In conjunction with weight measurement, height is used to calculate the BMI, a major indicator of body fatness.

3.2.2 Equipment

The equipment needed for height measurement in children will depend on three parameters:

- 1) the age category of children and thereby the measurement method used,
- 2) the level of importance of measurement tool (mandatory, optional, accessory), and
- 3) the place where the measurement is performed.

There are several brands and models of measuring devices. Accuracy and reliability of the measurement depends on the quality of these devices. The measurement equipment to be used should be under a good quality assurance, easy to calibrate, and well-maintained. For the measurements in a Health Examination Centre (HEC) or in a Mobile Examination Centre (MEC), the measuring device could be a stationary model (clinic use) or a portable model. For measurements at home, the measuring device should be a portable model.

The following equipment (Table 1) should be used when measuring height in children.

Table 1: List of required equipment for the height measurement in children

Equipment	Purpose	Infants: <2 years	Toddlers: 2 years	Children: 3-11 years	Adolescents: 12-19 years
Infantometer	To measure recumbent length	Mandatory	Optional	No	No
Stadiometer	To measure standing height	Optional	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory
Standardised length rods (e.g. 40 – 75 – 100 – 200 cm)	To check calibration of measuring devices	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional

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Equipment	Purpose	Infants: <2 years	Toddlers: 2 years	Children: 3-11 years	Adolescents: 12-19 years
Carpenter's level	To check the placement of measuring devices	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory
Examination couch papers	To overlay infantometer before laying the child	Accessory	Accessory	No	No
Antibacterial wipes	To clean the surface of devices	Accessory	Accessory	Accessory	Accessory
Step stool	To read the measured value	No	No	No	Accessory

3.2.3 Exclusion criteria

Height should be measured from all participants. However, a participant should be excluded from height measurement if he/she:

- is immobile or uses a wheelchair;
- has too stooped posture to obtain a reliable measurement;
- has difficulties in standing straight independently (standing height only);
- is taller than the maximum height of the stadiometer (standing height only);
- wears a headdress that is not compatible with a good height measure and the participant or his/her parent refuses to take it off;
- the participant or his/her parent refuses to collaborate for the measurement.

The reasons for the exclusion must be recorded for each participant.

3.2.4 Setting up a measurement site

If examinations are conducted in MEC or HEC, measurement devices are set up when the measurement clinic is set up.

For infantometer, place the measurement device on a hard and flat surface. Check the horizontal placement of the infantometer using the carpenter's level. Check the accuracy of the infantometer using standardised length rods (at the start of each daily measurement session or when moving a portable infantometer between different sites).

For standing height stadiometer, place the measurement device on the floor, on a hard and flat surface. The stadiometer is used with a fixed vertical height rule on a hard and flat surface with the base at floor level. Check the vertical and horizontal placement of the stadiometer and height rule using the carpenter's level. Check the accuracy of the height rule using standardised length rods and the stadiometer head piece. The accuracy of the measuring device should be checked at the

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start of each daily measurement session or when moving a portable stadiometer between different sites.

3.2.5 Measurement procedures

3.2.5.1 Recumbent length measurement

Infants should be measured lying down (recumbent length). However, if an infant slightly under 2 years old does not wish to lie down and a stadiometer is available, the standing height can optionally be measured and 0.7 cm is added to the measured value to convert it into length.²²² This should be specified in the survey feedback form.

The general technique used for the measurement of recumbent length is the same regardless of the equipment used (fixed or portable). The measurer must first explain the measurement procedure to the parent(s) and how he/she will be involved in the measurement. The measurer should also provide instructions to the parent at each step of the procedure.

The recumbent length measurement procedure in infants and toddlers is the following:

1. Cover the infantometer with an examination couch paper for hygiene and for the baby's comfort. Change the paper for each participant.
2. Ask the parent to remove the participants's shoes and socks and to lay the participant on the examination couch paper on the infantometer, with feet toward the foot piece, and head against the fixed head piece, compressing the hair.
3. Ask the parent to stand on the side of the infantometer when gently placing the participant down, make an eye contact with the child to help to him/her to feel comfortable, and talk to the child throughout the procedure.
4. Position the head of the participant in the Frankfort horizontal plane, i.e. so that an imaginary vertical line from the ear canal to the lower border of the eye socket is perpendicular to the board (see e.g. Figure 1, for a standing height measurement). The participant's eyes should be looking straight up.
5. Ask the parent to support the participant's head while the measurer ensures that the head lies in the Frankfort horizontal plane (as described above) and then to move behind the stadiometer and hold the head in this position.
6. Align the participant's legs by placing one hand gently but with mild pressure over the knees. With the other hand, slide the foot piece to rest firmly at the child's heels. The toes must point directly upward with both soles of the feet flexed perpendicular against the foot piece. To encourage the child to flex the feet, run the tip of your finger down the inside of the foot.
7. Ask the parent to inform you if the participant arches the back or moves out of position.
8. Read the measurement to the nearest tenth of a centimetre (0.1 cm) when the participant is correctly positioned. Release the participant's feet as you hold the foot piece in position. If the participant is extremely agitated and both legs cannot be held in position, measure with one leg in position.
9. Ask the parent to remove the participant from the infantometer and put on his/her socks and shoes.
10. Remove the examination couch paper and slide the foot piece to the end of the measurement column in preparation for the next measurement.

3.2.5.2 Standing height measurement

Standing height measurement for toddlers and children

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Toddlers and children who are able to stand unassisted should be measured vertically (standing height). However, if a child cannot stand and an infantometer is available, the recumbent length may be measured and 0.7 cm is subtracted from the measured value to convert it into height.²²² This should be specified in the survey feedback form.

The general technique used for the height measurement with a stadiometer in toddlers and children is the same regardless of the equipment used (fixed or portable). Because of the participant's young age, the measurer will have to help the participant more carefully in the actions to be performed. The measurer must first explain to the parent and participant what will happen and how they will be involved in the measurement. The measurer should provide instructions to the participant at each step of the procedure.

The standing height measurement procedure for toddlers and children is the following:

1. Clean the surface area of the stadiometer with antibacterial wipes. Check the vertical and horizontal placements of the stadiometer using the carpenter's level. Check the accuracy of the stadiometer using standardised length rods (at the start of each daily measurement session or when moving a portable stadiometer between different sites).
2. Ask the participant to remove his/her shoes and socks, and potential hat or cap, and to step onto the scale.
3. Ensure that the participant does not slip on the base of the stadiometer and that the participant's feet are flat on the base plate (not on tiptoes).
4. Assemble the stadiometer and raise the head plate to allow sufficient room for the participant to stand underneath it.
5. Ask the participant to stand with feet flat on the centre of the base plate, feet together and heel against the rod. The participant's back should be as straight as possible, preferably against the rod, and his/her arms hanging loosely by his/her sides. He/she should be facing forwards.
6. Place the measuring arm just above the participant's head.
7. Move the participant's head so that the Frankfort Plane is in a horizontal position (important for getting accurate measurements). To make sure that the Frankfort Plane is horizontal, use the Frankfort Plane Card to line up the bottom of the eye socket with the flap of skin on the ear. The Frankfort Plane is horizontal when the card is parallel to the stadiometer arm (see Figure 1). Explain what you are doing and ensure that participant does not move his/her head or stand on the tiptoes.
8. Grasp gently the participant's head in your hands, placing the heels of palms on either side of the chin, with your thumbs just in front of the ears, and your fingers going round towards the back of the neck. Ask the participant to breathe in.
9. Firmly but gently, apply upward pressure and lift the participant's head upward towards the stadiometer head plate and thus stretching the participant to their maximum height. Avoid jerky movements, perform the procedure smoothly and take care not tilting the head at an angle (keeping it in the Frankfort Plane). The head plate should touch the skull but not press down too hard.

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10. Still holding the participant's head relieve traction and allow the participant to stand relaxed and breathe out. The participant should be able to step off the stadiometer without ducking their head.
11. Read the measurement to the nearest tenth of a centimetre (0.1 cm).

Figure 1: Illustration of the position of head in horizontal Frankfort plane view during standing height measurement. The Frankfort horizontal plane represents an imaginary line from the ear canal to the lower border of the eye socket, so as to be perpendicular to the vertical board of the stadiometer (Image reproduced with the permission of The Scottish Health Survey's coordination team).

Standing height measurement for adolescents

For adolescents, the measurement protocol will be similar to that applied among adults²²³; as more independent collaboration of the participant is possible. The measurer will provide instructions to the participant at each step of the procedure.

The standing height measurement procedure in adolescents is the following:

1. Clean the surface area of the stadiometer with antibacterial wipes. Check the vertical and horizontal placements of the stadiometer using the carpenter's level. Check the accuracy of the stadiometer using standardised length rods (at the start of each daily measurement session or when moving a portable stadiometer between different sites).
2. Ask the participant to remove his/her shoes, heavy outer garments, hair ornaments and headdresses, where culturally acceptable. A veil does not prevent the measurement when it is thin.
3. Ask the participant to stand with his/her back to the height rule or to the wall.
4. Check that the back of the head of the participant, shoulder blades, buttocks and heels touch or are in line with the stadiometer or the wall.
5. Ask the participant to stand in a natural straight standing position, weight evenly on both feet, arms hanging loosely by body sides, and look straight ahead.

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6. Assist the participant to the proper head position. The head should be positioned so that Frankfort Plane is horizontal (see Figure 1, i.e. the top of the external auditory meatus (ear canal) is in line with the inferior margin of the bony orbit (cheek bone)).
7. Ask the participant to keep eyes focused ahead, breathe in deeply and stretch to full height.
8. Check standing position of the participant (standing straight and in the middle of the stadiometer) and lower the head piece of the stadiometer or the sliding part of the measuring rod so that the hair of the participant is pressed flat.
9. Read the measurement value to the nearest tenth of a centimetre (0.1 cm). If necessary, use step stool to read properly.

3.2.6 Specific issues when the measurement is taken at the participant's home

When the measurement is performed at the participant's home:

- the measurement protocol should be followed as closely as possible and performed with appropriate equipment (e.g. portable stadiometer);
- the position of the device and the participant should be carefully checked;
- the calibration of the measuring device should be checked upon installation and at regular intervals, following a predefined protocol; and
- any deviation from the measurement protocol should be recorded.

3.2.7 Information to be recorded

The following information should be recorded on each participant's recording form (see 3.2.11, Annex 1):

- type and reference number of the device;
- height or length to the nearest millimetre (i.e. the nearest tenth of a centimetre (0.1 cm)) at the resolution of the stadiometer or the infantometer;
- all issues that can affect the measurement results (e.g. hair style, headdress, shoes not removed);
- the method used for the measurement and any deviation from the protocol and reasons for the deviation.

The measurer must record the measurement value immediately after reading it.

3.2.8 Feedback to participant

The height measurement value can be communicated to the participant together with general information about outcomes based on national recommendations.

3.2.9 Safety

- Do not leave infants on their own at any moment during the recumbent length measurement.

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- The measurer must take care that toddlers, children and adolescents do not accidentally knock their heads against the horizontal bar of the stadiometer during the standing height measurement.

3.2.10 Quality assurance

The quality assurance of height measurement includes three main components:

1. The quality of equipment which is regularly checked and calibrated.

Regular maintenance and calibration helps to ensure that height/length measurement devices produce accurate and reliable results when proper measurement techniques are followed. Equipment that shows evidence of damage should not be used and must be replaced. All equipment should be checked regularly. Each check and its outcome are recorded in the log book. Infantometer and stadiometer should be calibrated using standardised length rods, at least once a day. The horizontal and vertical placement of the height rule should be checked daily by using the Carpenter's level. The height of the rule should be checked whenever a new examination site is set up. If height rule is fixed on a hard surface, it should also be checked with standardised rod at regular intervals and corrected if the error is greater than 2 mm. If the portable stadiometer needs to be moved during the day between different measurement sites, the vertical and horizontal placement of the device should be checked at regular intervals, depending on the device used. The results of calibration and the checking should be recorded in the survey log book.

2. The use of a standardised measurement protocol and staff training.

Each measurer should understand the rationale of the standardised measurement and have enough time to practice before field work. He/she must receive supervision and feedback. If the survey is prolonged or when deviations are observed, refreshing sessions about the measurement should be organised, at regular intervals. There should be explicit, detailed guidelines at the survey site for performing the measurement.

3. The audit visits during fieldwork and evaluation of measurement data.

The study coordination should organise control visits during the fieldwork. The control visits can be entrusted to an external provider. The purpose of these control visits is to check the measurement practices in the field and the difficulties or deviations encountered by the measurers, as well as to monitor the quality of data produced. The analysis of all this information should allow improving the practices and thereby the accuracy of the data.

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3.2.11 Annex 1: Recording form for height and weight measurements in children

1. Basic information

Measurer id: |||||
 Participant id: |||||
 Date of the measurement |||||||||
 Examination site | at HEC/MEC
| at home

2. Height measurement

Reference number of the measurement device Infantometer: ||||
 Stadiometer: ||||
 Height (cm) |||
 Reason(s) if measurement was not conducted Hairstyle or bulky headdress
 Immobile or uses a wheelchair
 Unsteady stand
 Height exceeds the upper limit of the measurement device, max (cm):
|||
 Refusal to collaborate to the measurement
 Other, please specify: _____

 Observations by the measurer which can affect the result of the measurement (if relevant) _____

3. Weight measurement

Reference number of the measurement device Digital infant scale: ||||
 Infant beam scale: ||||
 Digital adult scale: ||||
 Adult balanced beam scale: ||||
 Use of the tared weighing method for infants and toddlers Yes
 No
 Weight (kg) For infants and young toddlers:
||||

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For small and young children and adolescents: |_|_|_|_|. |_|_|

Measurement conditions of participant (small and young children, and adolescents)

Fasting Yes. Time since the last meal: |_|_| hours

No

The participant emptied his/her bladder before weighting Yes

No

For pregnant participants

Gestational age in weeks |_|_| weeks

Self-reported weight (kg) before pregnancy |_|_|_|_|. |_|_|

Reason(s) if measurement was not performed Heavy clothing or wet underwear not removed

Immobile or uses a wheelchair

Unsteady stand

Weight exceeds the upper limit of the measurement device, max: |_|_|_|_|. |_|_| kg

Refusal to collaborate in the measurement

Other, please specify: _____

Observations by the measurer which can affect the result of the measurement (if relevant)

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3.3 Weight measurement

3.3.1 Rationale

Weight measurement is an anthropometric indicator which allows measuring how heavy an individual is at a given moment. It can be used as an indicator of the person's nutritional status and general health; and also to assess childhood malnutrition both at individual and population level. The measured weight value is used in conjunction with height to calculate the Body Mass Index (BMI), a major indicator of body fatness.

Weight data are also used to produce children's growth charts. Since disturbances in health and nutrition almost always affect growth²²⁴, monitoring of growth contributes to characterising the health and nutritional status in a population of children and to implementing appropriate public health policies.

3.3.2 Equipment

The equipment needed for weight measurement in children depends on the age of the participant and the place where the measurement is performed. The level of importance of the measurement tool to be used can be classified as mandatory, optional or accessory.

There are several brands and models of measuring devices. The accuracy and reliability of the measure are dependent on the quality of these devices. The measurement equipment should be under a good quality assurance, easy to calibrate, and well-maintained. For the measurements in a HEC or in a MEC, the measuring device could be a stationary clinical use model or a portable model. For measurements at home, the device should be a portable model.

Scales should comply with the most up-to-date EC directives for medical use and calibration. Adult digital scale should also have both a hold and tare facility.

The following equipment (Table 2) should be used when weighing children.

Table 2: List of required equipment for weight measurement in children

Equipment	Purpose	Infants:	Toddlers:	Children:	Adolescents:
		<2 years	2 years old	3-11 years	12-19 years
Digital infant scale or infant beam scale	To weigh infants and toddlers	Mandatory	No	No	No
Digital scale or balanced beam scale (adult models)	To weigh children or adolescents	Optional	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory
Calibration weights (e.g. 3 – 5 – 10 – 20 – 50 – 100 kg)	To calibrate scales	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional
Carpenter's	To check the	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory

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Equipment	Purpose	Infants: <2 years	Toddlers: 2 years old	Children: 3-11 years	Adolescents: 12-19 years
level	placement of measuring devices				
Examination couch papers	To overlay infant scales before laying the child	Accessory	No	No	No
Antibacterial wipes	To clean the surface of devices	Accessory	Accessory	Accessory	Accessory

3.3.3 Exclusion criteria

Weight should be measured for all participants, except if the participant:

- is immobile or uses a wheelchair;
- has severe difficulties in standing steady (toddlers, children and adolescents);
- is heavier than the upper limit of the scale;
- the participant or the parent refuses to collaborate for the measurement.

The reasons for exclusion must be recorded. If an adolescent is pregnant, pregnancy weeks should be recorded, and self-reported weight before pregnancy should be recorded separately from the measured weight. This information should also be recorded on the recording form.

3.3.4 Measurement procedures

3.3.4.1 Weighing infants and toddlers

Infants and toddlers unable to stand still should be weighed using an appropriate infant scale or using the tared weighing with an adult. However, the primary method is direct weighing of the child alone.

Weighing infants and toddlers alone

Infants and toddlers who cannot stand on the scale should be weighed alone using an appropriate scale. The measurer should provide instructions to the parent at each step of the procedure.

The weight measurement protocol of an infant or toddler alone using a digital infant scale is the following:

1. Lay down the scale on a hard and flat surface. Check the horizontal placement of the scale using the carpenter's level (or the built-in level of the scale). Cover the scale with an examination couch paper. Remember to change paper for each participant.
2. Switch on the scale and wait for the start-up procedure to end (until the display reads 0.0). Check the accuracy of the scale using standard weights (at the start of each daily measurement session or after position changes).

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3. Ask the parent to remove the participant's clothing to underwear and to remove the nappy if it is wet. Participants should be weighed with minimal clothing.
4. Ask the parent to gently lay the participant on his/her back or sitting on the tray of the scale.
5. Make sure that the participant is not touching anything but the scale tray. The weight will appear on the display panel.
6. Read and record the weight to the nearest hundredth of a kilogram (0.01 kg). If the weight changes between two values without stopping, record either number.
7. Ask the parent to take off the participant from the scale. Generally, the scale should switch off automatically a few seconds after the participant steps off it.
8. Remove the examination couch paper and prepare the scale for the next participant.

The weight measurement protocol of an infant or toddler alone using an infant beam scale is the following. The measurer should provide instructions to the parent at each step of the procedure.

1. Lay down the scale on a hard and flat surface. Check the horizontal placement of the scale using the carpenter's level. Place both the sliding beam weights directly over their respective zeroes. Check the accuracy of the scale using standard weights (at the start of each daily measurement session or after position changes).
2. Loosen the screw on the adjustable zeroing weight or counter weight. Move it until the beam balances, then tighten the screw on the counter-weight.
3. Ask the parent to remove the participant's clothing to undergarments and to remove the nappy if it is wet. Participants should be weighed with minimal clothing.
4. Ask the parent to gently lay the participant on his/her back or sitting on the tray of the scale.
5. Make sure the participant is positioned at the centre of the platform and his/her arms are along his/her side.
6. Move the large counterweight until you find the first notch where the beam falls, then move the weight back one notch.
7. Slowly push the small counterweight across the beam until it is balanced. You may need to move it back and forth in small increments several times to reach balance.
8. Read and record the measured weight to the nearest hundredth of a kilogram (0.01 kg).
9. Ask the parent to take the participant off from the scale.
10. Return counter weights to their zero position in preparation for the next measurement.

Tared weighing

Infants and toddlers who cannot lay or sit still enough on the scale may also be weighed with the assistance of an adult. The measurer should provide instructions to the parent at each step of the procedure.

The weight measurement of infants and toddlers using tared weighing procedure is the following:

1. Explain the procedure to the adult. Lay down the scale on a hard and flat surface. Check the horizontal placement of the scale using the carpenter's level (or the built-in level of the scale). Switch on the scale and wait that display reads 0.0 (if using digital scale). Check the

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accuracy of the scale using standard weights (at the start of each daily measurement session or after the scale has been relocated).

2. Ask the parent to remove the participant's clothing to underwear. Change the nappy if it is wet. Participants should be weighed with minimal clothing. While waiting to be weighed, ensure that the participant does not get cold, for example by wrapping in a blanket until weighing. Have someone else hold the undressed baby wrapped in a blanket.
3. Ask the parent to stand in the middle of the scale, feet slightly apart, and to remain still. Weigh the adult as normal following the adult weighing protocol adapted to the type of scale used.
4. A. Using an adult digital scale: With the parent still on the scale and his/her weight displayed, tare the scale using tare function/button. Scale display returns to "zero". Then weigh the adult and participant together.
B. Using an adult balanced beam scale: Weigh the parent alone, and then weigh the parent with the participant. The difference between the two measures will be used to determine the weight of the participant.
5. Read and record the measured weight to the nearest hundredth of a kilogram (0.01 kg).

3.3.4.2 Weighing toddlers, children and adolescents

Toddlers able to stand still, children and adolescents should be weighed alone, following a procedure similar to the measurement protocol for adults²²⁵. Whenever possible, the weight measurement should be carried out after the participant has emptied his/her bladder.

The main steps of the measuring procedure of weight measurement in toddlers, children and adolescents using an adult digital scale are described below. The measurer should provide instructions to the participant at each step of the procedure.

1. Lay down the scale on a hard and flat surface. Check the horizontal placement of the scale using the carpenter's level (or the built-in level of the scale). Wipe the footplate surface of the scales with an antibacterial wipe and allow drying.
2. Ask the participant to remove his/her shoes, heavy outer garments and heavy accessories and jewellery. The measurement should be done on as little clothing as possible, ideally on underwear. If the participant refuses to undress to his/her underwear or feels uncomfortable undressing, record the clothing worn during the measurement.
3. Switch on the scale and wait for the start-up procedure to end (until the display reads 0.0). Check the accuracy of the scale using standard weights (at the start of each daily measurement session or after the scale has been relocated).
4. Ask the participant to stand on the scale with feet together in the centre and heels against the back edge of the scale, the arms hanging loosely at the sides and the head facing forward.
5. Encourage the participant to 'be as still as a statue' for an accurate reading. Ensure that the participant keeps looking ahead and not looking down at weight reading. Read the value when it has stabilised.
6. Read and record weight to the nearest tenth of a kilogram (0.1 kg) before the participant steps off the scale.

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7. Ask the participant to step off the scale. The scale should switch off automatically a few seconds after the participant steps off it.

The main steps of the measuring procedure of weight measurement in toddlers, children and adolescents using an adult balanced beam scale are described below. The measurer should provide instructions to the participant at each step of the procedure.

1. Lay down the scale on a hard and flat surface. Check the horizontal placement of the scale using the carpenter's level. Place both sliding beam weights directly over their respective zeroes.
2. Loosen the screw on the adjustable zeroing weight or counter weight. Move it until the beam balances, then tighten the screw on the counter-weight.
3. Ask the participant to remove shoes and any heavy clothing such as jackets, sweatshirts, sweaters.
4. Ask the participant to step onto the scale.
5. Make sure the participant is positioned at the centre of the platform and his/her arms are along his/her side.
6. Move the large counterweight until you find the first notch where the beam falls, then move the weight back one notch.
7. Slowly push the small counterweight across the beam until it is balanced. You may need to move it back and forth in small increments several times to reach balance.
8. Read and record the weight to the nearest tenth of a kilogram (0.1 kg) before the participant steps off the scale.
9. Ask the participant to step off the scale.
10. Return the weights on the beam to zero in preparation for the next measurement.

3.3.5 Specific issues when the measurement is taken at the participant's home

When the measurement is performed at the participant's home:

- the same protocol should be followed as in an examination centre;
- a portable scale should be used;
- the position of the device and the participant should be carefully checked;
- the calibration should be checked upon installation of the measuring device and at regular intervals, following a predefined protocol;
- any deviation from the protocol measurement must be recorded.

3.3.6 Information to be recorded

The following information should be recorded on each participant's recording form (see Annex 1 in Part D, section 3.2.11):

- type and reference number of the device;

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- the weight read at the stabilisation of the scale to the nearest hundredth of a kilogram (0.01 kg) (i.e. with 10 g precision) for infants and to the nearest tenth of a kilogram (0.1 kg) (i.e. with 100 g precision) for toddlers, children and adolescents;
- all issues that can affect the measurement results (pregnancy, bulky clothing etc.);
- the method used for the measurement, any deviation from the protocol and the reason for the deviation.

Record measurement value immediately after measurement.

3.3.7 Feedback to participant

The height measurement value can be communicated to the participant together with general information about outcomes based on national recommendations.

3.3.8 Safety

Do not leave infants or toddlers on their own at any moment during the weight measurement.

3.3.9 Quality assurance

Quality assurance of weight measurement includes three main components:

1. The quality of equipment which is regularly checked and calibrated.

Regular maintenance and calibration helps to ensure that scale devices produce accurate and reliable measurements when proper measurement techniques are followed. Equipment that shows evidence of damage should not be used and must be replaced. If the scale is operated with batteries, check that there is voltage on the batteries and that spare ones are on hand. All equipment should be checked at predefined regular intervals. Each check and its outcome are recorded in the log book. Measuring devices should be checked daily and when a new examination site is set up. Use the carpenter's level (or the built-in level if the device has one) to check that the scale is placed horizontally. Use calibration weights to check that the scale is accurate when setting up the examination site, following the specific instructions for each device model (see each notice of the manufacturer). Briefly described, gently place calibration weights one by one on the scale, gradually from a lighter to a heavier one (e.g. from 3 kg to 20 kg on an infant scale and from 10 kg to 100 kg on an adult scale). The measurement reading should be exactly the same each time as the known weight of the calibration weight. If the error is greater than 0.02 kg on the infant scale or greater than 0.2 kg on the adult scale, the device should be corrected or changed.

2. The use of a standardised measurement protocol and staff training.

Each measurer should understand the rationale of the standardised measurement and have enough time to practice before field work, and he/she should receive supervision and feedback. If the survey is prolonged or when deviations are observed, refreshing sessions about the measurement should be organised, at regular intervals. There should be explicit, detailed guidelines at the survey site for performing the measurement.

3. The audit visits during fieldwork and evaluation of measurement data.

The study coordination should organise audit visits during the fieldwork. The audit visits can be entrusted to an external provider. If audit visits are conducted by an external provider,

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they have to know the protocol and have a detailed check list to follow during the visit. The purpose of these audit visits is to check the measurement practices in the field and the difficulties or deviations encountered by the measurers, as well as to monitor the quality of data produced. The analysis of all this information should allow improving the practices and thereby the accuracy of the data

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4 Blood pressure for children and adolescents

4.1 Rationale

Both the measurers and the participants should understand the rationale of the blood pressure measurement to motivate them to take part and carry out the measurements following the protocol. The rationale should be explained to the children and adolescents in a way that is suitable considering their age. A simple explanation suitable for parents/guardians and older children is that blood pressure is the pressure exerted by circulating blood upon the walls of blood vessels. The blood pressure varies during the day for each individual. When blood pressure results are presented, two values are given; systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Systolic blood pressure, higher of the two values, represents the pressure while the heart contracts to pump blood to the body and diastolic blood pressure, lower of the two values, represents the pressure when the heart relaxes between beats. For HBM studies among children and adolescents, the recommendation is to perform blood pressure measurement subjects who are at least five years of age. Thus, adjusting the explanation according to the subject's age is appropriate.

Elevated blood pressure is uncommon among children. Risk factors for high blood pressure in children include obesity and a family history of high blood pressure. Furthermore, elevated blood pressure in childhood is considered a risk factor for hypertension in early adulthood. Among children, secondary causes for hypertension are more prevalent than in adults, and the prevalence of essential (primary) hypertension remains unknown. There are various secondary causes of hypertension in childhood, including congenital defects of the kidney, heart, and other organs²²⁶.

Traditionally, the gold standard for blood pressure measurement has been the mercury sphygmomanometers. The Commission Regulation (EC) no 847/2012 has banned the sale of mercury sphygmomanometers from 10 April 2014 onwards in Europe.²²⁷ This, together with the development of oscillometric devices has increased the use of automated oscillometric devices in health surveys. Here, instructions are given assuming that oscillometric device is used in the measurement.

The standardisation of the blood pressure measurement procedure is important to obtain as valid readings as possible. There are many issues that affect the blood pressure levels. The following activities affect the blood pressure level among adults and can be assumed to affect the blood pressure levels of children and adolescents as well: ^{228,229}

- Full bladder²³⁰
- Not resting 3 to 5 minutes before measurement
- Back/feet unsupported²³⁰
- Supine posture instead of sitting posture^{231,232}
- Legs crossed²³³
- Participant talking during the measurement^{230,234}
- Arm below heart level or arm above heart level^{235,236,231}
- Physical exercise
- Left arm instead of right arm²³⁷
- Cuff too small or too large^{235,230}

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- Cuff over clothing²³⁰
- Arm unsupported during the measurement^{235,230}

4.2 Equipment

Measuring blood pressure among children is challenging. The selection of the equipment is critical. For example, blood pressure levels are overestimated with a cuff that is too small and underestimated by a cuff that is too large.

Required devices are:

- An automated blood pressure monitoring device, which has passed the validation based on one of the following protocols: the International protocol of the European Society of Hypertension²³⁸, Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation (AAMI) protocol²³⁹, Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation/European Society of Hypertension/International Organization for Standardization (AAMI/ESH/ISO) Collaboration Statement²⁴⁰ or the British Hypertension Society protocol²⁴¹. A list of validated automated blood pressure measurement devices with reference to the published validation results can be found from the British Hypertension Society web site (<http://www.bhsoc.org/bp-monitors/bp-monitors/>).
- 2-4 cuffs of different sizes depending on the age range of children or adolescents included
- Non-elastic measurement tape
- Thermometer
- Watch (for recording the time of the measurement)

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4.2.1 Selection and validation of the automated (oscillatory) device

When an automated device is used for blood pressure measurement in a survey, special attention has to be paid to the selection of brand and type. The selected device should have passed at least one of the validation protocols listed above.

It is also important to maintain same brand and type of the device in subsequent surveys to ensure comparability of the results between surveys and reliable estimation of time trends.

If previous surveys have been done using mercury sphygmomanometer or other brand/type of automated device, a validation study should be conducted to estimate potential differences.

4.2.2 Selection of cuffs for the survey

A set of 2 or 4 cuffs are needed for the blood pressure measurement depending on the age range of children or adolescents included, to ensure as accurate measurement as possible. The width of the bladder of the cuff should be at least 40% of the arm circumference and the length of the bladder at least 80% of the arm circumference. Each study specific manual should have a table listing which cuffs are used for specific arm circumferences.

Manufacturers have different cuff sizes on the market and especially for the automated devices, often only the device specific cuffs can be used. Therefore, providing specific widths for the bladder of the cuffs is difficult.

It is important that the cuffs are selected for correct arm circumference. This can be calculated as follows:

1. Number selected cuffs as 1 = narrowest cuff, 2 = 2nd narrowest cuff, ...
2. Measure the width of the bladder of cuffs. Let them be CUFF1, CUFF2, ...
3. Calculate the optimal arm circumference (OAC_i) for each cuff as: $OAC_i = CUFF_i / 0.4$
4. Calculate the mid-point of each pair of adjacent cuff sized (MP_{ij}): $MP_{ij} = (OAC_i + OAC_j) / 2$
5. Use the mid-points of cut points for selection of different cuffs.

For example, the cuff sizes could be as presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Example of arm circumference vs. acceptable cuff sizes

Cuff size	Bladder width (cm)	Arm circumference
Child	9	17–21.9
Adult	12	22–29.9
Large adult	15	30–37.9
Adult thigh	18	38–47.9

4.3 Exclusion criteria

Blood pressure should be measured from all children aged 5+ except if the child has

- any problems **on both arms** preventing to place the cuff properly on neither arm, such as:
 - amputation,

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- casts,
- open wounds/sores or severe rash,
- malformations or
- lymph node malfunction.

4.4 Measurement procedures

4.4.1 Setting up the measurement site

The measurement site should be selected so that the room in which the blood pressure is measured is quiet and has a comfortable temperature. The room temperature should be recorded for each participant. If there is any disturbance during the measurement, this should be noted on the recording form.

The measurement device should be placed on the table in front of the measurer so that she/he has a clear view on the device but that the participant cannot see the result from the device.

For the participant, there should be a chair which has a backrest. For the short participants, a support for their feet should be available. The table or armrest of the chair should be on the right hand side of the participant.

4.4.2 Preparation for the measurement

General issues

Each blood pressure measurement device used in the survey should have an individual number. This number should be recorded with each measurement.

Each measurer should have an individual identification, which is recorded with each measurement.

Instructions to the participants

Before coming to the examination, participants should be instructed to abstain from eating, drinking (except water), smoking, and heavy exercise for one hour before the measurement. The participants should also be instructed to empty their bladder, if needed, before the measurement as a full bladder affects blood pressure.

The subject should remove outer garments and all other tight clothing. Sleeves should be rolled up so that the upper arm is bare. The remaining clothing should not be constrictive, and the blood pressure cuff should not be placed over any clothing.

Position of the subject

The participant should be in a sitting position so that the arm and back are supported. The participant's feet should be resting firmly on the floor, not dangling. If the participant's feet do not reach the floor, a platform should be used to support them. If the participant cannot sit and the measurement is taken in supine posture, this should be recorded.

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Position of the arm

The measurements should be taken on the right arm whenever possible. If not possible, e.g. the arm has been amputated or has rashes, adhesive dressing, casts, open sores, hematomas, wounds, arteriovenous shunt or any other intravenous access device, or if axillary lymph nodes have been removed, the left arm should be used. The use of left arm and reason for this should be recorded.

The arm should be resting on the desk so that the antecubital fossa (a triangular cavity of the elbow joint that contains a tendon of the biceps, the medial nerve, and the brachial artery) is at the level of the heart and palm is facing up. To achieve this position, either the chair should be adjusted or the arm on the desk should be raised, e.g. by using a pillow. The participant must always feel relaxed and comfortable.

Selection of the cuff for the participant

The greatest circumference of the upper arm is measured using a non-elastic tape, with the arm relaxed and in the normal blood pressure measurement position. The measurement should be read to the nearest centimetre and recorded.

Select the correct cuff size for the arm circumference and record the size of the selected cuff.

4.4.3 Number of measurements

Three measurements should be taken, one minute apart.

4.5 Measurement protocol

4.5.1 Automated (oscillatory) blood pressure measurement device

The detailed measurement protocol for the automated blood pressure measurement devices is type specific and should be adjusted for the instructions provided by the manufacturer of the specific device. Here is the generic measurement protocol.

1. Ask the child or adolescent to sit still for 5 minutes before starting the measurement. If this is not possible, the child should at least calm down and avoid running and bouncing. If the child is clearly nervous of the measurement, let him/her take a closer view of the measurement device.
2. Explain the measurement procedure to the participant and emphasise that he/she should not move or talk during and between measurements as that will increase the blood pressure.
3. Measure the arm circumference and select correct cuff size.
4. Attach the air tube of the cuff to the air jack of the machine. Check that the cuff is airless.
5. Make sure that the batteries are inserted to the device or that the adapter is on.

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6. Palpate the radial pulse and count the pulse rate for 60 seconds, measured by a stop watch, a digital wrist watch or watch with a second hand.
7. Record 60-second pulse count and whether or not the pulse was regular.
8. Place the cuff on the right arm so that its bottom edge is 2-3 cm above the antecubital fossa. Check that the top edge of the cuff isn't restricted by clothing. Make sure that the tubes from the cuff are not under arm or otherwise tide up.
9. Press the "ON" button: all the symbols on the display will light up in order to check the display. Note: in some models, pressing "ON" will start the measurement. In case you are using such a device, omit steps 9 and 10.
10. All the symbols then disappear and the air release symbol begins to flash.
11. Push the "START" button: the device automatically determines the correct level of inflation pressure.
12. When the target inflation values are reached, the air is automatically released. The value in the display counts downwards.
13. As soon as the monitor detects the pulse, the symbol begins to flash.
14. When the monitor no longer detects the pulse while the cuff pressure is dropping, the systolic and diastolic pressure is displayed.
15. Record the measurement as shown in the display. In case the device gives an error code, record this code. Do not tell the participant his/her blood pressure at this point.
16. After one minute, make the second measurement by repeating steps 11-15. Ask the participant to sit still and not change his/her position during this wait. Note: some automated devices can be programmed to take 2 or 3 measurements automatically with one minute between the measurements. If such a device is used, you don't need to repeat steps 11-15 manually.
17. After another minute, make the third measurement by repeating steps 11-15.

4.6 Special issues when the measurement is taken at home of the participant

If the blood pressure is measured during the home visit, all the same requirements and procedures apply than for the measurements conducted at the specific examination site. Attention should be given to find a quiet place with optimal position for the participant and the measurer. All compromises in the setting and position should be recorded.

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4.7 Information to be recorded

The information which should be recorded for each participant includes the results of the three blood pressure measurements, the measured pulse rate and the cuff size used as well as issues related to the measurement situation such as measurement time and room temperature, activities of the child or adolescent just prior to the measurement and the posture of the child or adolescent during the measurement. If the measurement cannot be conducted, the reason for this shall be recorded. The EHES Manual includes a blood pressure recording form with information to be recorded.²⁴²

4.8 Feedback to participants

The participant should be informed about his/her blood pressure levels (at least the lowest values of the repeated measurements) and if their blood pressure needs to be controlled. The participant should receive a copy of his/her recordings with written instructions, when needed. There may be national differences on how this feedback needs to be provided; directly to the participant or to his/her parent/guardian at the survey site or by the person's general practitioner. The European Society of Hypertension guidelines for management of high blood pressure in children and adolescents include reference values for normotension, high-normal values and hypertension²⁴³.

4.9 Quality assurance

Quality assurance of blood pressure measurements includes the following components:

- Training of the personnel;
- Checking the equipment and regular calibration of the devices;
- Audit visits and evaluation of the measurement data during the field work.

4.9.1 Training of the measurers

Training of the blood pressure measurers should include:

- Theory
 - Why it is important to measure blood pressure in this survey.
 - Why blood pressure measurement has to be standardised.
 - What are the implications of the changes in the procedure to the blood pressure levels.
- Practical training ideally with people with different blood pressure levels, and in the presence of a supervisor who gives feedback.

4.9.2 Checking the equipment and regular calibration of the devices

All equipment needs to be checked regularly. Each check and its outcome are recorded to the log book. If any problems are observed during the checks, the device in question is replaced and also this is recorded to the log book.

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Daily checks or when new examination place is set up

Every day, before starting the examinations, or when the examination site is set up in new place, the following issues from the equipment are checked:

- Make sure that the AC adapter cord of the device unit (i.e. the power source cord) is securely plugged in or in case the device is operated by batteries that batteries have power.
- Check the air tube for cracks, and confirm that the tube is securely attached to the device.

Weekly checks or when a new examination site is set up

Every week or whenever the examination site is set up in new place, check that the cuff material is clean and intact.

4.9.3 Quality control by coordinating office during the fieldwork

Quality control during the fieldwork includes actions to be carried out in the field by measurers regularly and keeping the log book of the regular checks as well as actions conducted by the coordinating office.

The coordinating office/fieldwork coordinators/supervisors should carry out audit visits to the fieldwork site to monitor the measurements, and/or use an external auditor. In addition to the monitoring of the measurement practice, the coordinating office should monitor the quality of the measurements by checking the data. In regular intervals, which depend on the number of measurements conducted daily, the following should be checked from the data:

1. For each device, the mean and standard deviation of the systolic and diastolic blood pressure measurements should be checked, to determine if a device produces systematically lower or higher readings than the average.
2. For each measurer, the proportion of identical measurements for same participants (systolic and diastolic separately), to determine if the measurers are really doing all 3 measurements for each subject.
3. The mean and standard deviation of the systolic and diastolic blood pressure measurement should be checked, to determine if the measurers are producing readings that are systematically lower or higher than the team average. Measurer effect is also possible with automated devices: the nurses can e.g. have differences in how they make the subjects feel relaxed and comfortable.

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5 Puberty

5.1 Rationale

Puberty reflects the transition from childhood to adolescence and is associated to the development of secondary sexual characteristics, accelerated growth, behavioural changes, and the ability to reproduce. Pubertal development is initiated hormonally by hypothalamic secretion of gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) that stimulates the secretion of gonadotropins from the pituitary, which in turn stimulates the production of sex steroids from the gonads. Pubertal development is a continuous process, which constitutes a combination of several physical changes. Three notable characteristics reflect puberty in girls, namely breast development, pubic hair development and the first occurrence of menstruation. In boys, puberty characteristics include voice break, increase in testicular volume, as well as genital and pubic hair development (see also Part C, Chapter 3.3 in this document).

There are major differences in age at pubertal onset. It varies between genders and from individual to individual and is influenced by factors like ethnicity, genetics and environmental factors. Because of the significant variation in pubertal onset and progression between individuals, chronological age is not an accurate proxy for the pubertal development of a child or adolescents.

It may therefore be relevant to include an evaluation of a child's or adolescents' pubertal development in a health examination and/or Human Biomonitoring study of children and adolescents for several reasons. Firstly, pubertal milestones and the age they have been achieved are relevant clinical biomarkers of effects on the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal hormone axis when examining for factors (e.g. environmental chemicals) that may affect reproduction. Secondly, the stage of the sexual maturation of an individual may be an important confounder as it has an impact on several clinical and biochemical parameters that may be used as biomarkers of effect. Pubertal development may also have an impact on biomarkers of exposure as the metabolism of endogenous and exogenous chemicals often are different in pre-pubertal children compared to sexually matured individuals. Sexual maturation is also associated with changes in behaviour and lifestyle, which subsequently may have an impact on exposure patterns.

5.2 Evaluation of puberty

Puberty development is a gradual process, which is described by a set of rating scales that describes the consecutive pubertal changes in boys and girls, respectively, as introduced by Marshall and Tanner^{244,245}, the so-called Tanner staging. In girls, a scale for breast development (stage B1 to B5) and a scale for pubic hair development (stage PH1 to PH5) is used whereas in boys a scale for male genitalia development (stage G1 to G5) and pubic hair development (stage PH1 to PH5) is used. The Tanner stages describe the pubertal stages and are accompanied by visual standards for each stage. In addition to the Tanner stages in boys, testicular volume is usually measured, and a volume >3 mL estimated by Prader's orchidometer is generally accepted as a marker of pubertal onset with testicular secretion of testosterone.

Optimally, evaluation of pubertal onset and progression in children should be performed by a trained physician or nurse by visual inspection and palpation. Despite physical examinations being considered the most accurate method of determining the pubertal stage, the use of these examinations is debated, especially in clinical studies and epidemiologic studies.²⁴⁶ The children or parents may be uncomfortable with the physical examination and inclusion of it could have a

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negative impact on the participation rate. Furthermore, individual assessment of puberty is time consuming, logistically challenging and thus expensive. In some settings physical examination can furthermore be challenging for cultural reasons. For these reasons, self-assessment of puberty has been suggested as an alternative to the physical examinations. In self-assessment of pubertal staging either the child or the parent(s) are asked to rank the development of the child according to graphics and text describing the different stages on the pubertal development scales. Self-assessments will not be as precise as an assessment performed by physical examination and palpation by a trained person. Some studies have observed reasonable agreement between self-assessment and examination by physician.^{247,248} However, a recently conducted study including approximately 900 children concluded that pubertal assessment by child or parent in general is not a reliable measure of exact pubertal staging.²⁴⁶ Because it was easier for the children to assess whether there were any signs of puberty or not, than to evaluate the exact pubertal staging it was furthermore concluded that for large epidemiologic studies self-assessment can be sufficiently used in the simple distinction between pre-puberty and puberty. Thus, the choice of method for assessing puberty either by performing physical examinations or using self-assessment must depend on the specific aim of the study as well as a matter of prioritisation when preparing the study protocol.

5.3 Protocol for pubertal staging

The scales generally used worldwide for pubertal staging are based on the original publications of Marshall and Tanner from 1969-70^{244,245} In practice today, the visual presentation of the different stages is often presented as drawings. Examples of description of the pubertal stages scales are published in the original publication of Marshall and Tanner, and in a more recent publication²⁴⁶ and can also be found online.^{249,250}

5.3.1 Physical assessment

5.3.1.1 Equipment

Besides Tanner's stage drawings which are available online, no specific equipment is needed for the assessment of puberty development in girls. For measurement of testicular size in boys a Prader orchidometer is needed.

5.3.1.2 Setting up measurement site

A location for the physical examination should be set up so that the privacy of the participant is ensured. Thus, as a minimum a separate secluded room where the examination can take place is needed. Optimally, a private changing room, where the participant can undress and safely store their belongings during the examination, should be available in direct connection to the examination room.

5.3.1.3 Exclusion criteria

- Being in treatment with sex steroids or sex steroid analogs or being in gonadotropin suppression treatment (e.g. for puberty disturbances or transgender treatment);
- known sex chromosome aberrations or other disorders of sex development caused by genomic factors;
- the child or his/her parent refuses to collaborate for the measurement.

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5.3.1.4 Measurement procedure

Girls

Position: The examination should be performed with the participant standing upright and assessed according to the methods of Marshall and Tanner accompanied by visual standards for each pubertal stage.

Breast stage: Breast development is evaluated by palpation to distinguish between fat pads and true breast tissue development. Puberty stage for breast development should be recorded as a value from B1 to B5, where B1 is the prepubertal stage.

Pubic hair development is evaluated by visual inspection. The puberty stage for, respectively, breast development and pubic hair is determined by comparing the observed development with a graphic description of the Tanner stages. Puberty stage for pubic hair development should be recorded as a value from PH1 - PH5, where PH1 is the prepubertal stage with no sexual hair.

There is a normal variation in whether the first signs of puberty in girls are beginning breast development or beginning pubic hair development. Information on whether the girl has had menarche (start of menstrual bleeding) should be obtained and recorded at the examination if this information is not obtained from questionnaire. Information on use of oral contraception is often relevant in studies of adolescents and could likewise be obtained during the examination if done discreetly and in confidentiality.

Boys

Position: The individual should be standing upright or lying supine and assessed according to the methods of Marshall and Tanner accompanied by visual standards for each pubertal stage.

Development of the genitalia should be recorded as a value from G1 to G5, where G1 corresponds to the prepubertal stage.

Pubic hair development: Pubic hair development should be recorded as a value from PH1 to PH5, where PH1 is the prepubertal stage with no sexual hair.

Testicular volume: estimated by palpation to the nearest 1 ml using Prader's orchidometer. The size of the left and the right testis should be recorded separately in mL. In case, that the two testes are not equal in size, the measurement based on the largest testis is used. Pubertal onset is defined as a testicular volume more than 3 ml. Alternative methods for testis measurement are available, including blunt calipers, a tape-measure, or straight ruler, or the measurement may be made using ultrasonography.

5.3.1.5 Feedback to the participant

Not needed.

5.3.1.6 Safety issues

Considering the participant as well as the examiner, it is strongly recommended that the examiner should be of the same sex as the participant and if this is not possible another person of the same sex as the participant or one of the parents should be in the same room during the examination.

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5.3.2 Self-assessment of pubertal development

Depending on the age of the study participant self-assessment can be performed by either the parent or the child/adolescents. Examples of protocols for self-assessment can be found on the PhenX toolkit webpage.²⁴⁹

5.3.2.1 Equipment

Sex specific forms for self-assessment of pubertal development are needed. The form should contain graphical presentations and text explaining the characteristics of the different pubertal stages according to Marshall and Tanner and explanations on how to evaluate and record own pubertal stage accordingly. The form should be in the native language of the study participants.

5.3.2.2 Exclusion criteria

- Being in treatment with sex steroids or sex steroid analogs or being in gonadotropin suppression treatment (e.g. for puberty disturbances or transgender treatment);
- known sex chromosome aberrations or other disorders of sex development caused by genomic factors;
- the child or his/her parent refuses to collaborate for the measurement.

5.3.2.3 Procedure and information obtained

Questions related to growth and puberty followed by drawings of Tanner stages are usually used when determining pubertal age.^{246,248,251} Thus in girls, questions related to Tanner stages for pubic hair development (PH1-PH5) and breast development (B1-B5) followed by drawings are included as well as questions related to menarche (first occurrence of menstruation).

Likewise for boys, questions related to Tanner stages for pubic hair development (PH1-PH5) and genital development (G1-G5) followed by drawings are included as well as questions related to voice break and age at first ejaculation.

As the self-estimation of pubertal staging may not be accurate, the information obtained may discretionarily be used to make a simple distinction between prepuberty and puberty.²⁴⁶

5.3.2.4 Feedback to the participant

Not needed.

5.3.2.5 Safety issues

There are no safety issues.

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6 Spirometry

6.1 Rationale

Spirometry measures ventilation objectively; how much and fast air is flowing into the lung and out of the lung. For diagnosing and following up many respiratory diseases in clinical practice spirometry is a crucial diagnostic tool^{252,253}, and according to the results from spirometry, diseases can be classified as causing bronchial obstruction and lung restriction. Multiple factors and diseases, such as smoking, some muscular disorders, uncontrolled asthma and chronic obstructive lung diseases (COPD), affect values measured in spirometry. Of these asthma is the most common chronic disease among children, and asthma and COPD are the most common chronic respiratory diseases among adults^{253,254,255,256} (see also Part C, Chapters 3.12 and 3.13 in this document). Spirometry is the most important diagnostic tool for diagnosing these diseases.

Substances studied in HBM might cause pulmonary diseases and airway obstruction. Objective measurement for lung functions is needed to measure these abnormalities. Spirometry is the most commonly used standard method used for measuring respiratory health, lung functions and their abnormality and trends at population level^{257,258,259}. It is sensitive already for mild and non-symptomatic restrictive and obstructive changes in the respiratory tract.^{252,253,260} For instance, COPD among adults is an underdiagnosed obstructive disease which might cause no or only mild symptoms in the early stage.²⁵⁴ Therefore, to determine the real prevalence of COPD at the population level, spirometry is needed in addition to data from questionnaires (diseases and symptoms) and medications.

The European Respiratory Society (ERS) and the American Thoracic Society (ATS) have published a series of articles about lung function testing in 2005, Global Lung Function Initiative (GLI-2012) reference values for lung functions in 2012 and ATS recommendations for spirometry in 2017^{252,253,260,261,262}, and additionally, ERS a step by step guideline for performing spirometry.²⁶³ This guideline is based on mainly of these articles and guidelines. Additionally, recommendations and experiences from previous health examination surveys are utilised as there are specific requirements when spirometry is performed on field.

This guideline gives a common description for performing spirometry in a HBM or a health examination survey, for subjects aged 6 years and older. However, each survey has its own purpose, perspective, resources and device, and therefore, the coordinators in each survey should design spirometry for each survey. There are some differences in the protocol for children aged 6–11 years. Children aged 12 years and older can normally perform spirometry with the same procedures as adults. When spirometry is performed among children, it is particularly important to keep the atmosphere as pleasant as possible during measurements and to pay attention to the level of child's understanding and co-operation when educating him/her.

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6.2 Protocol

6.2.1 Equipment

Selection of the spirometry device in a health examination survey should occur according to the requirements of each study. Specific requirements for a spirometry device in a health examination survey occur such as that the device should be reliable, simple to use, fast, strong, light, and in common use.

Multiple manufacturers have spirometry devices, which all have their own instructions for use. An example of a spirometry device is given in Figure 2. Manufacturers have responsibility to produce spirometry devices which satisfy the ERS/ATS 2005 recommendations. If not, the manufacturers should identify which requirements have not been met. However, the user is responsible for ensuring that the device satisfies these recommendations and that the measurements remain accurate²⁵³.

The use of a computer driven flow-volume spirometry device is recommended.

Figure 2: Spirometry device

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6.2.2 Setting up measurement site

A peaceful, comfortable and safe measurement site is important, especially for children. The room should for instance have toys for children to make them feel as comfortable and relaxed as possible. The measurement points should at least be divided with curtains and each measurement point should have chairs for the subject, the technician and the parent in the case of a child, space for spirometry device, enough plugs and other required articles.

6.2.3 Exclusion criteria

The common exclusion criteria are given below, and should be interpreted according to the subject's sex and age. Measurement is not conducted in following cases^{258,261,264}

- Pregnancy
- Myocardial infarction (heart attack) less than three months ago
- Abdominal or chest surgery less than three months ago

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- Retina or eye surgery less than three months ago
- Current painful ear infection
- History of aneurysm or collapsed lung
- History of coughing up blood in one month
- Admittance to a hospital for heart complaint less than one month ago
- Resting pulse rate over 120 beats/minute (after sitting for at least 5 minutes before the pulse rate was taken)
- Person or family member has tuberculosis exposure or person is currently taking medications for treating tuberculosis
- Person does not understand the instructions due to dementia or some other cognitive problem
- The person refuses (or the parent in the case of children)
- The nurse notices that continuing spirometry is unsafe for any reason
- Performing spirometry for an immunocompromised and contagiously infected patient should be considered case by case.

Most of the children aged 6 and older can follow instructions and perform spirometry adequately²⁵⁶. However, if the co-operation of the child is insufficient, spirometry should not be performed.

Reason for the exclusion should be recorded.

6.2.4 Measurement procedures

General information

The most important reliability criterion for spirometry is to follow the acceptability and reproducibility criteria for spirometry curves (see 6.2.6). If spirometry is not performed according to beforehand agreed criteria and, for instance, curves with poor quality are accepted, the data is useless. Spirometry protocol is nowadays quite complex and computer programs have an important role in the spirometry procedure. Therefore, the importance of following the manufacturer's instructions for the specific device and high quality education and training for technicians and, also, for medical directors responsible for pulmonary function testing, cannot be excessively highlighted.^{258,261}

To avoid infection transmission, common hygienic norms and manufacturer's recommendations should be followed. Such norms include for instance washing hands between each subject, cleaning contaminated surfaces, using a clean mouthpiece for each child and using disposable inline filters if possible.

Preparing spirometry device, general information

Follow the manufacturer's instructions on how to use and maintain the spirometry device before, during and after the study. The same device type should be used for all subjects in the same study, and if possible the same device for the same subject.

Preparing to spirometry by the subject before the study

In a HBM and health examination survey, spirometry is performed with subject's normal medication.^{252,260,261} This kind of spirometry presents subject's everyday lung health. However, to keep the results comparable, the study participant (and in the case of children his/her parent) should be informed about the following instructions before arriving to the health examination study for spirometry:

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- No inhaled short acting beta2-agonist (SABA) within 12 hours before spirometry
- No smoking within 1 hour
- No coffee, tea, coke or energy drink within 4 hours
- No large meal within 2 hours
- No alcohol within 4 hours
- No hard physical training within 30 minutes
- No tight clothing that restricts full chest and abdominal expansion

Not following these instructions should be recorded.

Preparing by the subject on the examination day

The following should be defined before performing spirometry:^{252,258,260,261,265}

- height, weight (wearing indoor clothes) and body mass index (BMI, kg/m²)
- sex
- age
- ethnicity (if allowed by national protocol)
- the use of medication for pulmonary diseases.

The following should be explained to the subject before performing spirometry^{253,266}

- The idea of spirometry;
- The purpose of the test: to blow in minimum three acceptable spirometry curves of which two are reproducible;
- What kind of blows will be done;
- To explain and demonstrate how to blow to the device: as hard as possible and as long as possible.

Demonstration of the procedure

The spirometry procedure should be demonstrated personally for each subject (Figure 2)^{253,258,261,266}. Among children, the spirometry procedure should be explained and demonstrated personally for each child simply and in detail with visual feedback. The procedure for performing spirometry should be the same for all subjects participating in the study. For demonstration, a spirette (= mouth piece) which is not connected to the spirometry device can be used.

- The mouth piece should be held with lips (not teeth) so that lips are firmly around the mouth piece and no air can escape;
- The tongue should be depressed so that it does not block the air flow;
- The blowing technique with inspiration and various expirations (full expiration normally, with a fast start and total expiration) should be demonstrated as they will be done while performing spirometry;
- The expiration should last ≥ 6 s among adults;
- The expiration should last ≥ 3 s in children aged 6–9 years and ≥ 6 s in children aged 10 years or over.

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6.2.5 Performing spirometry

The procedure for performing spirometry, including instructions, blowing technique and computer procedure, should be the same for all subjects participating in the study.^{253,258,261,266} The order could be as follows: spirometry, flow-volume loops, bronchodilation agent, 15–30 minutes break and repeating spirometry and flow-volume loops (explained more exactly below).

- The participant should be sitting in a chair with arms and without wheels. Feet should be touching the floor (e.g. the chair should not be too high) with small gap between the legs and back touching the chair.
- Tight clothes should be loosened to allow subject to breath and blow freely.
- Dentures should be left in the mouth unless they are loose.
- The procedure should be demonstrated before performing spirometry (see 6.2.4).
- The mouth piece should be given to the subject, the plastic bag removed and the mouth piece set in mouth.
- The nose clip should be put on.
- The subject should breathe normally through the mouth piece with the nose clip.
- After the subject feels comfortable with breathing through the mouth piece with a nose clip the mouth piece should be removed from the mouth and the spirometry procedure started.
- Tell the subject (according to the computer program's instructions) when and how they should start breathing in and blowing out.
- The common procedure for blowing could be as follows:
 - 1) Breathing in as deeply as possible without any hesitation.
 - 2) Thereafter, putting a spirette into the mouth quickly.
 - 3) Blowing out air as forcefully as possible and keeping breathing out for as long as possible (≥ 3 s in children aged 6–9 years and ≥ 6 s in adults and children aged 10 years or over) without any hesitation.
 - 4) The subject should be encouraged to keep blowing out for as long as they can (keep going, keep going, keep going...).
 - 5) When the subject has finished breathing out, he/she should take another deep breath in.
 - 6) Thereafter, the subject can take the spirette out from his/her mouth.
 - 7) Then the same procedure should be repeated.
 - 8) A minimum break of 30 seconds is taken between the blows.

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Figure 3: Performing spirometry

(Picture Wikipedia, picture reused according to Wikipedias licence to copy picture (licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported); <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:DoingSpirometry.JPG>. Date last accessed 28.11.2018)

6.2.6 Acceptability and reproducibility criteria

Individual curves are acceptable if ^{258,267}

- They are free from artefacts: no cough during the first second of exhalation, no glottis closure that influences the measurement, no early termination or cut-off, no leak, no obstructed mouthpiece, and subject's maximal effort throughout;
- They have good starts;
- They have satisfactory exhalation
 - among adults minimal duration of 6 s or a plateau in the volume–time curve or if the subject cannot or should not continue to exhale
 - among children no change in volume for ≥ 1 s and exhale for ≥ 3 s in children aged 6–9 years and ≥ 6 s in children aged 10 years or over.

The curves are reproducible if

- After three acceptable curves the two largest values of FVC and FEV₁ must be within 0.150 L of each other. The test session may be concluded if both criteria are fulfilled;
- If not, testing should continue until both criteria are fulfilled or a maximum 8 tests have been performed or subject cannot continue;
- Minimum three satisfactory curves should be saved.

6.2.7 Bronchodilation test

Criterion to perform and not to perform a bronchodilation test

Criterion to perform and not to perform a bronchodilation test^{252,253,265} should be defined beforehand when planning a survey and followed during the survey. The criterion for bronchodilation test could be for example:

- 1) To perform a bronchodilation test for all study subjects;
- 2) To perform a bronchodilation test if FEV₁/FVC is below the lower limit of normal (LLN) according to the Global Lung Function Initiative reference values from the year 2012 (GLI-2012, see Chapter 6.2.8);
- 3) Exclusion criterion: subject refuses or does not co-operate in basic spirometry.

The reason for not performing bronchodilation according to defined criterions should be recorded.

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Positive bronchodilation response

A positive bronchodilation response^{253,256} is determined as increase in FEV₁ and/or FVC 12% or higher and 200 mL or higher compared to the control spirometry values. If no significant increase in FEV₁ and/or FVC is measured, an improvement in lung function parameters within the tidal breathing range, such as increased partial flows and decrease of lung hyperinflation, might explain a decrease in dyspnea.

Among children, the pulmonary deposition of bronchodilator (salbutamol aerosol) is generally smaller than in adults. A positive bronchodilator response in children aged 6–11 years is increase in FEV₁ of >12% or higher predicted. In children aged 12 years and older, the criteria are equal to the criteria of adults (as above).

Performing bronchodilation test

- 1) Spacer's (Volumatic, Optichamber, Aerochamber etc.) mouthpiece is firmly and tightly administered in the participant's mouth.
- 2) Technician gives 0.1 mg dose of salbutamol aerosol (Ventoline Evohaler 0.1 mg/dose) into spacer.
- 3) After that and a normal rest exhalation the subject is instructed to steadily fill their lungs with air through chamber and then to hold their breath for 5 seconds.
- 4) The same procedure is repeated 4 times among adults (total dose of salbutamol is 0.4 mg). Among children, the procedure is repeated 2–4 times. The dose of salbutamol is estimated according to the size of the child (total dose being 0.2–0.4 mg).
- 5) The spirometry test should be repeated a minimum of 15 minutes after the administration of salbutamol.
- 6) In the spirometry FEV₁, FVC and FEV₁/FVC values are recorded as before.
- 7) The same spacer type should be used during the whole survey.

Artefacts and possible errors

The acceptability and reproducibility criteria and other instructions presented in this guideline should be followed to avoid artefacts and errors.

Analysing spirometry

The use of computer driven spirometry which automatically analyses spirometry curves is recommended²⁶⁸. Each spirometry curve should be performed according to the criteria determined in this protocol.

Spirometry device measure multiple parameters. When planning a survey, the coordinating team should decide, which spirometry parameters are reported. Many of the measured parameters are sensitive to errors and do not add clinical utility (Table 4 and Figure 4). ATS recommends reporting routinely only FVC, FEV₁, and FEV₁/FVC, and additionally, slow VC and calculation of FEV₁/VC if airflow obstruction is suspected. Also reporting FEV₁/FVC (or FEV₁/VC) as a decimal fraction (not as a percentage of the predicted value) is recommended to minimise misunderstanding.

Table 4: Definition for values measured in spirometry

Abbreviation, Test	Definition
FVC, Forced Vital Capacity	The total volume that is forcible blown out after a full inspiration (in litres)
FEV ₁ , Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second	The total volume that is forcible blown out in one second (in litres during forced blowing)
FEV ₁ %, FEV ₁ /FVC	The ratio of FEV ₁ to FVC
PEF, Peak Expiratory Flow	The speed of air moving out of the lungs at the beginning of the expiration (in litres per second)
FEF (25–75), Forced Expiratory Flow	The average flow of air coming out of the lungs during the middle time of the expiration (in litres per second)
FIF, Forced Inspiratory Flow	The same as FEF but measured during inspiration
FET, Forced Expiratory Time	The length of forced expiration in seconds
V _t , Tidal Volume	The volume of air inspired and expired in the lungs during a normal respiratory cycle

Figure 4: Flow-volume spirometry loop

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6.2.8 Reference values

The multi-ethnic, global reference values, GLI-2012 equations for spirometry were published in 2012.^{260,268,265} GLI-2012 reference values were determined from multi-ethnic spirometry records of 97 759 healthy non-smokers aged 3 to 95 based on the age, sex, and height of subjects, and have therefore been validated also for children. GLI-2012 were determined separately for four ethnic groups (Caucasians, black, South East Asians and North East Asians), while genetic variations in the spirometry results were found in populations in body composition and in the size of the thoracic cavity. The use of GLI-2012 reference values and grading the severity of obstruction and restriction according to GLI-2012 is recommended in international studies and publications to achieve spirometry data which is comparable between countries and studies. The codes and programs for GLI-2012 are available on ERS webpage²⁶⁹.

6.3 Information to be recorded

In minimum three satisfactory curves should be saved but only the 2 best which are reproducible should be analysed. If suspending spirometry, the reason should be recorded and the possibly performed spirometry saved.^{253,258,268,266}

In addition, ambient temperature, barometric pressure and time of the day should be recorded. The quality of spirometry curves should be recorded according to beforehand accepted criteria (excellent, good, bad or corresponding).

All exceptions from spirometry procedure, such as using medications against regulations, concerns about subject's health and reasons for excluding the subject from spirometry should be recorded.

6.4 Feedback to participants

After the measurements, subject (and, in the case of children, the parent) should get a printed copy and oral information about their results. If spirometry is abnormal the subject should get instructions about what to do. If having concern about subject's health after spirometry (pain in chest, difficulties in breathing etc.) instructions about where the subject can search for medical assessment should be given.

6.5 Safety

Performing spirometry is generally safe. However, exclusion criteria (see 6.2.3) should be followed in a HBM and a health examination survey. Any concerns about the subject's safety in regards to blowing spirometry are a reason to interrupt the examination. Interrupting spirometry and the reason for it should be recorded. Additionally, there should be a back-up plan if the technician suspects that the subject is feeling discomfort during measurement. This could be for instance background medical support for consultation^{258,266}.

Spirometry device should qualify the current norms. If there is suspicion of malfunction (broken wire etc.) the device should not be used and replaced with another similar one. If spirometry is not performed this should be recorded.

6.6 Quality assurance

6.6.1 General considerations

To guarantee the quality and reproducibility of spirometry in a survey, a continuing quality control program according to beforehand agreed regulations should be actualised. This includes calibration procedures, test-performance procedures, calculations criteria, reference values source,

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and instructions on situations where the technician observes weird or extremely low values. The instructions on recording spirometry curves and other issues during the measurements should be defined and educated for all persons who are involved in the spirometry examinations. The technician has an important role in controlling quality of spirometry. If any problems occur, the technicians should have medical background support available.^{258,261}

6.6.2 Training for technicians performing spirometry

The most important factor for successfully performed spirometry is a well-motivated, enthusiastic technician. If the participants are children, the technician should have education on working with children. For the encouragement of children, detailed but simple instructions and visual feedback are especially important. Thus, it is very important to pay attention on careful and sufficient education and motivation for technicians. This also guarantees the quality of spirometry in the survey.

The technician should have primary education on health-related sciences, such as nursing, medical assistant, respiratory therapy, including basic background knowledge about lung physiology and pathology.^{258,261,266}

Education should include lectures, written information and practical training on how to perform spirometry and use the computer program in the current study. It should cover understanding on the purpose and basic interpretation of spirometry and device's calibration, quality control and hygienic rules associated with spirometry. The personnel should have a sufficient experience in performing spirometry in practice with the device used the survey before they perform it in the survey. This education and practical training can be organised in specific spirometry training courses or by coordinators in the survey in question.

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6.6.3 Equipment, calibration and other issues

The guideline from the spirometry device's manufacturer about performing spirometry, calibration of the spirometry device, hygienic regulations and other procedures performed routinely daily, weekly, in between subjects and when an error occur should be followed (Table 5).

Each check and its outcome should be recorded in the log book. If any problems are observed during the checks, the device in question should be replaced. This is also recorded in the log book.

Table 5: Equipment quality control, a general summary²⁵³

Test	Interval (minimum)	Action	Others
Volume	Daily/ more often if temperature changes	Calibration check (3 L syringe)	The same humidity and temperature should be maintained at the testing site
Leak	Daily	≥3 cmH ₂ O (0.3 kPa) constant pressure for 1 min	Volume loss >30 mL indicates leak and should be corrected
Volume linearity	Changing the place in survey	1L increment measured with calibration syringe over entire volume range	Check manufacturer's guideline
Flow accuracy	At least daily/ after changing a new flow sensor	3L syringe at least three times	
Flow linearity	Weekly/ when setting up a new examination site	At least 3 different flow ranges	
Time	When setting up a new examination site	Record mechanically with stop watch	

6.6.4 Regular check-ups

Quality control during the fieldwork includes actions to be carried out in the field by measurers and technicians regularly and keeping the log book of the regular checks as well as actions conducted by the coordinating office.

The coordinating office/fieldwork supervisors and/or an external auditor should carry out audit visits to the fieldwork site to monitor the measurements. In addition to the monitoring of the measurement in practice, the coordinating office should monitor the quality of the measurements by checking the recorded data.

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7 Electrocardiogram (ECG)

7.1 Rationale

Cardiovascular diseases are a significant public health problem worldwide causing morbidity and mortality, and ischemic heart disease remains the most important one of them being globally and in Europe the number one cause of death^{270,271} (see also Part C, Chapter 3.8 in this document). The most often performed measurement to examine ischemic heart disease and other heart diseases is electrocardiogram (ECG). In Europe, 300 million ECGs are conducted yearly. ECG is an ideal measurement: cheap, reproducible, safe for the patient, fast and available all around the world.^{272,273,274}

ECG records electrical activity of the heart during the cardiac cycle and reflects differences in transmembrane voltages in myocardial cells during heart's repolarisation and depolarisation.²⁷² ECG is the first choice measurement for a subject with chest pain, dizziness and syncope. It gives up-to-date data about myocardial diseases, such as acute coronary syndrome, arrhythmias and intraventricular conduction disturbances, and, additionally, ECG may reflect anatomic, electrophysiological, metabolic and hemodynamic alterations in body.^{275,273} In health examination surveys, ECG is used for studying pathologies in heart at a population level.^{276,277} Substances studied in HBM might cause cardiac diseases and thereby changes in ECG.

This guideline gives a common description about how to conduct a standard resting ECG with 12-leads in HBM and health examination surveys for adults. The guideline is based on the American Heart Association's (AHA's) recommendations from 1989 to 2009, other previous literature about this topic and data from previous health examination surveys.^{272,276,275,278}

7.2 General information on ECG and measuring ECG

7.2.1 General information on ECG, electrodes and leads

Resting ECG with standard 12-leads measures electrical impulses from various parts of the heart during diastole and systole. Basic information for the values and units measured with ECG is compiled in Table 6 and Figure 5. In practice, ECG device draw complexes according to electronical signals conducted to leads.^{272,277} A standard ECG with 12-leads consists of 3 limb leads (leads I, II and III), 3 augmented limb leads which are paired with the exploring electrode (aVR, aVL and aVF) and 6 precordial leads (V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6)^{274,279,280}

Table 6: Definition and interpretation for values measured in ECG^{278,281,282}

Term	Definition	Normal	Basic interpretation
Heart rate	Number of beats per minute	50–100 beats/ min	Frequency, constant or varying rhythm
P wave	Activation of heart's atriums by electric wave	Duration < 0.12 s	Location, morphology, duration
PQ interval	Conduction of electric wave from atriums to ventricles	Duration ≤ 0.2 s	Duration, regularity
QRS complex	Conduction of electric wave through the ventricles	Duration < 0.12 s	Morphology, duration, axis
T wave	Ventricular repolarisation		Morphology, direction
U wave	A mechano-electric phenomenon which occur after T wave	Low amplitude and frequency	Morphology, direction
ST segment	Early part of the ventricular repolarisation	Constant and at the same level with the ECG baseline	Elevation or depression from the baseline
QT interval,	Time of ventricular activity including depolarisation and repolarisation	QTc: ≤ 460 ms in women and ≤ 450 ms in men	Abnormal interval
QTc interval	Rate corrected QT interval		
Other	Rhythm	Sinus	Regularity, ventricular/atrial; A general overview about ECG's shape and form

Figure 5: A normal ECG complex with some of the above defined terms

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<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:SinusRhythmLabels.svg>. Date last accessed 28.11.2018)

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7.2.2 Placing electrodes

Electrodes are placed as follows (Figures 6 and 7):^{272,274,279}

Limb electrodes:

1. Right arm limb lead (RA, red) – electrode right forearm, proximal to wrist (inside the lower arm).
2. Left arm limb lead (LA, yellow) – electrode left forearm, proximal to wrist (inside the lower arm).
3. Left leg limb lead (LL, green) – electrode left lower leg, proximal to ankle (inner leg, 4–5 cm above the ankle).
4. Right leg limb lead (RL, black) – electrode right lower leg, proximal to ankle (inner leg, 4–5 cm above the ankle).
5. The limb electrodes should be pointed to subject's upper arm and leg.

Figure 6: Places for limb electrodes

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The precordial electrodes (on chest):

1. V1 (red, C1), fourth intercostal space at the right sternal border.
2. V2 (yellow, C2), fourth intercostal space at the left sternal border.
3. V3 (green, C3), midway between V2 and V4.
4. V4 (brown, C4), fifth intercostal space in the midclavicular line.
5. V5 (black, C5), in the horizontal plane of V4 at the anterior axillary line, or if the anterior axillary line is ambiguous, midway between V4 and V6.
6. V6 (purple, C6), in the horizontal plane of V4 at the mid-axillary line.
7. The tabs on precordial electrodes should be pointed to subject's cable yoke.

Figure 7: Places for precordial electrodes

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7.2.3 ECG formatting according to leads

Formatting ECG according to leads (see also Figure 8):

- 1) Lead I: Left and right arm electrodes
- 2) Lead II: Right arm and left leg electrodes
- 3) Lead III: Left arm and left leg electrodes
- 4) aVR: Right arm (+) and other limb electrodes as a common ground (-)
- 5) aVL: Left arm (+) and other limb electrodes as a common ground (-)
- 6) aVF: Left leg (+) and other limb electrodes as a common ground (-)
- 7) V1 -V6: The six chest leads monitor the heart from six progressively different positions on the chest.^{274,279}

Figure 8: Formatting ECG

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7.3 Protocol

7.3.1 Equipment

There are multiple digital devices on market which measure resting 12-lead ECG, and the selection of device should occur according to the requirements of the study in question. An example is presented in Figure 9. Common requirements include that the device should record ECG digitally, process signal electronically and give an automatic diagnostic interpretation after recording ECG. In health examination surveys, the ECG device should be reliable, simple to use, fast, strong, light,

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in common use and filling common standards. The use of the same device type through-out the survey is recommended.^{273,276,275}

The software program which analyses ECGs after the field survey should also be selected before the survey. Generally, it is recommended that the program is reliable and in common use, has an adequate capacity and qualify the common standards²⁷⁶.

Each manufacturer which produces ECG devices and software for analysing data has its own instructions for use. Manufacturers have a responsibility to produce devices and software which satisfy the common standards and recommendations. However, the user is responsible for ensuring that the used device and software satisfy these recommendations before, during and after the survey.^{272,273,276}

Figure 9: ECG Device

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7.3.1.1 Setting up measurement site

ECGs should be performed in a safe, quiet, comfortable and private place if possible, and the subject should be treated with dignity and respect. Subject's personal data should be handled in a confidential and secure way. Possible cultural sensitivities should be respected. The measurement points should at least be divided with curtains and each measurement point should have a bed, space for the ECG device, enough plugs and other required articles.^{272,274}

7.3.2 Exclusion criterion

The ECG should not be performed if the subject is sitting in a wheelchair and cannot move to the examination table by himself/herself or with assistance. There are no other exclusion criteria²⁷⁹.

7.3.3 Measurement procedures

General information^{272,274,277,275,279,283,284}

- 1) It should be checked daily that the equipment and all supplies are available for each subject before performing ECG.
- 2) Technician should clean hands by washing them or by using alcohol gel before, after and in between all subjects.

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- 3) The use of disposable electrodes with adhesive hydrogel is recommended. Electrodes should be stored in a sealable plastic bag.
- 4) Unopened electrode bags should be stored in a cool and dry place.

General information on preparing the ECG device

ECG device should be prepared for the survey according to the manufacturer's guidelines. This includes programming filters and other software according to general regulations and checking these regularly to achieve the desirable sensitivity and specificity.

Common instructions for preparation of an ECG device:

- 1) The speed of paper is normally 25 mm/s and voltage gain calibrated in 10 mm/mV.
- 2) No filter (disturbance elimination) is used routinely in initial recording. If there is evidence of somatic muscle interference the recording should be repeated with filter on. The filter reduces interference but also distorts ECG.
- 3) It should be decided beforehand whether a paper printout is printed for survey, in addition to digitally saved data.
- 4) Paper speed, other used settings and subject's personal data should be written on each digitally saved ECG and paper print.
- 5) ECG device and table for the device should be cleaned when necessary.
- 6) ECG device's parts should be inspected regularly for fraying or other damage and all parts should be attached safely.
- 7) The device should have enough battery charge.

Daily procedures during the survey

1. Check that all necessary equipment and supplies are available for each day and subject;
2. Check that all settings are correct;
3. Check that the examination bed is clean.

Measurement procedure for standard 12-lead ECG

1. Enter the following data on computer before performing ECG:
 - Subject's ID code (and name if defined in study protocol)
 - Age
 - Sex
 - Date and time of study
2. Alteration from the standard places of electrodes
3. Ask the subject to take off shirt, bras and socks. Skin on chest, ankles and wrists should be visible.
4. Ask the subject to lie in supine position on bed with a pillow under the head, arms at the side of the body and legs side by side (not crossed).
5. Place the bed in supine position while position (sitting or 45 degrees upright) might affect ECG's quality.
6. Shave remarkable body hair if located on places where the electrodes should be placed.
7. Clean skin with alcohol and make a gentle abrasion on each location where the electrodes should be placed before attaching electrode (to get a proper touch for the electrodes).

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8. Position limb (four) and chest (six) electrodes according to instructions for standard 12-lead ECG (see Figure 2 and 3 and 7.2.2). Press each electrode gently on the skin to ensure a good adhesion.
9. The limb and chest lead wire connectors should be placed on the banana plugs according to the devices guidelines to the corresponding tabs of electrodes (See 7.2.2 and 7.2.3).
10. Double check that all 10 electrodes and lead wires are located correctly.
11. Check that a continuous ECG curve is visible on computer's screen from each of the 12 leads.
12. Help the subject to feel as relaxed and comfortable as possible while lying on his/her back. If necessary, cover the subject to preserve her/his modesty.
13. Ask him/her to breath regularly and not to talk or move.
14. Check the technical quality of ECG from the computer's screen.
15. When no baseline wandering or movement artefacts are visible on ECG, press record button.
16. Check the ECG's quality. If not satisfying, take a new recording. Check electrodes if necessary.
17. Check again the quality of the recorded ECG and entered data on screen and print. If the quality is low or data not correct or missing (name, date of birth etc.), add missing data and check electrodes if necessary and take a new recording.
18. Save the approved records digitally and print one record for subject and one for the survey (if this belongs to the protocol).
19. Remove the lead wires and electrodes carefully one after another.
20. Clean the bed and examination table for the next study subject.

Special situations in performing ECG

1. If the subject's limb has been amputated place electrode in the amputated stub as distal as possible while conductance in various parts of torso and limbs variate according to composition of the tissue and distance from the heart.
2. If the subject has significant muscular tremor use filter (disturbance elimination function).
3. If a woman has large breasts place electrodes under the breasts on standard places.
4. If a subject is obese or has breast implants this should be reported while these might affect the quality of ECG.
5. If a subject has dextro-cardia (cardiac mal-positioning on right side) make the initial recording with electrodes in standard positions and repeat recording with right-sided chest leads V3R to V6R.
6. Report if ECG is not recorded according to the standards for some reason.

Artefacts and possible errors

Technician should understand the basic technical background about ECG recording, the effect of various factors on the quality and appearance of ECG and various messages about errors from the used ECG device. Some common technical errors are listed below.^{285,286,287}

1. The baseline drift should be corrected while ECG device does not cause this. Common reasons for baseline drift:
 - a. Poor contact between electrode and skin. Suggestion: shave body hair before attaching the electrode. Tape down electrodes if necessary.
 - b. Poor skin preparation. Suggestion: clean skin better and make a better abrasion for the place of each electrode.

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2. Minimise movement.
3. Does the subject have muscle tension or tremor? Is subject cold, tensed or having some muscle or nerve disease? Suggestion: Place limb leads in upper arm and tights if tremor is irritating. Put hands on stomach or under the buttocks. Put a pillow under subject's knee.
4. Does the subject breathe too deep? Does subject have difficulties in breathing, for example asthma attack, hyperventilation or hiccup? Suggestion: Try to help the subject to breathe smoothly.
5. Tension on lead wires.
6. Poor connection between electrode and lean wire.
7. Desiccated electrodes.
8. Wrong placement of electrodes, especially chest electrodes. Suggestion: double check the electrodes routinely.
9. Wrong placement of leads. Suggestion: double check the leads routinely.
10. Interference from nearby electrical equipment. Suggestion: Check beforehand that there is no equipment nearby which could cause interference. Watches, glasses, rings and bracelets do not cause interference.
11. Interference with alternating current.
12. Excess skin paste use.
13. Variation in body habitus, such as marked obesity and chronic lung disease.
14. False settings of device. Suggestion: check the settings routinely, such as the calibration marks and paper speed.
15. Poor quality of ECG noticed afterwards. Suggestion: check the quality of recorded, saved and printed ECG routinely. The survey should have an official quality control program which detects if there is a repeating problem in quality.

Analysing ECG

The device generates an electronic diagnostic interpretation about ECG. However, diagnostics should not be conducted according to these automatic interpretations. The devices are generally regulated to be too sensitive which means that the devices over-diagnose diseases in ECG (not to miss any real pathology). Therefore, ECGs should be analysed afterwards electronically with a special computer program and also by a physician who controls diagnoses. To avoid misinterpretation, pathological findings in ECG should be correlated with the clinical picture and other experimental findings from the survey^{272,273,288}.

7.4 Information to be recorded

ECG with the best technical quality should be saved for further analysis. One paper copy should be given to the subject and another copy printed for survey purpose (if so determined in the study protocol).^{276,279}

There should be a plan for how and where the recorded ECG data is transmitted and saved and where a backup copy is saved after each subject and survey day. Additionally, there should be a backup plan if ECG cannot be saved electronically (for instance, taking a printed copy for each subject). If saving printed ECGs for survey purpose these should be stored in a cool, dry and dark place²⁷².

If ECG is not performed according to given instructions or at all, this and the reason should be recorded. The reasons not to perform ECG could be for example one of the following: subject refuses, there is no time to perform ECG, subject is physically unable to cooperate or does not understand instructions for ECG, equipment does not work, paper has run out etc.²⁷⁹

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7.5 Feedback to participants

One paper copy should be given to the subject. When the ECG is not interpreted as normal, the subject should be asked to take it to his/her general practitioner²⁷⁷.

7.6 Safety

There are no major risks in performing ECG. However, there should be a backup plan if the technician suspects that the subject is having chest pain, sudden arrhythmia or other discomfort or observes in his/her opinion a dangerously pathological ECG. This could be for instance a medical background to consult.

ECG device should qualify the current norms. If there is suspicion of malfunction (broken wire etc.) the device should not be used and replaced with another similar one.

7.7 Quality assurance

7.7.1 General information

To guarantee the quality and reproducibility of ECG in a survey, there should be a continuing quality control program according to beforehand agreed regulations. A coordinating office / fieldwork supervisor should be in charge of quality control, standardisation and technicians' education and support before and during the survey. The common quality control in surveys includes calibration and test-performance procedures and technician's control for the quality of each ECG during and after measurement.^{277,279}

Manufacturer's guidelines about the device's standard hygienic regulations and other procedures performed routinely weekly, daily, in between subjects and when an error occurs should be followed. The device should be checked regularly to ensure that the standards are met and the device should be replaced with another similar one if it is not working in regular tests or in practice as it should. Each check should be recorded in the log book.

7.7.2 Training for technicians performing ECG

The technicians' high-quality education is the most important guarantee for a high quality and reproducible ECG (see Figure 2). The education should cover both theoretical learning and practical training – including sufficiently performed ECGs according to survey protocol with the device used in the survey, working with the ECG device and software used in the survey, learning the quality control and hygienic rules associated with ECG. This education can be organised in specific courses or by coordinators of the survey.^{272,274,279}

In addition to technical expertise, technicians should have a basic clinical knowledge about heart physiology and ECG's background. This includes primary education for health-related sciences, such as nursing or medical assistant. The technicians should have a basic understanding about interpretation of ECG and the device's possible diagnostic suggestions. They should have a list of diagnostic suggestions grading with severity and urgency for possible abnormalities²⁷⁶.

7.7.3 Acceptability and reproducibility criteria

Instructions presented above should be followed. Recording ECG not according to these criteria does not fulfil the acceptability and reproducibility criterion.

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7.7.4 Calibration

The device should be calibrated according to the manufacturer's guidelines. Each check should be recorded in the log book.

7.7.5 Regular check-ups

The importance of qualified education for technicians performing ECGs cannot be highlighted to excess. The technicians should control the quality of each ECG to ensure that it fulfils the quality criteria. They should, for instance, understand how it affects ECG if electrodes are misplaced or leads misconnected. The technicians should perform a regular quality control and keep a log book about the regular checks. Additionally, the coordinating office or fieldwork supervisors should participate in regular quality control during the fieldwork by observing measurements in practice and monitoring recorded data.^{277,279}

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8 Conclusions

This section has provided SOPs for measurement of anthropometric measurements of height and weight in children and adolescents, blood pressure in children and adolescents, puberty development, conducting spirometry in adults and children, and conducting electrocardiogram (ECG) for adults. As can be seen from Table 2 in Part C of this report, the list of health effects associated with the 1st and 2nd priority chemicals relevant for the HBM4EU is wide and these SOPs together with once available through EHES Manual does not cover all of them.

WP11 will continue working on the preparation of additional SOPs for identified health outcomes and also provide more information about validity of different data collection methods, questionnaires vs. objective health measurements vs. health records, where possible.

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Overall conclusions

Human Biomonitoring uses similar methods for data collection as health monitoring in general, i.e. both collect data through surveys. Regardless of the aim of the survey, there are several common elements in planning and organisations. During the planning, the target population has to be defined, sampling frame and scheme decided and actual sample selected. Organisation includes the recruitment of survey participants and in most surveys also administration of questionnaires. Additional to these general issues, HBM and health studies both collect biological samples and do some health measurements such as anthropometric measurements.

Due to these common components, in many occasions it could be possible to combine HBM and health studies into one study using common survey logistics and personnel. This would provide wider aim for the survey but also save money by removing duplication of planning and fieldwork organisation and management.

In Europe, we have many regional or nationally representative health studies which could be used also for HBM studies. It was evaluated what type of obstacles survey organisers would see in combining HBM and health studies. The most common obstacles were related to very sparse financial resources, difficulties in logistics due to large sample size and legislative issues. For potentials following the combination of HBM and health studies, utilisation of existing infrastructure from health surveys, reduced costs, increase in sample size, access to wide range of details on nutrition and health were mentioned.

In addition to the combined HBM and health studies, a possibility to link survey data to administrative health registers such as information on hospitalisations, cancers, and mortality would provide a cost-effective way to collect baseline health profiles, as well as morbidity and mortality follow-up information. Even though many countries have national registers and personal identifiers which could be used for record linkage, in some cases national data protection regulations prevent the record linkage.

We also provided an overview of the potential health effects along with the measurements commonly used to assess them related to the HBM4EU priority chemicals. We also provided some information about available data sources for information on the health outcomes, i.e. survey questionnaires, objective measurements during the survey and use of medical records. For conducting these objective health measurements in future surveys in a standardised way, standardised operating procedures (SOPs) were provided for some of the identified health outcomes.

This deliverable will be updated in coming years as Deliverable D11.4 (due M52). The update will evaluate new health studies and biological samples from health studies which could potentially be combined with HBM studies, and obtain more information about administrative registers in Europe. New detailed standardised operating procedures for recommended health measurements which would be needed for combined HBM and health studies based on research questions relevant for 1st and 2nd priority chemicals will be prepared, excluding those already included in the EHES Manual.

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References

¹ <http://www.ehes.info>

² http://www.ehes.info/national/national_hes_status.htm

³ Deliverable 14.3 Report on available biomarkers of effect of utility in human epidemiological studies for the 1st set of prioritised substances. Available at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-14.3-Report-on-available-biomarkers-of-effect-of-utility-in-human-epidemiological-studies-for-the-1st-set-of-prioritised-substances.pdf>

⁴ Deliverable D 11.1. Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies. Available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-11.1-Report-on-opportunities-and-obstacles-of-combining-HBM-and-health-studies-availability-of-health-studies-with-biological-samples-availability-of-administrative-registers-and-guidelines-for-combining-HBM-and-health-studies.pdf>

⁵ The following countries were included: Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland.

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/United_Nations_geoscheme_for_Europe

⁷ Deliverable D 11.1. Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies. Available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-11.1-Report-on-opportunities-and-obstacles-of-combining-HBM-and-health-studies-availability-of-health-studies-with-biological-samples-availability-of-administrative-registers-and-guidelines-for-combining-HBM-and-health-studies.pdf>

⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_identification_number#Europe

⁹ Roos LL, Wadja A. Record linkage strategies. Part I: Estimating information and evaluating approaches. *Methods of Information in Medicine* 1991;30(2):117-123

¹⁰ Blakely T, Salmond C. Probabilistic record linkage and a method to calculate the positive predictive value. *International Journal of Epidemiology* 2002;31(6):1246-1252

¹¹ United National Economic Commission for Europe. Register-based statistics in the Nordic countries. Review of best practices with focus on population and social statistics. 2007. United National.

¹² Deliverable 4.3. Prioritization strategy and criteria. Available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Deliverable-4.3-Prioritisation-strategy-and-criteria.pdf>

¹³ Deliverable 14.2 - List of effect biomarkers for the first set of prioritized substances, September 2018. Available at: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/upload-work-package/get/file/Additional-Deliverable-14.2-Granada-Workshop-Effect-biomarkers-establishing-exposure-and-health-relationships.pdf>

¹⁴ Zoeller RT, Brown TR, Doan LL et al. Endocrine-disrupting chemicals and public health protection: a statement of principles from the Endocrine Society. *Endocrinology* 2012; 153(9): 4097-4110

¹⁵ Wass JAH, Stewart PM et al. Oxford textbook of endocrinology and diabetes (2nd ed.). 2011. Oxford University Press. DOI: 10.1093/med/9780199235292.001.1

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
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- ¹⁶ Schwartz CL, Christiansen S, Vinggaard AM et al. "Anogenital distance as a toxicological or clinical marker for fetal androgen action and risk for reproductive disorders." *Archives of Toxicology* 2019; 93(2): 253-272.
- ¹⁷ Salazar-Martinez E, Romano-Riquer P et al. Anogenital distance in human male and female newborns: A descriptive, cross-sectional study. *Environmental Health* 2004; 3(1):8.
- ¹⁸ Le Moal J, Sharpe RM, Jvarphirgensen N et al. "Toward a multi-country monitoring system of reproductive health in the context of endocrine disrupting chemical exposure." *Eur J Public Health* 2016; 26(1): 76-83.
- ¹⁹ Thankamony A, Pasterski V, Ong KK, Acerini CL, Hughes IA. Anogenital distance as a marker of androgen exposure in humans. *Andrology*. 2016 Jul;4(4):616-25.
- ²⁰ Hood E. Are EDCs blurring issues of gender? *Environmental Health Perspectives* 2005; 113: A670-A677.
- ²¹ Toppari J, Virtanen HE, Main KM, Skakkebaek NE. Cryptorchidism and hypospadias as a sign of testicular dysgenesis syndrome (TDS): environmental connection. *Birth Defects Res A Clin Mol Teratol*. 2010 Oct;88(10):910-9.
- ²² Hutson JM. A biphasic model for the hormonal control of testicular descent. *Lancet*. 1985;2:419–421.
- ²³ Brucker-Davis F, Pointis G, Chevallier D, Fenichel P. Update on cryptorchidism: endocrine, environmental and therapeutic aspects. *J Endocrinol Invest*. 2003;26(6):575–587.
- ²⁴ Jamalalail YA, Guerra LA, Leonard MP. Selective use of laparoscopy in nonpalpable undescended testes. *Urol Ann*. 2016 Jan-Mar;8(1):81-3.
- ²⁵ Hughes IA, Lim HN, Martin H et al. Developmental aspects of androgen action. *Mol Cell Endocrinol*. 2001 Dec 20;185(1-2):33-41.
- ²⁶ Kalfa N, Paris F, Philibert P et al. Is Hypospadias Associated with Prenatal Exposure to Endocrine Disruptors? A French Collaborative Controlled Study of a Cohort of 300 Consecutive Children Without Genetic Defect. *Eur Urol*. 2015 Dec;68(6):1023-30.
- ²⁷ Nassar N, Abeywardana P, Barker A, Bower C. Parental occupational exposure to potential endocrine disrupting chemicals and risk of hypospadias in infants. *Occup Environ Med*. 2010 Sep;67(9):585-9.
- ²⁸ Keays MA, Dave S. Current hypospadias management: Diagnosis, surgical management, and long-term patient-centred outcomes. *Can Urol Assoc J*. 2017 Jan-Feb;11(1-2Suppl1):S48-S53.
- ²⁹ Rolland, M, Le Moal J, Wagner V et al. "Decline in semen concentration and morphology in a sample of 26,609 men close to general population between 1989 and 2005 in France." *Hum Reprod* 2013; 28(2): 462-470.
- ³⁰ World Health Organization, Department of Reproductive Health and Research (2010). WHO laboratory manual for the examination and processing of human semen. Fifth edition. https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/44261/9789241547789_eng.pdf;jsessionid=05CD7A63ABF70A175AFE715589FABF85?sequence=1
- ³¹ Le Moal J, Rolland M, Gorla S et al. Semen quality trends in French regions are consistent with a global change in environmental exposure. *Reproduction*. 2014 Mar 8;147(4):567-74. Erratum in: *Reproduction*. 2014 Jun;147(6):X3.
- ³² Sakkas D, Alvarez JG. Sperm DNA fragmentation: mechanisms of origin, impact on reproductive outcome, and analysis. *Fertil Steril*. 2010 Mar 1;93(4):1027-36.
- ³³ Pacey AA. Environmental and lifestyle factors associated with sperm DNA damage. *Hum Fertil (Camb)*. 2010 Dec;13(4):189-93.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
Authors: Hanna Tolonen et al.	Page: 142

- ³⁴ Tingen, C, Stanford JB, Dunson DB. "Methodologic and statistical approaches to studying human fertility and environmental exposure." *Environ Health Perspect* 2004; 112(1): 87-93.
- ³⁵ Gnoth C, Godehardt E, Frank-Herrmann P et al. "Definition and prevalence of subfertility and infertility." *Hum Reprod* 2005; 20(5): 1144-1147.
- ³⁶ Caserta D, Mantovani A, Marci R et al. "Environment and women's reproductive health." *Hum Reprod Update* 2011; 17(3): 418-433.
- ³⁷ Le Moal J, Sharpe RM, Jvarphirgensen N et al.. "Toward a multi-country monitoring system of reproductive health in the context of endocrine disrupting chemical exposure." *Eur J Public Health* 2016; 26(1): 76-83.
- ³⁸ Skulstad SM, Iglund J, Johannessen A et al. Validation of maternal reported pregnancy and birth characteristics against the Medical Birth Registry of Norway. *PLoS One* 2017; 12(8): e0181794. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0181794>
- ³⁹ Abreu AP, Kaiser UB. Pubertal development and regulation. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol.* 2016 Mar;4(3):254-264.
- ⁴⁰ Rasmussen AR, Wohlfahrt-Veje C, Tefre de Renzy-Martin K, Hagen CP, Tinggaard J, Mouritsen A, et al. Validity of Self-Assessment of Pubertal Maturation. *Pediatrics.* 2015;135(1):86–93.
- ⁴¹ Terry MB, Goldberg M, Schechter S, Houghton LC, White ML, OToole K, et al. Comparison of Clinical, Maternal, and Self Pubertal Assessments: Implications for Health Studies. *Pediatrics.* 2016;138(1):e20154571–e20154571.
- ⁴² Coleman L, Coleman J. The measurement of puberty: A review. *J Adolesc.* 2002;25(5):535–50.
- ⁴³ Dzwilewski KL, Schantz SL. Prenatal chemical exposures and child language development. *J Commun Disord.* 2015 Sep-Oct;57:41-65.
- ⁴⁴ Freire C, Ramos R, Lopez-Espinosa MJ et al. Hair mercury levels, fish consumption, and cognitive development in preschool children from Granada, Spain. *Environ Res.* 2010 Jan;110(1):96-104.
- ⁴⁵ Albers, Craig A.; Grieve, Adam J. (2007-06-01). "Test Review: Bayley, N. (2006). *Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development– Third Edition*. San Antonio, TX: Harcourt Assessment". *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment.* 25 (2): 180–190. doi:10.1177/0734282906297199
- ⁴⁶ Madrell C, Goldenberg DS. DIAL-4 training packet Co. Bloomington, IL: NCS Pearson, Inc. 2011
- ⁴⁷ Newborg J. Battelle Development Inventory (2nd ed.). Itasca, IUL: Riverside Publishing. 2005
- ⁴⁸ Elliott CD. *Differential Ability Scales* (2nd ed). San Antonio, Tx: Harcourt Assessment. 2007
- ⁴⁹ Kaplan, R. M., & Sacuzzo, D. P.(2010). *Psychological Testing: Principles, Applications, & Issues*, Eighth Edition. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth, Cengage Learning
- ⁵⁰ Flint DL, Hick TL, Horan MD et al. Dimensionality of the California Preschool Social Competence Scale. *Applied Psychological Measurements* 1980; 4(2): 203-212
- ⁵¹ American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*. 4th ed., American Psychiatric Association, Washington, DC (1994).
- ⁵² Williams J, Scott F, Stott C, et al. The CAST (Childhood Asperger Syndrome Test) : test accuracy. *Autism* :2004, 45-68.
- ⁵³ Scott F, Baron-Cohen S, Bolton P, Brayne C. The CAST (Childhood Asperger Syndrome Test) : Preliminary development of UK screen for mainstream primary-school children. *Autism* 2002; 6(1):9-31.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
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⁵⁴ Goodman R (2001) Psychometric properties of the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry* 40:1337–1345.

⁵⁵ Wechsler D. Wechsler Preschool and Primary Scale of Intelligence—Third Edition. 2002. San Antonio, TX: The Psychological Corporation.

⁵⁶ Achenbach TM. The Achenbach System of Empirically Based Assessment (ASEBA): Development, Findings, Theory, and Applications. University of Vermont Research Center for Children, Youth, & Families, Burlington, VT (2009).

⁵⁷ Langrigan PJ et al. The developing brain and the environment. *Environ Health Perspect* 2000; 108(Suppl 3): 373-595.

⁵⁸ Anger, W. K. Workplace exposures. Pp. 331–347 in *Neurobehavioral Toxicology*, Z. Annau, ed. Baltimore, Md.: Johns Hopkins University Press 1986.

⁵⁹ Kimmel CA. Current status of behavioural teratology. Science and regulations. *CRC Crit Rev Toxicol* 1988; 19:1-10.

⁶⁰ Nelson BK. Evidence for behavioural teratogenicity in humans. *J Appl Toxicol* 1991; 11: 33-37.

⁶¹ Jacobson JL, Jacobson SW. Assessing neurotoxicity in children. In Tilson HA & Harry GJ ed. *Neurotoxicology*. New York, Taylor and Francis 1999, pp. 339-366.

⁶² Needleman HL, Schell A, Bellinger D, Leviton A & Alfred EN. The long-term effects of exposure to low doses of lead in childhood. An 11 year follow-up report. *N Eng J Med* 1990; 322(2): 83-88.

⁶³ Rosenberg NL (1995) Basic principles of clinical neurotoxicology. In: Chang LW & Slikker W ed. *Neurotoxicology: Approaches and methods*. New York, Academic Press, pp 617-627.

⁶⁴ Feldman RG (1999) Occupational and environmental neurotoxicology. Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, Lippincott-Raven.

⁶⁵ Schaumburg HH (2000) Human neurotoxic disease. In: Spencer PS, Schaumburg HH, & Ludolph AC ed. *Experimental and clinical neurotoxicology*. New York, Oxford University Press, pp 55-82.

⁶⁶ White RF & Proctor SP (1995) Clinico-neuropsychological assessment methods in behavioural neurotoxicology. In: Chang LW & Slikker W ed. *Neurotoxicology: Approaches and methods*. New York, Academic Press, pp 711-726.

⁶⁷ Johnson BL, Baker EL, El Batawi M, Gilioli R, Hänninen H, Seppäläinen AM, & Xintaras C (1987) Prevention of neurotoxic illness in working populations. New York, John Wiley & Sons.

⁶⁸ Iregren A (1998) Computer-assisted testing. In: Costa LG & Manzo L ed. *Occupational neurotoxicology*. Boca Raton, Florida, CRC Press, pp 213-233.

⁶⁹ Anger WK, Letz R, Chrislip D, Frumkin H, Hudnell K, Russo JM, Chappell W, & Hutchinson L (1994) Neurobehavioral test methods for environmental health studies of adults. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*, 16: 489-497.

⁷⁰ Laursen P (1990) A computer-aided technique for testing cognitive functions validated on a sample of Danes 30 to 60 years of age. *Acta Neurol Scand Suppl*, 131: 1-108.

⁷¹ Williamson AM (1990) The development of a neurobehavioral test battery for use in hazard evaluations in occupational settings. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*, 12: 509-514.

⁷² Cassito MG, Gilioli R, & Camerino D (1989) Experiences with the Milan Automated Neurobehavioral System (MANS) in occupational neurotoxic exposures. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*, 11: 571-574.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
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⁷³ Eckerman DA, Carroll JB, Foree D, Gullion CM, Lansman M, Long ER, Waller MB, & Wallsten TS (1985) An approach to brief field testing for neurotoxicity. *Neurobehav Toxicol Teratol*, 7: 387-393.

⁷⁴ Baker EL, Letz RE, Fidler AT, Shalat S, Plantamura D, & Lyndon M (1985) A computer based neurobehavioural evaluation system for occupational and environmental epidemiology: Methodology and validation studies. *Neurobehav Toxicol Teratol*, 7:369-377.

⁷⁵ Gamberale F, Iregren A, & Kjellberg A (1990) Computerized performance testing in neurotoxicology. Why, what, how and whereto? In: Russel RW, Flattau PE, & Pope AM ed. *Behavioral measures of neurotoxicity*. Washington, DC, National Academy Press, pp 359-395.

⁷⁶ Bolla KI & Roca R (1994) Neuropsychiatric sequelae of occupational exposure to neurotoxins. In: Bleeker ML & Hansen JA ed. *Occupational neurology and clinical neurotoxicology*. Baltimore, Maryland, Williams and Wilkins, pp 133-158.

⁷⁷ McNair et al. (1971) *Manual for the Profile of Mood States*. San Diego, CA: Educational and Industrial Testing Service.

⁷⁸ Grove, J.R., & Prapavessis, H. (1992). Preliminary evidence for the reliability and validity of an abbreviated Profile of Mood States. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 23, 93-109.

⁷⁹ Hänninen H (1971) Psychological picture of manifest and latent carbon disulfide poisoning. *Br J Ind Med*, 28: 374-381.

⁸⁰ Chouaniere D, Cassitto MG, Spurgeon A, Verdier A, & Gilioli R (1997) An international questionnaire to explore neurotoxic symptoms. *Environ Res*, 73(1-2): 70-72.

⁸¹ Hogstedt C, Andersson K, & Hane M (1984) A questionnaire approach to the monitoring of early disturbances in central nervous function. In: Aitio A, Riihimäki V, & Vainio H ed. *The biological monitoring of exposure to industrial chemicals*. Washington, DC, Hemisphere, pp 275-287.

⁸² Hooisma J, Hänninen H, Emmen HH, & Kulig BM (1994) Symptoms indicative of the effects of organic solvent exposure in Dutch painters. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*, 16: 613-622.

⁸³ Ruijten MWMM, Hooisma J, Brons JT, Habets CEP, Emmen HH, & Muijser H (1994) Neurobehavioral effects of long-term exposure to xylene and mixed organic solvents in shipyard spray painters. *Neurotoxicology*, 15(3): 613-620.

⁸⁴ Viaene MK, Masschelein R, Leenders J, De Groof M, Swerts LJ, & Roels HA (2000) Neurobehavioural effects of occupational exposure to cadmium: A cross sectional epidemiological study. *Occup Environ Med*, 57: 19-27.

⁸⁵ Mergler D (1995) Behavioural neurophysiology: Quantitative measures of sensory function. In: Chang LW & Slikker W ed. *Neurotoxicology: Approaches and methods*. New York, Academic Press, pp 727-736.

⁸⁶ Araki S, Yokoyama K, & Murata K (1997) Neurophysiological methods in occupational and environmental health: Methodology and recent findings. *Environ Res*, 73: 42-51.

⁸⁷ Anger WK, Letz R, Chrislip D, Frumkin H, Hudnell K, Russo JM, Chappell W, & Hutchinson L (1994) Neurobehavioral test methods for environmental health studies of adults. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*, 16: 489-497.

⁸⁸ Amler RW, Anger WK, & Sizemore OJ (1995) Adult environmental neurobehavioral test battery. Training manual. Atlanta, Georgia, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry, pp 1-360.

⁸⁹ Mergler D (1995) Behavioural neurophysiology: Quantitative measures of sensory function. In: Chang LW & Slikker W ed. *Neurotoxicology: Approaches and methods*. New York, Academic Press, pp 727-736.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
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- ⁹⁰ Dick RB, Bhattacharya A, & Shukla R (1990) Use of a computerized postural sway measurement system for neurobehavioural toxicology. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*, 12: 1-6.
- ⁹¹ Newland MC (1997) Neural, behavioural and measurement considerations in the detection of motor impairment. In: Lowndes HE & Reuhl KR ed. *Comprehensive toxicology*. New York, Pergamon Press, pp 309-331.
- ⁹² Urban P, Lukás E, Nerudová J, Cábelloková Z, Cikrt M. Neurological and electrophysiological examinations on three groups of workers with different levels of exposure to mercury vapors. *Eur J Neurol*. 1999 Sep;6(5):571-7.
- ⁹³ Prockop LD (1995) Neuroimaging in neurotoxicology. In: Chang LW & Slikker W ed. *Neurotoxicology: Approaches and methods*. New York, Academic Press, pp 753-763.
- ⁹⁴ Sullivan E, Rosenbloom M, & Pfefferbaum A (1998) Effect of neurotoxins revealed through in vivo brain imaging. In: Tilson H & Harry G ed. *Neurotoxicology*. New York, Taylor and Francis, pp 287-309.
- ⁹⁵ Trieberg G (1998) Role of brain imaging techniques in occupational neurotoxicology. In: Costa LG & Manzo L ed. *Occupational neurotoxicology*. Boca Raton, Florida, CRC Press, pp 199-210.
- ⁹⁶ Jurewicz J, Polańska K, Hanke W. Chemical exposure early in life and the neurodevelopment of children--an overview of current epidemiological evidence. *Ann Agric Environ Med*. 2013;20(3):465-86.
- ⁹⁷ De Felice A, Ricceri L, Venerosi A, Chiarotti F, Calamandrei G. Multifactorial Origin of Neurodevelopmental Disorders: Approaches to Understanding Complex Etiologies. *Toxics*. 2015 Mar 23;3(1):89-129.
- ⁹⁸ Landrigan PJ, Kimmel CA, Correa A, Eskenazi B. Children's health and the environment: public health issues and challenges for risk assessment. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2004 Feb;112(2):257-65.
- ⁹⁹ Winneke G. Endpoints of developmental neurotoxicity in environmentally exposed children. *Toxicol Lett*. 1995 May;77(1-3):127-36.
- ¹⁰⁰ Jacobson JL, Jacobson SW. Methodological issues in research on developmental exposure to neurotoxic agents. *Neurotoxicol Teratol*. 2005 May-Jun;27(3):395-406.
- ¹⁰¹ Squires J, Bricker D. *Ages & Stages Questionnaires, Third Edition (ASQ-3)*. Brookes, Baltimore, 2009.
- ¹⁰² Singh A, Yeh CJ, Boone Blanchard S. Ages and Stages Questionnaire: a global screening scale. *Bol Med Hosp Infant Mex*. 2017;74(1):5-12.
- ¹⁰³ Schonhaut L, Armijo I, Schönstedt M, Alvarez J, Cordero M. Validity of the ages and stages questionnaires in term and preterm infants. *Pediatrics*. 2013;131(5):e1468-74.
- ¹⁰⁴ Glascoe FP, Byrne KE. The accuracy of developmental screening tests. *J Early Interv* 1993;17:368-78.
- ¹⁰⁵ Coghlan D, Kiing JS, Wake M. Parents' Evaluation of Developmental Status in the Australian day-care setting: developmental concerns of parents and carers. *J Paediatr Child Health*. 2003;39(1):49-54.
- ¹⁰⁶ Lowe JR, Erickson SJ, Schrader R, Duncan AF. Comparison of the Bayley II Mental Developmental Index and the Bayley III Cognitive Scale: are we measuring the same thing? *Acta Paediatr*. 2012 Feb;101(2):e55-8.
- ¹⁰⁷ Johnson S, Moore T, Marlow N. Using the Bayley-III to assess neurodevelopmental delay: which cut-off should be used? *Pediatr Res*. 2014;75(5):670-4.
- ¹⁰⁸ Hadders-Algra M. *Neurological Examination of the Child with Minor Neurological Dysfunction*. 3rd Edition. London: Mac Keith Press; 2010

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
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Authors: Hanna Tolonen et al.	Page: 146

¹⁰⁹ Amiel-Tison C. Update of the Amiel-Tison neurologic assessment for the term neonate or at 40 weeks corrected age. *Pediatric Neurology*. 2002;27:196–212.

¹¹⁰ Milani-Comparetti A, Gidoni EA. Routine developmental examination in normal and retarded children. *Dev Med Child Neurol*. 2008;9:631–8.

¹¹¹ Haataja L, Mercuri E, Regev R, Cowan F, Rutherford M, Dubowitz V, et al. Optimality score for the neurologic examination of the infant at 12 and 18 months of age. *J Pediatr*. 1999;135:153–61.

¹¹² Gascon M, Casas M, Morales E, Valvi D, Ballesteros-Gómez A. Prenatal exposure to bisphenol A and phthalates and childhood respiratory tract infections and allergy. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2015 Feb;135(2):370-8.

¹¹³ Robinson L, Miller R. The Impact of Bisphenol A and Phthalates on Allergy, Asthma, and Immune Function: a Review of Latest Findings. *Curr Environ Health Rep*. 2015 Dec;2(4):379-87

¹¹⁴ Bornehag CG, Nanberg E. Phthalate exposure and asthma in children. *Int J Androl*. 2010 Apr;33(2):333-45.

¹¹⁵ Boldt A, Borte S, Fricke S et al (2014) Eight-color immunophenotyping of T-, B-, and NK-cell subpopulations for characterization of chronic immunodeficiencies. *Cytometry B Clin Cytometry* 86:191–206.

¹¹⁶ Porwit A, Rajab A (2015) Flow cytometry immunophenotyping in integrated diagnostics of patients with newly diagnosed cytopenia: one tube 10-color 14-antibody screening panel and 3-tube extensive panel for detection of MDS-related features. *Int J Lab Hematol* 37(Suppl 1):133–143.

¹¹⁷ Streitz M, Miloud T, Kapinsky M et al (2013) Standardization of whole blood immune phenotype monitoring for clinical trials: panels and methods from the ONE study. *Transplant Res* 2:17.

¹¹⁸ Roederer M, Tarnok A (2010) OMIPs—orchestrating multiplexity in polychromatic science. *Cytometry A* 77:811–812.

¹¹⁹ Claus M, Dychus N, Ebel M et al. (2016) Measuring the immune system: a comprehensive approach for the analysis of immune functions in humans. *Arch Toxicol* (2016) 90:2481–2495.

¹²⁰ WHO (2000). Obesity: preventing and managing the global epidemic: report of a WHO consultation. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization (WHO Technical Report Series, No. 894). Available from: http://www.who.int/nutrition/publications/obesity/WHO_TRS_894/en/

¹²¹ Roundtable on Environmental Health Sciences, Research, and Medicine; Board on Population Health and Public Health Practice; Health and Medicine Division; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. The Interplay Between Environmental Chemical Exposures and Obesity: Proceedings of a Workshop. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2016 Jul. The National Academies Collection: Reports funded by National Institutes of Health.

¹²² Kelishadi R, Poursafa P, Jamshidi F. Role of environmental chemicals in obesity: a systematic review on the current evidence. *J Environ Public Health*. 2013;2013:896789.

¹²³ Tolonen H (Ed.) EHES Manual. Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5> (Sections 5.1.2 Height and 5.1.3 Weight)

¹²⁴ WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study Group. WHO Child Growth Standards: Growth velocity based on weight, length and head circumference: Methods and development. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2009.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
Authors: Hanna Tolonen et al.	Page: 147

¹²⁵ WHO Multicentre Growth Reference Study Group. WHO Child Growth Standards. Methods and development: Length/height-for-age, weight-for-age, weight-for-length, weight-for-height and body mass index-for-age. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2006.

¹²⁶ Maukonen M, Männistö S, Tolonen H. A comparison of measured versus self-reported anthropometrics for assessing obesity in adults: a literature review. *Scand J Public Health*. 2018 Jul;46(5):565-579.

¹²⁷ Ashwell M, Gunn P, Gibson S. Waist-to-height ratio is a better screening tool than waist circumference and BMI for adult cardiometabolic risk factors: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obes Rev*. 2012 Mar;13(3):275-86.

¹²⁸ Lo K, Wong M, Khalechelvam P, Tam W. Waist-to-height ratio, body mass index and waist circumference for screening paediatric cardio-metabolic risk factors: a meta-analysis. *Obes Rev*. 2016 Dec;17(12):1258-1275.

¹²⁹ Elobeid MA, Padilla MA, Brock DW, Ruden DM, Allison DB. Endocrine disruptors and obesity: an examination of selected persistent organic pollutants in the NHANES 1999-2002 data. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2010 Jul;7(7):2988-3005.

¹³⁰ Hatch EE, Nelson JW, Qureshi MM, Weinberg J, Moore LL, Singer M, Webster TF. Association of urinary phthalate metabolite concentrations with body mass index and waist circumference: a cross-sectional study of NHANES data, 1999-2002. *Environ Health*. 2008 Jun 3;7:27.

¹³¹ Waist circumference and waist-hip ratio: report of a WHO expert consultation, Geneva, 8-11 December 2008. Available from: http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/44583/9789241501491_eng.pdf?ua=1

¹³² Schwandt P, Haas GM. Is the ratio waist circumference to height (WHtR) of 0.5 a universal measure for abdominal adiposity in children and adolescents? *Int J Obes (Lond)*. 2016 Jul;40(7):1141-2.

¹³³ Tolonen H (Ed.) EHES Manual. Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5> (Section 5.1.4 Waist circumference)

¹³⁴ "Classification of Overweight and Obesity by BMI, Waist Circumference, and Associated Disease Risks," 2012, http://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/health/public/heart/obesity/lose_wt/bmi_dis.htm. (Accessed March 8, 2019)

¹³⁵ de Onis M, Onyango AW, Borghi E, Siyan A, Nishida C, Siekmann J. Development of WHO growth reference for school-aged children and adolescents. *Bull World Health Organ*, 85 (9) (2007), pp. 660-667

¹³⁶ Cole TJ, Bellizzi MC, Flegal KM, Dietz WH. Establishing a standard definition for child overweight and obesity worldwide: international survey. *BMJ*, 320 (2000), pp. 1240-1243.

¹³⁷ Maukonen M, Männistö S, Tolonen H. A comparison of measured versus self-reported anthropometrics for assessing obesity in adults: a literature review. *Scand J Public Health*. 2018 Jul;46(5):565-579.

¹³⁸ Gallagher D, Heymsfield SB, Heo M, Jebb SA, Murgatroyd PR, Sakamoto Y. Healthy percentage body fat ranges: an approach for developing guidelines based on body mass index. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 2000 Sep;72(3):694-701.

¹³⁹ Fryar CD, Gu Q, Ogden CL, Flegal KM. Anthropometric reference data for children and adults: United States, 2011–2014. National Center for Health Statistics. *Vital Health Stat* 2016;3(39).

¹⁴⁰ Vasudev S, Mohan A, Mohan D, Farooq S, Raj D, Mohan V. Validation of body fat measurement by skinfolds and two bioelectric impedance methods with DEXA--the Chennai Urban Rural Epidemiology Study [CURES-3]. *J Assoc Physicians India*. 2004 Nov;52:877-81.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
Authors: Hanna Tolonen et al.	Page: 148

¹⁴¹ Lu HK, Chiang LM, Chen YY, Chuang CL et al. Hand-to-Hand Model for Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis to Estimate Fat Free Mass in a Healthy Population. *Nutrients*. 2016 Oct 21;8(10).

¹⁴² Grundy SM, Brewer HB Jr, Cleeman JI, Smith SC Jr, Lenfant C; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute; American Heart Association. Definition of metabolic syndrome: report of the National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute/American Heart Association conference on scientific issues related to definition. *Arterioscler Thromb Vasc Biol*. 2004 Feb;24(2):e13-8.

¹⁴³ Lottenberg, Simão Augusto, Glezer, Andrea, & Turatti, Luiz Alberto. (2007). Metabolic syndrome: identifying the risk factors. *Jornal de Pediatria*, 83(5, Suppl.), S204-S208

¹⁴⁴ World Health Organization (2016). Global report on diabetes. World Health Organization. <http://www.who.int/iris/handle/10665/204871>

¹⁴⁵ Papalou O, Kandaraki EA, Papadakis G, Diamanti-Kandarkis e. Endocrine disrupting chemicals: An occult mediator of metabolic disease, *Front Endocrinol* 2019;10:112. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2019.00112

¹⁴⁶ Use of glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) in the diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2011.

¹⁴⁷ Nathan DM, Davidson MB, DeFronzo RA, Heine RJ, Henry RR, Pratley R, Zinman B. Impaired Fasting Glucose and Impaired Glucose Tolerance. *Diabetes Care* Mar 2007, 30 (3) 753-759

¹⁴⁸ Paalanen L, Koponen P, Laatikainen T, Tolonen H. Public health monitoring of hypertension, diabetes and elevated cholesterol: comparison of different data sources. *Eur J Public Health*. 2018 Aug 1;28(4):754-765.

¹⁴⁹ www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases

¹⁵⁰ Global Atlas on Cardiovascular Disease Prevention and Control. Mendis S, Puska P, Norrving B editors. World Health Organization, Geneva 2011

¹⁵¹ EJ, Virani SS, Callaway CW et al. and On behalf of the American Heart Association Council on Epidemiology and Prevention Statistics Committee and Stroke Statistics Subcommittee. Heart Disease and Stroke Statistics—2018 Update: A Report From the American Heart Association; Benjamin. *Circulation* 2018;137:e67–e492. doi.org/10.1161/CIR.0000000000000558

¹⁵² Han C, Hong YC. Bisphenol A, Hypertension, and Cardiovascular Diseases: Epidemiological, Laboratory, and Clinical Trial Evidence. *Curr Hypertens Rep*. 2016 Feb;18(2):11.

¹⁵³ Franklin BA, Brook R, Arden Pope C 3rd. Air pollution and cardiovascular disease. *Curr Probl Cardiol*. 2015 May;40(5):207-38.

¹⁵⁴ Arnett DK, Blumenthal RS, Albert MA et al. ACC/AHA Guideline on the Primary Prevention of Cardiovascular Disease. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 2019. DOI: 10.1016/j.jacc.2019.03.010

¹⁵⁵ Klungel OH, de Boer A, Paes AH, Seidell JC, Bakker A. Cardiovascular diseases and risk factors in a population-based study in The Netherlands: agreement between questionnaire information and medical records. *Neth J Med*. 1999;55(4):177–83.

¹⁵⁶ Muggah E, Graves E, Bennett C, Manuel DG. Ascertainment of chronic diseases using population health data: a comparison of health administrative data and patient self-report. *BMC Public Health*. 2013;13:16.

¹⁵⁷ St Sauver JL, Hagen PT, Cha SS, Bagniewski SM, Mandrekar JN, Curoe AM, et al. Agreement between patient reports of cardiovascular disease and patient medical records. *Mayo Clin Proc*. 2005;80(2):203–10.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
Authors: Hanna Tolonen et al.	Page: 149

- ¹⁵⁸ Bolland MJ, Barber A, Doughty RN, Grey A, Gamble G, Reid IR. Differences between self-reported and verified adverse cardiovascular events in a randomised clinical trial. *BMJ Open*. 2013;3(3).
- ¹⁵⁹ Heistaro S. Methodology Report: Health 2000 Survey. Publications of the National Public Health Institute, Helsinki 2008. Available at: <http://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe201204193320>
- ¹⁶⁰ Lundqvist A, Mäki-Opas T (eds.). Health 2011 Survey - Methods. 2016. Juvenes Print - Finnish university Print Ltd, Tampere, Finland 2016. Available at: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-669-8>
- ¹⁶¹ Tolonen H (Ed.) EHES Manual. Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>
- ¹⁶² Lee W. General principles of carotid Doppler ultrasonography *Ultrasonography*. 2014 Jan; 33(1): 11–17
- ¹⁶³ World Health Organization. (2004). ICD-10 : international statistical classification of diseases and related health problems : tenth revision, 2nd ed. Geneva : World Health Organization. <http://www.who.int/iris/handle/10665/42980>
- ¹⁶⁴ Bergmann MM, Calle EE, Mervis CA, Miracle-McMahill HL, Thun MJ, Heath CW. Validity of self-reported cancers in a prospective cohort study in comparison with data from state cancer registries. *Am J Epidemiol*. 1998;15;147(6):556-62.
- ¹⁶⁵ Cho S, Shin A, Song D, Park JK, Kim Y, Choi JY, Kang D, Lee JK. Validity of self-reported cancer history in the health examinees (HEXA) study: A comparison of self-report and cancer registry records. *Cancer Epidemiol*. 2017;50:16-21.
- ¹⁶⁶ Prüss-Ustün A, Vickers C, Haefliger P, Bertollini R. Knowns and unknowns on burden of disease due to chemicals: a systematic review. *Environ Health*. 2011 Jan 21;10:9.
- ¹⁶⁷ Kang MY, Cho SH, Lim YH, Seo JC, Hong YC. Effects of environmental cadmium exposure on liver function in adults. *Occup Environ Med*. 2013 Apr;70(4):268-73.
- ¹⁶⁸ Kasarala G, Tillmann HL. Standard liver tests. *Clinical liver disease* 2016;8(1):13-18.
- ¹⁶⁹ Hoekstra et al. Physiological and biochemical basis of clinical liver function tests: a review. *Ann Surg*. 2013;257(1):27-36
- ¹⁷⁰ Lo Re V 3rd, Carbonari DM, Forde KA, Goldberg D et al. Validity of diagnostic codes and laboratory tests of liver dysfunction to identify acute liver failure events. *Pharmacoepidemiol Drug Saf*. 2015 Jul;24(7):676-83.
- ¹⁷¹ Hsu RK, Hsu CY. The Role of Acute Kidney Injury in Chronic Kidney Disease. *Semin Nephrol*. 2016;36(4):283-92.
- ¹⁷² Kataria A, Trasande L, Trachtman H. The effects of environmental chemicals on renal function. *Nat Rev Nephrol*. 2015;11(10):610-25.
- ¹⁷³ Rahman M, Shad F, Smith MC. Acute kidney injury: a guide to diagnosis and management. *Am Fam Physician*. 2012 1;86(7):631-9.
- ¹⁷⁴ Koza Y. Acute kidney injury: current concepts and new insights. *J Inj Violence Res*. 2016;8(1):58-62.
- ¹⁷⁵ Kashani K, Shao M, Li G, Williams AW. No increase in the incidence of acute kidney injury in a population-based annual temporal trends epidemiology study. *Kidney Int*. 2017 Sep;92(3):721-728.
- ¹⁷⁶ Anandarajah S1, Tai T, de Lusignan S, Stevens P, O'Donoghue D, Walker M, Hilton S. The validity of searching routinely collected general practice computer data to identify patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD): a manual review of 500 medical records. *Nephrol Dial Transplant*. 2005 Oct;20(10):2089-96.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
Authors: Hanna Tolonen et al.	Page: 150

¹⁷⁷ Qaseem A, Wilt TJ, Weinberger SE et al. American College of Physicians; American College of Chest Physicians; American Thoracic Society; European Respiratory Society. Diagnosis and management of stable chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a clinical practice guideline update from the American College of Physicians, American College of Chest Physicians, American Thoracic Society, and European Respiratory Society. *Ann Intern Med*. 2011 Aug 2;155(3):179-91. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-155-3-201108020-00008

¹⁷⁸ Delzell JE Jr. Common lung conditions: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *FP Essent*. 2013 Jun;409:23-31

¹⁷⁹ Muggah E, Graves E, Bennett C, Manuel DG. Ascertainment of chronic diseases using population health data: a comparison of health administrative data and patient self-report. *BMC Public Health*. 2013 Jan 9;13:16.

¹⁸⁰ Gini R, Francesconi P, Mazzaglia G, Cricelli I et al. Chronic disease prevalence from Italian administrative databases in the VALORE project: a validation through comparison of population estimates with general practice databases and national survey. *BMC Public Health*. 2013 Jan 9;13:15.

¹⁸¹ Reddel HK, Taylor DR, Bateman ED, et al. An official American Thoracic Society/European Respiratory Society statement: asthma control and exacerbations: standardizing endpoints for clinical asthma trials and clinical practice. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2009; 180: 59–99

¹⁸² Bousquet J, Mantzouranis E, Cruz AA, Ait-Khaled N, et al. Uniform definition of asthma severity, control, and exacerbations: document presented for the World Health Organization Consultation on Severe Asthma. *J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2010; 126: 926–938

¹⁸³ Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA). Global Strategy for Asthma Management and Prevention 2012 (update). <https://ginasthma.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/2012-GINA.pdf>

¹⁸⁴ Gascon M, Casas M, Morales E, Valvi D, Ballesteros-Gómez A. Prenatal exposure to bisphenol A and phthalates and childhood respiratory tract infections and allergy. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2015 Feb;135(2):370-8.

¹⁸⁵ Robinson L, Miller R. The Impact of Bisphenol A and Phthalates on Allergy, Asthma, and Immune Function: a Review of Latest Findings. *Curr Environ Health Rep*. 2015 Dec;2(4):379-87.

¹⁸⁶ Bornehag CG, Nanberg E. Phthalate exposure and asthma in children. *Int J Androl*. 2010 Apr;33(2):333-45.

¹⁸⁷ Beasley R, Semprini A, Mitchell EA. Risk factors for asthma: is prevention possible? *Lancet*. 2015 Sep 12;386(9998):1075-85.

¹⁸⁸ Asher MI, Montefort S, Bjorksten B, et al. Worldwide time trends in the prevalence of symptoms of asthma, allergic rhinoconjunctivitis, and eczema in childhood: ISAAC Phases One and Three repeat multicountry cross-sectional surveys. *Lancet* 2006;368:733–743.

¹⁸⁹ International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC) Steering Committee. Worldwide variations in the prevalence of asthma symptoms: the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC). *Eur Respir J* 1998;12:315–335.

¹⁹⁰ Lai CK, Beasley R, Crane J, et al. Global variation in the prevalence and severity of asthma symptoms: phase three of the International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood (ISAAC). *Thorax* 2009;64:476–483.

¹⁹¹ Lang A, Carlsen KH, Haaland G, et al. Severe asthma in childhood: assessed in 10 year olds in a birth cohort study. *Allergy* 2008;63:1054–1060.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
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- ¹⁹² Sigurs N, Gustafsson PM, Bjarnason R, et al. Severe respiratory syncytial virus bronchiolitis in infancy and asthma and allergy at age 13. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2005; 171: 137–141
- ¹⁹³ Miller RL, Ho SM. Environmental epigenetics and asthma: current concepts and call for studies. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2008; 177: 567–573.
- ¹⁹⁴ Ober C, Hoffjan S. Asthma genetics 2006: the long and winding road to gene discovery. *Genes Immun* 2006; 7: 95–100.
- ¹⁹⁵ The International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood, ISAAC. <http://isaac.auckland.ac.nz/>
- ¹⁹⁶ Braun-Fahrländer C, Wüthrich B, Gassner M, Grize L, Sennhauser FH, Varonier HS, Vuille JC. Validation of a rhinitis symptom questionnaire (ISAAC core questions) in a population of Swiss school children visiting the school health services. SCARPOL-team. Swiss Study on Childhood Allergy and Respiratory Symptom with respect to Air Pollution and Climate. International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood. *Pediatr Allergy Immunol.* 1997 May;8(2):75-82.
- ¹⁹⁷ Fuso L, de Rosa M, Corbo GM, Valente S, Forastiere F, Agabiti N, Pistelli R. Repeatability of the ISAAC video questionnaire and its accuracy against a clinical diagnosis of asthma. *Respir Med.* 2000 Apr;94(4):397-403.
- ¹⁹⁸ Cotes JE. Medical Research Council Questionnaire on respiratory symptoms. Correspondence, *Lancet* , 1987, vol. 2 pg. 1028
- ¹⁹⁹ European Community Respiratory Health Survey, ECRHS. <http://www.ecrhs.org/Quests.htm>
- ²⁰⁰ Sunyer J, Basagana X, Burney P, Anto JM. International assessment of the internal consistency of respiratory symptoms. European Community Respiratory Health Study (ECRHS) *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 2000;162(3 Pt 1):930–935.
- ²⁰¹ International Union Against Tuberculosis and Lung Disease (IUATLD) questionnaire https://digital.library.adelaide.edu.au/dspace/bitstream/2440/45467/1/hdl_45467.pdf
- ²⁰² Ravault C, Kauffmann F. Validity of the IUATLD (1986) questionnaire in the EGEA study. International Union Against Tuberculosis and Lung Disease. Epidemiological study on the Genetics and Environment of Asthma, bronchial hyperresponsiveness and atopy. *Int J Tuberc Lung Dis.* 2001 Feb;5(2):191-6.
- ²⁰³ Ferris BG. Epidemiology Standardization Project. II. Recommended respiratory disease questionnaires for use with adults and children in epidemiological research. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1978; 118: 7–57.
- ²⁰⁴ National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/nhanes/nhanes_05_06/sp_rdq_d.pdf
- ²⁰⁵ Tan CH, Rasool S, Johnston GA. Contact dermatitis: allergic and irritant. *Clin Dermatol.* 2014 Jan-Feb;32(1):116-24.
- ²⁰⁶ Williams HC. So How Do I Define Atopic Eczema? A Practical Manual for Researchers Wishing to Define Atopic Eczema. www.nottingham.ac.uk/dermatology/eczema/ . Date last updated: November 1996
- ²⁰⁷ Severity scoring of atopic dermatitis: the SCORAD index. Consensus Report of the European Task Force on Atopic Dermatitis. *Dermatology.* 1993;186(1):23-31.
- ²⁰⁸ Kunz B, Oranje AP, Labrèze L, Stalder JF, Ring J, Taïeb A. Clinical validation and guidelines for the SCORAD index: consensus report of the European Task Force on Atopic Dermatitis. *Dermatology.* 1997;195(1):10-9

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
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- ²⁰⁹ Oranje AP, Glazenburg EJ, Wolkerstorfer A, de Waard-van der Spek FB. Practical issues on interpretation of scoring atopic dermatitis: the SCORAD index, objective SCORAD and the three-item severity score. *Br J Dermatol*: 2007 Oct;157(4):645-8. Epub 2007 Aug 21
- ²¹⁰ Grados F, Fechtenbaum J, Flipon E ym. Radiographic methods for evaluating osteoporotic vertebral fractures. *Joint Bone Spine* 2009;76:241-7
- ²¹¹ Laugier P. An overview of bone sonometry. *Int Congr Ser*. 2004;1274:23–32
- ²¹² Chin KY, Ima-Nirwana S. Calcaneal quantitative ultrasound as a determinant of bone health status: what properties of bone does it reflect? *BMC Geriatr*. 2014 :20;14:143
- ²¹³ Thomsen K, Ryg J, Hermann AP, Matzen L, Masud T. Calcaneal quantitative ultrasound and phalangeal radiographic absorptiometry alone or in combination in a triage approach for assessment of osteoporosis: a study of older women with a high prevalence of falls. *BMC Geriatr*. 2014: 20;14:143
- ²¹⁴ Tolonen H (Ed). EHES Manual, Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>
- ²¹⁵ Tolonen H (Ed). EHES Manual, Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>
- ²¹⁶ WHO (World Health Organization). WHO child growth standards: length/height-for-age, weight-for-age, weight-for-length, weight-for-height and body mass index-for-age: methods and development. Department of Nutrition for Health and Development, Geneva, WHO, 2006. URL: https://www.who.int/childgrowth/standards/Technical_report.pdf?ua=1
- ²¹⁷ Darbre PD. Endocrine Disruptors and Obesity. 2017. *Curr Obes Rep*. 6:18-27.
- ²¹⁸ Barlow SE. Expert committee recommendations regarding the prevention, assessment, and treatment of child and adolescent overweight and obesity: summary report. *Pediatrics* 2007;120(Suppl 4):S164–92.
- ²¹⁹ CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention). Defining Childhood Obesity URL: <https://www.cdc.gov/obesity/childhood/defining.html>
- ²²⁰ Kêkê LM, Samouda H et al. Body mass index and childhood obesity classification systems: a comparison of the French, International Obesity Task Force (IOTF) and World Health Organization (WHO) references. *Revue d'Épidémiologie et de Santé Publique* 2015;63:173-182.
- ²²¹ Canadian Paediatric Society, Community Health Nurses Association of Canada, Dietitians of Canada, and The College of Family Physicians of Canada [A collaborative statement]. Use of growth charts for assessing and monitoring growth in Canadian infants and children: Executive summary. 2004. *Paediatr Child Health* 9:171–3.
- ²²² World Health Organization. Training Course on Child Growth Assessment. Geneva, WHO, 2008. https://www.who.int/childgrowth/training/module_b_measuring_growth.pdf
- ²²³ See, for example: Tolonen H (Ed.) EHES Manual. Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>
- ²²⁴ Canadian Paediatric Society, Community Health Nurses Association of Canada, Dietitians of Canada, and The College of Family Physicians of Canada [A collaborative statement]. Use of growth charts for

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
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assessing and monitoring growth in Canadian infants and children: Executive summary. 2004. *Paediatr Child Health* 9:171–3.

²²⁵ See, for example: Tolonen H (Ed.) EHES Manual. Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5>

²²⁶ Falkner B, Daniels SR, Flynn JT, Gidding S et al. National High Blood Pressure Education Program Working Group on High Blood Pressure in Children and Adolescents. *Pediatrics* August 2004, VOLUME 114 / ISSUE Supplement 2

²²⁷ European Commission. Commission Regulation (EU) No 847/2012 on 19 September 2012 amending Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the council on the registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals (REACH) as regards mercury. In 847/2012. Edited by European Commission. Off J Eur Union, L253, 20.9.2012.

²²⁸ Campbell NRC, McKay DW, Chockalingam A, Fodor JG. Errors in assessment of blood pressure: patient factors. *Revue Canadienne de Santé Publique* 1994;85(Suppl 2): S12-S17

²²⁹ Campbell NRC, McKay DW. Accurate blood pressure measurement: Why does it matter? *CMAJ* 1999; 161(3):277-279

²³⁰ Handler J. The importance of accurate blood pressure measurement. *The Permanente Journal* 2009; 13(3): 51-54

²³¹ Netea RT, Lender JWM, Smots P, Thien Th. Both body and arm position significantly influence blood pressure measurement. *Journal of Human Hypertension* 2003; 17: 459-462

²³² Jamieson MJ, Webster J, Seren P, Jeffer TA, Scott AK, Robb OJ, Lovell HG, Petrie J. The measurement of blood pressure: sitting or supine, once or twice? *Journal of Hypertension* 1990; 8; 635-640

²³³ Keele-Smith R, Price-Danie C. Effects of crossing legs on blood pressure measurement. *Clinical nursing research* 2001; 10(2): 202-213

²³⁴ Schulze MB, Kroke A, Saracci R, Boeing H. The effect of difference in measurement procedure on the comparability of blood pressure estimates in multi-centre studies. *Blood Pressure Monitoring* 2002; 7: 95-104

²³⁵ O'Brien E, Asmar R, Beilin L et al. European Society of Hypertension recommendations for conventional, ambulatory and home blood pressure measurement. *Journal of Hypertension* 2003; 21: 821,848

²³⁶ Netea RT, Lender JWM, Smits P, Thien T. Arm position is important for blood pressure measurement. *Journal of Human Hypertension* 1999; 13:105-109

²³⁷ Gould BA, Hornung RS, Kieso HA, Altman DG, Raftery EB. Is the blood pressure the same in both arms? *Clin. Cardiol.* 1985; 8: 423-426

²³⁸ O'Brien E, Atkins N, Stergiou G, Karpettas N, Parati G, Asmar R, et al. European society of hypertension international protocol revision 2010 for the validation of blood pressure measuring devices in adults. *Blood Press Monit.* 2010;15(1):23–38.

²³⁹ AAMI. Non-invasive sphygmomanometers – part 2: clinical validation of automated measurement type. ANSI/AAMI/ISO 81060-2. Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation, 2013.

²⁴⁰ Stergiou G, Alpert B, Mieke S, et al. A universal standard for the validation of blood pressure measuring devices: Association for the Advancement of Medical Instrumentation/European Society of

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
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Hypertension/International Organization for Standardization (AAMI/ESH/ISO) Collaboration Statement. *Journal of Hypertension* 2018; 36: 472-478.

²⁴¹ O'Brien E, Petrie J, Little W, de Swiet M, Padfield PL et al. The British Hypertension Society protocol for the evaluation of blood pressure measuring devices. *Journal of Hypertension* 1993; 11(Suppl 2): S43-S62

²⁴² Tolonen H (Ed.) EHES Manual. Part B. Fieldwork procedures. 2nd edition. National Institute for Health and Welfare, 2016. Directions 2016_14. URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5, URL: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5> (Appendix 5.1 Blood pressure recording form).

²⁴³ Lurbe E, Agabiti-Rosei E, Cruickshank JK, Dominiczak A, Erdine S et al. 2016 European Society of Hypertension guidelines for the management of high blood pressure in children and adolescents. *Journal of Hypertension* 2016; 34: 1887-920.

²⁴⁴ Marshall WA, Tanner JM. Variations in pattern of pubertal changes in girls. *Arch Dis Child*. 1969 Jun;44(235):291–303.

²⁴⁵ Marshall WA, Tanner JM. Variations in the pattern of pubertal changes in boys. *Arch Dis Child*. 1970 Feb;45(239):13–23.

²⁴⁶ Rasmussen AR, Wohlfahrt-Veje C, Tefre de Renzy-Martin K, Hagen CP, Tinggaard J, Mouritsen A, et al. Validity of Self-Assessment of Pubertal Maturation. *Pediatrics*. 2015;135(1):86–93.

²⁴⁷ Terry MB, Goldberg M, Schechter S, Houghton LC, White ML, OToole K, et al. Comparison of Clinical, Maternal, and Self Pubertal Assessments: Implications for Health Studies. *Pediatrics*. 2016;138(1):e20154571–e20154571.

²⁴⁸ Coleman L, Coleman J. The measurement of puberty: A review. *J Adolesc*. 2002;25(5):535–50.

²⁴⁹ Hamilton et al (2011) The PhenX Toolkit: Get the Most From Your Measures. *American Journal of Epidemiology*, 174(3), 253-60.

²⁵⁰ en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tanner_scale;
www.medschool.lsuhsu.edu/medical_education/undergraduate/spm/SPM_100/documents/tannerstagescard.pdf

²⁵¹ Monteilh C, Kieszak S, Flanders WD, Maisonet M, Rubin C, Holmes AK, et al. Timing of maturation predictors of Tanner stage transitions in boys enrolled in a contemporary British cohort. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2011;25(1):75–87.

²⁵² Pellegrino R, Viegi G, Brusasco V et al. Interpretative strategies for lung function tests. *Eur Respir J* 2005 November 01;26(5):948-968.

²⁵³ Miller MR, Hankinson J, Brusasco V et al. Standardisation of spirometry. *Eur Respir J* 2005 August 01;26(2):319-338.

²⁵⁴ Vogelmeier CF, Criner GJ, Martinez FJ et al. Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management, and Prevention of Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease 2017 Report: GOLD Executive Summary. *Eur Respir J* 2017 March 06;49(3):2017.

²⁵⁵ Reddel HK, Bateman ED, Becker A et al. A summary of the new GINA strategy: a roadmap to asthma control. *Eur Respir J* 2015 September 01;46(3):622-639.

²⁵⁶ GINA, Asthma recommendations, 2018. Available at: <https://ginasthma.org/2018-gina-report-global-strategy-for-asthma-management-and-prevention/>. Accessed November 15 2018.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
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²⁵⁷ Aromaa A, Heliövaara M, Knekt P, et al. Cardiovascular and respiratory survey methods. Part 2 (in Finnish with English summary). Publications of the Social Insurance Institution 1985. Helsinki and Turku. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10138/162384>. Accessed November 15 2018.

²⁵⁸ NHANES, Respiratory Health, Spirometry Procedures Manual. 2008. Available at: https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/nhanes/nhanes_07_08/spirometry.pdf.

²⁵⁹ Health Survey for England 2015. 2016; Available at: <https://files.digital.nhs.uk/publicationimport/pub22xxx/pub22610/hse2015-methods.pdf> .

²⁶⁰ Quanjer PH, Pretto JJ, Brazzale DJ, Boros PW. Grading the severity of airways obstruction: new wine in new bottles. Eur Respir J 2014 February 01;43(2):505-512.

²⁶¹ Miller MR, Crapo R, Hankinson J et al. General considerations for lung function testing. Eur Respir J 2005 July 01;26(1):153-161.

²⁶² Culver BH, Graham BL, Coates AL et al. Recommendations for a Standardized Pulmonary Function Report. An Official American Thoracic Society Technical Statement. Am J Respir Crit Care Med 2017 December 01;196(11):1463-1472.

²⁶³ V.C. Moore. Spirometry: step by step. Breathe 2012;8.:232-240.

²⁶⁴ Health and Social Care Information Centre. Health Survey for England 2010, volume 2, Methods and documentation. 2011. Available at: <https://files.digital.nhs.uk/publicationimport/pub09xxx/pub09300/hse2011-methods-and-docs.pdf>.

²⁶⁵ Quanjer PH, Stanojevic S, Cole TJ et al. Multi-ethnic reference values for spirometry for the 3-95-yr age range: the global lung function 2012 equations. Eur Respir J 2012 December 01;40(6):1324-1343.

²⁶⁶ Health and Social Care Information Centre. Health Survey for England 2010, volume 2, Methods and documentation. 2011. Available at: <https://files.digital.nhs.uk/publicationimport/pub09xxx/pub09300/hse2011-methods-and-docs.pdf>

²⁶⁷ Standardization of Spirometry, 1994 Update. American Thoracic Society. Am J Respir Crit Care Med 1995 September 01;152(3):1107-1136.

²⁶⁸ Culver BH, Graham BL, Coates AL, Wanger J, Berry CE, Clarke PK, et al. Recommendations for a Standardized Pulmonary Function Report. An Official American Thoracic Society Technical Statement. Am J Respir Crit Care Med 2017 December 01;196(11):1463-1472.

²⁶⁹ ERS. GLI reference values. 2018; Available at: <https://www.ers-education.org/guidelines/global-lung-function-initiative.aspx>. Accessed November 15 2018.

²⁷⁰ World Health Organization (WHO). Medical center, fact sheets about cardiovascular diseases. Available at: <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs317/en/> . Accessed November 10, 2018.

²⁷¹ WHO, fact sheet top 10 causes of death. 2018. Available at: <http://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/the-top-10-causes-of-death> . Accessed November 10, 2018.

²⁷² Kligfield P, Gettes LS, Bailey JJ, Childers R, Deal BJ, Hancock EW, et al. Recommendations for the standardization and interpretation of the electrocardiogram: part I: The electrocardiogram and its technology: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association Electrocardiography and Arrhythmias Committee, Council on Clinical Cardiology; the American College of Cardiology Foundation; and the Heart Rhythm Society: endorsed by the International Society for Computerized Electrocardiology. Circulation 2007 March 13;115(10):1306-1324.

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
WP 11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers	Version: 2.0
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²⁷³ Fisch C. Clinical competence in electrocardiography. A statement for physicians from the ACP/ACC/AHA Task Force on clinical privileges in cardiology. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 1995 May 1;25(6):1465-1469.

²⁷⁴ Campbell B, Richley D, Ross C, Eggett CJ. Clinical Guidelines by Consensus: Recording a standard 12-lead electrocardiogram. An approved method by the Society for Cardiological Science and Technology (SCST) 2017. Guideline for recording standard ECG. 2017; Available at: http://www.scst.org.uk/resources/SCST_ECG_Recording_Guidelines_20171.pdf .

²⁷⁵ Kadish AH, Buxton AE, Kennedy HL, Knight BP, Mason JW, Schuger CD, et al. ACC/AHA clinical competence statement on electrocardiography and ambulatory electrocardiography. A report of the ACC/AHA/ACP-ASIM Task Force on Clinical Competence (ACC/AHA Committee to Develop a Clinical Competence Statement on Electrocardiography and Ambulatory Electrocardiography). *J Am Coll Cardiol* 2001 December 1;38(7):2091-2100.

²⁷⁶ Lundqvist A, Mäki-Opas T (eds.). Health 2011 Survey - Methods. 2016. Juvenes Print - Finnish university Print Ltd, Tampere, Finland 2016. Available at: <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-669-8> .

²⁷⁷ Heistaro S. Methodology Report: Health 2000 Survey. Publications of the National Public Health Institute, Helsinki 2008. Available at: <http://urn.fi/URN:NBN:fi-fe201204193320>.

²⁷⁸ Mason JW, Hancock EW, Gettes LS, American Heart Association Electrocardiography and Arrhythmias Committee, Council on Clinical Cardiology, American College of Cardiology Foundation, Heart Rhythm Society, et al. Recommendations for the standardization and interpretation of the electrocardiogram: part II: Electrocardiography diagnostic statement list: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association Electrocardiography and Arrhythmias Committee, Council on Clinical Cardiology; the American College of Cardiology Foundation; and the Heart Rhythm Society: endorsed by the International Society for Computerized Electrocardiology. *Circulation* 2007 March 13;115(10):1325-1332.

²⁷⁹ NHANES III, ECG protocol. 1991; Available at: <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/data/nhanes3/manuals/ecg.pdf>. Accessed November 10, 2018.

²⁸⁰ Harrigan RA, Chan TC, Brady WJ. Electrocardiographic electrode misplacement, misconnection, and artifact. *J Emerg Med* 2012 December 01;43(6):1038-1044.

²⁸¹ Surawicz B, Childers R, Deal BJ, Gettes LS et al. AHA/ACCF/HRS recommendations for the standardization and interpretation of the electrocardiogram: part III: intraventricular conduction disturbances: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association Electrocardiography and Arrhythmias Committee, Council on Clinical Cardiology; the American College of Cardiology Foundation; and the Heart Rhythm Society. Endorsed by the International Society for Computerized Electrocardiology. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 2009 March 17;53(11):976-981.

²⁸² Rautaharju PM, Surawicz B, Gettes LS, Bailey JJ et al. AHA/ACCF/HRS recommendations for the standardization and interpretation of the electrocardiogram: part IV: the ST segment, T and U waves, and the QT interval: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association Electrocardiography and Arrhythmias Committee, Council on Clinical Cardiology; the American College of Cardiology Foundation; and the Heart Rhythm Society. Endorsed by the International Society for Computerized Electrocardiology. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 2009 March 17;53(11):982-991.

²⁸³ Rose GA, Blackburn H., Gillium RF, Prineas RJ. Cardiovascular survey methods. World Health Organization - Monograph Series, Volume No. 56; 1982.

²⁸⁴ American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Data Standards (ACC/AHA/HRS Writing Committee to Develop Data Standards on Electrophysiology), Buxton AE, Calkins H, Callans DJ, DiMarco JP, Fisher JD, et al. ACC/AHA/HRS 2006 key data elements and definitions for

D11.3 - Report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies	Security: Public
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electrophysiological studies and procedures: a report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Data Standards (ACC/AHA/HRS Writing Committee to Develop Data Standards on Electrophysiology). *Circulation* 2006 December 5;114(23):2534-2570.

²⁸⁵ Garcia-Niebla J, Llontop-Garcia P, Valle-Racero JI, Serra-Autonell G, Batchvarov VN, de Luna AB. Technical mistakes during the acquisition of the electrocardiogram. *Ann Noninvasive Electrocardiol* 2009 October 1;14(4):389-403.

²⁸⁶ Rudiger A, Hellermann JP, Mukherjee R, Follath F, Turina J. Electrocardiographic artifacts due to electrode misplacement and their frequency in different clinical settings. *Am J Emerg Med* 2007 February 1;25(2):174-178.

²⁸⁷ Thaler T, Tempelmann V, Maggiorini M, Rudiger A. The frequency of electrocardiographic errors due to electrode cable switches: a before and after study. *J Electrocardiol* 2010 December 1;43(6):676-681.

²⁸⁸ Salerno SM, Alguire PC, Waxman HS. Competency in interpretation of 12-lead electrocardiograms: a summary and appraisal of published evidence. *Ann Intern Med* 2003 May 6;138(9):751-760.